

ABOVE ALL THAT IS BELOW · CRISTINA SANUY HERETER

ABOVE ALL THAT IS BELOW
Cocktail Parties with invisible urban animals

CRISTINA SANUY HERETER

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ELISAVA Faculty of Design
and Engineering of Barcelona

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Supervised by Dr. Manuela Valtchanova and Dr. Roger Paez

To Damià, Manuela, and Roger
for being my travel companions.

« We must first blow, in fancy, a soap bubble around each creature to represent its own world, filled with the perceptions which it alone knows. When we ourselves then step into one of these bubbles, the familiar meadow is transformed. Many of its colorful features disappear, others no longer belong together but appear in new relationships. A new world comes into being ».

J. V. UEXKÜLL,
A Stroll Through the Worlds of Animal and Men

Abstract

Above all that is below presents theoretical and practical arguments based on a mixed exploration of the fauna inhabiting the sewers of Barcelona. It is established on the hypothesis that the visibility of these species - *invisible animal city dwellers* - can influence the growth of future urban environments. To address this, current underground tracking technologies have been analyzed to propose a non-invasive one, research has been conducted on the role of multi-species design in reinventing the common environment, and sound has been used as an instrument to suggest new ways of reshaping future cities. Using the *Cocktail Party* effect to categorize recorded sounds in a controlled environment (the sewers of Barcelona), where sound becomes a generative tool that places all species on the same level of analysis, the audio recordings have been triangulated to obtain the exact positions of the emitters, and sound cartographies have been developed that directly correlate the underground and the surface. From this design proposal, the aim is to identify the inhabitation dynamics of the urban subterranean fauna to suggest new practices of multispecies urbanism.

(1) Glossary

MULTISPECIES DESIGN

It is the theoretical framework to support the shift towards more biodiverse habitats. It provides a foundation for rethinking the participation of non-humans in design and related processes, promoting the consideration of both needs.

URBAN ENVIRONMENT

It refers to the built and developed area that comprises a city. It includes buildings, streets, parks, infrastructures, transportation systems, and all the features associated with metropolitan life. This environment is usually characterized by the presence of a variety of social, economic, and cultural functions, as well as a high concentration of human activities.

UNDERGROUND URBAN FAUNA

Refers to the various forms of animal life that inhabit the urban underground, such as tunnels, caves, soils, and other subterranean structures. These species can range from small insects and arachnids to larger mammals like moles and shrews. They play an important role in underground ecosystems by contributing to nutrient cycling and soil aeration, among other functions.

METROPOLIS

A large city, typically the principal city of a region or country, serving as an economic, cultural, and political center. These urban areas usually have a high population density and are characterized by a variety of commercial, industrial, cultural, and social activities.

URBAN SUBSOIL

The space underground within a city, where infrastructures such as tunnels, sewers, and utility cables are located.

INVISIBLE URBAN ANIMAL

A coined term referring to animals that inhabit the urban underground, such as mice, rats, moles, and other species that are less visible—or invisible—to surface-dwelling urbanites, yet play an important role in the ecosystem of the large city. Also referred to as non-human emitter and underground urban fauna.

MORE-THAN-HUMAN

The concept of more-than-human refers to a way of thinking and understanding the world that goes beyond an exclusively human perspective. This term is often used in disciplines such as ecology, philosophy, anthropology, and cultural studies to highlight the interdependence and connection between humans and other entities in the world, including animals, plants, objects, technologies, and other forms of life.

SONIC CARTOGRAPHY

It is a graphic representation of a space that incorporates information about the sounds heard in that space. This representation may include recordings or descriptions of ambient sounds, or characteristic sounds of the place. It is a graphical way of capturing and sharing the soundscape of a specific location.

NON-HUMAN AGENT

Refers to any organism that does not belong to the human species, *Homo sapiens*. It includes all other living beings, such as animals, plants, fungi, bacteria, and other forms of life. The concept of non-human is often used in contexts where a clear distinction is needed between humans and other living beings or vice versa, whether for scientific, philosophical, or ethical reasons.

(II) List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

GPS: Global Positioning System.

RSSI: Received Signal Strength Indicator.

IMU: Inertial Measurement Units.

KPI: Key Performance Indicators.

ICA: Independent Component Analysis.

BSS: Blind Source Separation.

OPM: Object Process Methodology.

TOA: Time Of Arrival.

FFT: Fast Fourier Transform.

WAV: Waveform Audio Format.

SD / STD: Standard Deviation.

GND: Ground.

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The invitation

When we talk about the underground environment of the big city, two images automatically come to mind: the subway and the sewer system. Although there are many types of urban subsoil—services, foundations—and all of them can be interconnected, this work focuses on the sewers. Because it is the most stigmatized, the most distant, and, of course, the underworld itself.

The city of Barcelona has more than 1,700 km of sewers. A distance similar to that from Plaça Catalunya to Alexanderplatz. Considering that the width of the city—from Collserola to the sea—is 7 km, there is quite a maze of tunnels beneath our feet. This invention by the Babylonians to use the subsoil of their cherished city as a service is undoubtedly a whole world to discover¹. The grand comparison has always been with something terrifying, dangerous, satanic, foul, disgusting, evil, dark, and a long list of adjectives all along the same line of praise. In fact, when the Spanish *brought* potatoes to Europe, the French and Germans refused to consume them because they were seen as devil's beings, as they grew underground and had a strange shape. So much so that they called them *pommes de terre*, hoping that associating them with an apple would change their perception (The London Review and Weekly Journal of Politics, Literature, Art, & Society, 1862, p. 84).

The sewer imaginary to this day makes us think that if we venture into this space of the big city, we will encounter *Balrogs* and *Uruk-hai*, a giant basilisk, psychophonies of all kinds, Persephone herself, albino alligators, Judas goats, subterranean cannibal humanoids, and an extensive bestiary of fantastic and, of course, very dangerous beings. Although I am sure that the city of *Flushed Away* is hidden there, that a pastel-toned scene from the cozy-game *Stardew Valley* with the smell of strawberry pie appears around a corner, and that a very friendly rat and badger navigate through the streams of our waste. At least, that's what I thought when I embarked on this journey².

The sewer system is for the curious. With a quick search on the internet, you can discover that three rats eat as much organic matter as a human, becoming, along with other species, part of the ecosystem that cleans up much of the city's waste. We could say that cleaner than them, there are few beings.

¹ Information received from the BCasa technician who accompanied us during the installation of the microphones in the sewer system (May 2024 ,28, Barcelona).

² In order of appearance, the references of the mentioned characters: *The Lord of the Rings* (Tolkien, 1991); *Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets* (Rowling, 2014); *The Metamorphosis of Persephone: Ovid and the Self-Conscious Muse* (Hinds, 1987); *The Truth About Alligators in the Sewers of New York* (Kilgannon, 2020); *Mimic* (Del Toro, Mimic, 1997); *C.H.U.D.: Cannibal Humanoid Underground Dwellers* (Cheek, 1984); *Flushed Away* (Fell & Bowers, 2006); *Stardew Valley* [PC version] (Barone, 2016); *The Wind in the Willows* (Grahame & Bransom, 1908).

It can also be found that sewers harbor toxic gases such as methane, sulfuric acid, and carbon monoxide, among others³. The latter can be deadly, causing the so-called sweet death —although down there, death would be anything but sweet. This topic of gases allows us to introduce multispecies design through the historical tradition of miners, who used canaries to warn them of underground mortality. These poor caged birds would fall when they smelled danger, as it was the sense of smell that could warn of this imminent peril. The sentinel species: an undeniably more-than-human concept. A clear example that multispecies design is not always ethical and animalistic.

From a cross-disciplinary field in industrial design engineering and product design, with experience in multispecies design developed through participation in related workshops, I propose a research project that provides a new map of the city of Barcelona regarding the sewer system and the fauna that inhabits it.

Making subterranean urban fauna visible allows us to perceive the reality of this invisible part, as well as the collective issues addressed to build a general identity. Starting from a methodological proposal to know the animals of this hidden Barcelona —unexplored until now— the aim is to discover the autonomy of the underground city, with its own structure, entity, identity, and logic. Instead of an alternative or complementary urban system to that of the surface, the sewer system can be seen as an active and growing reality that develops a dimension in depth, forming part of the complete city.

This study presents both theoretical and practical arguments based on mixed research, combining qualitative and quantitative methods. It focuses on the installation of microphones in a controlled space to record environmental sounds, and by using the Cocktail Party effect to categorize and subsequently triangulate them to obtain their position in space, it aims to make *invisible urban animals* visible through cartographies that directly correlate the subsoil and the surface. To do this, current underground animal tracking technologies have been analyzed, research on the role of multispecies design to reinvent the common environment has been conducted, and sound has been reconsidered as a tool that places all beings on the same level of analysis, aiming at new ways to reformulate the cities of the future.

The purpose of this investigation is to make visible the presence of subterranean animals in the metropolis, as well as their movements, positions, and interactions within this environment. Through the proposed technology, the aim is to identify the occupancy

³ Information received from the technician of Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua (BCasa) who accompanied us during the installation of the microphones in the sewers (May 2024 ,28, Barcelona).

dynamics of these animals, with the objective of informing how urban growths could be rethought from a multispecies design perspective, pointing to potential more-than-human urban planning practices. However, this technology does not work like the drums to call the worms of Dune (Herbert, 1983), nor am I the Pied Piper of Hamelin. If only. We shall see what appears in the visitable section (spaces over 1.3 m) granted by the Barcelona City Council for less than 24 hours, amid hellish lights and the noise of humans under stress.

The goal is to hypothesize a relational framework for reconciliation discourses between the surface and the subsoil. But, how can we understand and adapt to the way of life of the subterranean ecosystem, and why is it important? Imagine it like the *Holodeck* (Allen, Fontana, & Roddenberry, 1987), but instead of holograms allowing you to dive firsthand into "inaccessible" life scenarios, it's about cartographies generated from sounds collected in these scenarios. Understanding and adapting to this sub-world is important because it hosts many plants, animals, and architectures that our eyes do not see. By exploring vulnerability and interconnectedness in urban settings, we can provoke new ways of addressing the nexus between the visible and the invisible, and generate new and unexpected ecologies. And someday, finding Cocktail Parties on *Eventbrite* or *Meetup* among urbanites of all kinds.

Above all that is below is, in fact, a Cocktail Party to which you have been invited. It takes place in a controlled environment within the sewers of Barcelona, and the guests are only the *invisible urban animals* and us. You must be careful because any kind of sound is analyzed. Where conversation and gazes are factors that can trigger new imaginaries of multispecies urban futures, and the gossip of the next day will reveal everything that happened at the event but was invisible to our eyes. This work does not intend to establish a new science but to build a solid foundation for a long, firm, and undoubtedly exciting investigation.

Research Challenge

Coexisting with wildlife in large cities is one of the study challenges of this project. Experts are beginning to communicate the need to rethink metropolitan environments to accommodate the different species that inhabit them, from the development of more green coverages to the possible implementation of biological corridors so they can reach urban green spaces (Costa, 2024). Given this situation, what can animals do if their presence in cities is impeded? What spaces are left for them to inhabit? As our presence expands, interactions with wildlife will become increasingly frequent. Environmentalist and president of *Galanthus Natura*, Sergi García (2024), discusses the ongoing development of the urban environment, driven by the rise in housing prices. He has questioned how it is possible to hear more frogs in Barcelona's parks than in the Llobregat Delta, which should be full of frogs and tadpoles. This is because urban gardens use fewer pesticides and the underground water often has better quality than that of the protected delta spaces.

Moreover, in the contemporary city, there has been a notable development underground, with significant exploitation of the possibilities it offers, mainly driven by the widespread use of construction techniques that make this space more accessible in terms of cost and means. Nowadays, the utilization of underground spaces (public or private, occasional or permanent) is growing, and with the generalization of artificial ventilation and lighting, there is an intensification in the use of plots, particularly in more central areas. According to Rosina Vinyes i Ballbé (2015), this trend has led to a surprising change in the urban landscape, with most constructions developing underground volumes, often in considerably larger proportions than the surface structures. This situation raises important questions about the direction of this process and its implications for urban sustainability and progress.

Another significant challenge in this context is the investigation of animal movement and behavior in underground environments. So far, most studies have focused on tracking animals when they are on the surface, without being able to automate the tracking of their underground activity. The attenuation of radio waves by the layers of earth makes it difficult to effectively monitor underground animals, and until now, the technology tested has always been invasive. This limitation represents a significant gap in our understanding of the behavior and habits of these animals, as well as in our comprehension of how their underground presence impacts the urban ecosystem and the quality of life of its inhabitants. Therefore, developing innovative and ethical systems to locate and monitor these underground animals will advance our ability to manage and design more sustainable urban environments in harmony with the wildlife that inhabits them.

In summary, the way contemporary cities are growing poses significant challenges to their sustainability and advancement, while directly affecting neighboring wildlife (Worrall, 2018). This is evident in places like Barcelona, where we are seeing significant changes in how we use the environment in a more ethical⁴ and ecological way. However, this development also makes us realize how much we still need to understand about the underground world, especially about the animals that live there. We need to find innovative ways of tracking and better understanding how their presence affects the balance of life in the city.

Methodology

The methodology of Rafael Pozo (2023) has been used as an inductive approach for conducting exploratory research, facilitating the development of the contextual framework and guiding initial decisions. This method addresses the fundamental question of how to reach the study area, establishing a connection between the literature review and the selection of the study area through the course on *Research Methodology in Design*.

Following the guidelines of Hernández and Mendoza (2018), the method used at various stages of the research has been required to be verifiable and explanatory in the case of qualitative approaches, and observable and measurable in quantitative approaches. The methodological contribution of Cross (2001) has also been considered, which establishes a relationship between design and science, emphasizing the need to define intuitive methods for advancement. Additionally, the work of Roca & Mensa (2009) has been taken into account, highlighting the importance of creativity in academic publication through the use of empirical methods and quantitative results. Based on the concept of 'rational method,' an approach has been adopted that promotes the generation of ideas and concepts through their combination, even allowing adaptations to the method itself. The exploratory phase of the research has been conceived as qualitative, focused on interviews, without intervening in or contaminating the environment.

For the design of the research activity, especially in obtaining qualitative results, a series of steps have been followed, including the exploration of information from a macro perspective, the delimitation of the study area, the definition of a micro perspective of observation, the description of the interaction of the study subjects, and the proposal of a working structure for the development of the research.

⁴ The concept of *ethics* is understood by considering its evolution over time and the personal definition of what it entails, being aware that the more empathy we have, the more aware we become of the impact we cause.

The adopted methodology is mixed, combining qualitative and quantitative approaches. In the qualitative aspect, a study of the state of the art in multispecies design and underground animal tracking technologies, along with relevant historical studies, has been conducted. Regarding the quantitative approach, the creation of an underground tracking system using the Cocktail Party effect has been implemented to make visible the fauna present in the urban subsoil, generating diverse data for potential cataloging and monitoring through sound cartographies. Additionally, sound cartographies will be created as a tool to communicate the obtained data to the urban public, and speculative fabulation (Haraway D. J., 2016, p. 213) and anticipatory narratives (Caplliure, 2023) will be used in subsequent steps to foster discussions about coexistence between the surface and the subsoil in future urban environments.

Special attention has been given to the ethical implications of the research, aiming to develop non-invasive technologies that decode urban underground systems, to promote bio-diverse metropolises and objectively understand subsoil fauna. An interdisciplinary approach combining scientific research with the development of sound cartographies, expert interviews, and design and engineering-based research is also promoted to generate comprehensive knowledge on the topic under study.

Figure 1 presents a graphical representation of the research's contextual framework, positioning multispecies design as the central theme of the study. It follows a process from macro to micro to adequately develop this section. The three defined subjects are: surface human dwellers (visible), underground animal dwellers (invisible), and data engineering, representing the researcher's observational position. The challenges and research question are framed within the latter, as they are proposed and resolved from this specific perspective. This diagram has been generated using the 6W method to establish all the definition points of the work, which can be consulted in Annex 1.

On the other hand, Figure 2 is an organizational chart illustrating the various work methods used in the research project, providing a structured view of the different phases and procedures to ensure optimal development of the work. The main research question, along with secondary questions, corresponding objectives, and associated methodologies, are represented in Table 1. Finally, the research project plan, represented by a Gantt chart, can be consulted in Figure 3. This diagram details the proposed timeline for the completion of the various project phases.

Figure 1
 Graphical representation of the research's contextual framework.

Note. Graphical representation of the research's contextual framework, used as a hypothetical scenario where the interaction of a specific set of study subjects is manifested. It aims to expose the synergies between the subjects, as well as all information and data that are directly or indirectly related within their individual and collective environments. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 2

Organigram of Working Methods.

1 EXPLORATÒRIA

ENGINYERIA + ARTS I HUMANITATS
ENGINYERIA DE PRODUCTE
DISSENY MULTIESPÈCIE / FAUNA SUBTERRÀNIA
SUBSOL DE BARCELONA

2 GENERATIVA

Procés de disseny:

- **Explorar** projectes sobre el disseny multiespècie en entorns urbans subterranis.
- **Documentar** els mètodes de monitoratge d'animals subterranis.
- **Analitzar** en profunditat cadascun dels mètodes trobats.
- **Sintetitzar** els mètodes escollits.
- **Dissenyar** la tecnologia a utilitzar.
- **Prototipar** la tecnologia i dur a terme primeres proves funcionals.
- **Formalitzar** la tecnologia i instal·lar-la a la zona d'estudi.

M.5 - Assaigs

ASSAIG A Punt N° 1

Recollida de dades mitjançant el prototip.

ASSAIG A Punt N° 2

Recollida de dades mitjançant el prototip.

Resultats A

Resultats B

Pre-resultats

3 EVALUATIVA

M.6 - Projecte de Disseny

M.7 - Avaluació de Resultats Model analític

Resultats

Conclusions

Aportació

Recomanacions

Camí Futur

Redacció MEMÒRIA

Note. Organigram of the working methods to be used in the research project, following the guidelines of the method proposed by Rafael Pozo (2023). Source: Own authorship (2024).

Table 1

Main and Secondary Research Questions, with Corresponding Objectives and Methodologies.

Pregunta Principal	Objectiu Principal	Metodologia
La visibilitat dels <i>urbanites animals invisibles</i> pot condicionar el creixement d'entorns urbans futurs?	Generar discursos multiespècie per al creixement urbà futur	Anàlisi de l'espai genèric
Pregunta Secundària	Objectiu Secundari	Metodologia
Nivell EXPLORATORI		
Com s'adapten/reformulen les grans ciutats actuals al flux exponencial d'animals salvatges?	Anàlisi de l'estat actual de la problemàtica	Representació del marc contextual i revisió de la literatura
Quina és l'ètica animal envers els animals salvatges en entorns urbans?	Ajuntar informació	Entrevistes a experts i revisió de la literatura
Nivell GENERATIU		
És possible visibilitzar la fauna subterrània (<i>urbanites animals invisibles</i>) amb una tecnologia no invasiva?	Projecte de disseny + Realització del prototip	Recollir dades mitjançant el prototip / Treball de camp
De quina manera es visibilitza el subsol urbà amb una tecnologia de rastrejament d'animals subterranis no invasiva?	Generar informació i dades inèdites	Assaig A + Assaig B
Nivell GENERATIU		
Com es pot comunicar el coneixement generat als <i>urbanites humans</i>?	Proposar un nou model generatiu	Avaluar: Catalogació, cartografies sonores

Note. Main and secondary research questions, with their respective objectives and methodologies, following the guidelines of the method proposed by Rafael Pozo (2023).

Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 3
Gantt chart.

- █ Presa de dades (40%)
- █ Anàlisi de dades (40%)
- █ Diagnosi Urbana (20%)

- A** Informe de recerca
- B** Primer prototip funcional i aproximació a la recollida de dades / ToC i draft de memòria (primera redacció general)
- C** OPM / Software de catalogació de sons / Aplicació per instal·lació de sensors
- D** Desenvolupament del software de rastreament de posició
- E** Entrevistes amb experts i escriptura sobre la primera part
- F** Instal·lació del prototip en espai controlat
- G** Anàlisi dels resultats
- H** Escriitura sobre la segona part
- I** Realització de cartografies sonores
- J** Escriitura sobre la tercera part
- K** Consolidació de la memòria final

Note. Gantt chart used to develop the research project. Source: Own authorship (2024).

First part

The subjects:
The invisible urban animals

FIRST CHAPTER

ON MULTISPECIES DESIGN

Introduction to the discipline

Ivica Mitrovič (2023) presents multispecies design as an emerging and necessary discipline in a world increasingly aware of the interconnectedness between humans and other forms of life. It invites us to consider not only human perspectives but also those of non-human agents with whom we share our environment. This project delves into the development of a multispecies design perspective through experimental practice, situated at the transdisciplinary intersection of engineering and product design. In this research, design is conceived as a tool to evaluate the function and purpose of objects not only from a utilitarian perspective but also from their symbolic significance and their potential for re-signification in relation to non-human presences.

Mia Roth and Tonči Čerina (2023) explain that this discipline envisions futures where humans and non-humans coexist and collaborate in shaping their shared environments. Experimentation with multispecies representation methods allows for the construction of inclusive narratives that reflect the complexity and richness of interspecies interactions. Thus, the visibility of other beings becomes a powerful tool for better understanding non-human perspectives and designing with them in mind.

Multispecies design questions whether, as humans, we can adopt other forms of being and perceiving to create a design culture that celebrates the life of any kind of being. This transition clearly requires a paradigm shift, moving from an anthropocentric design practice centered exclusively on human interests to an ecocentric practice that addresses the diverse tensions of multispecies coexistence. This new approach to design must be aware of relationships and their constant development, prioritizing them over mere existence.

Examining environmental issues from a more-than-human perspective can introduce alternative scenarios compared to those envisioned through technocentric approaches. This leads us to the question posed by Matthew Rimmer (2013), based on the work of artist Patricia Piccinini, about how contemporary technology and culture change our

understanding of what it means to be human, and how our relationships —between people and other beings, between beings and the environment, between people and their own bodies, and between the artificial and the natural— are intrinsically connected to what we create and our responsibilities towards it.

Multispecies design provides a tangible model for how practices and systems can be more sustainable and equitable. Demonstrating the benefits of an approach centered on interdependence and biodiversity can inspire and catalyze broader changes in how we design and manage our social and environmental systems. Design-driven research, committed to experimenting with ways to engage with more-than-human dynamics, based on speculation and embodied in participatory actions, has the potential to initiate future resiliencies and coexistences that serve both as case studies and guides for rethinking more inclusive urban futures (Mitrović, Roth, & Čerina, 2023).

Through current design conventions, we have managed to include many humans (though not all), but very few non-human creatures, modifying the natural patterns of the places where we live to fit an exclusively human vision. Mitrović (2023) argues that a designer is, or should be, someone who transfers methods, tools, and techniques to the community while facilitating an understanding of the processes occurring around us and revealing the anatomy of the system itself.

Multispecies design is a practice based on creating systems, artifacts, or spaces that benefit multiple species, regardless of their form of life. The methodology applied in this discipline is based on the idea that healthy ecosystems depend on the interconnectedness and interdependence of various beings. Therefore, the needs and behaviors of all species are considered when creating any project. For example, this might involve integrating natural habitats for local wildlife in urban areas, designing gardens that attract pollinators, or creating architectural structures that provide refuge and food for various species.

A notable example is the practice of product designer Gionata Gatto. Gatto (2019) employs a unique methodology in her projects, which involves tracking plant collectives through multiple locations and actors she frequents in her daily life. This method fosters a sustainable way of thinking, cultivating reciprocal relationships in the multispecies landscapes of the Anthropocene. This approach not only promotes sustainability but also enriches the understanding and appreciation of the interspecies dynamics that shape our shared environments.

The methodology of multispecies design aims to go beyond traditional design practices by integrating ecological awareness and a deep consideration of the needs of all forms of life. This perspective not only has the potential to create more inclusive and sustainable spaces but also invites us to rethink our relationships with the natural world and to value the interdependence that sustains life on our planet (Gatto & McCardle, 2019).

Connection with other disciplines

Multispecies design involves a systemic shift, recognizing the interconnections between different aspects of a system and addressing environmental and social issues from a global perspective. This discipline integrates ecology, biology, philosophy and ethics, architecture, anthropology, and sociology, among others, to understand complex systems and develop integrated solutions (Mitrović, Roth, & Čerina, 2023).

Ecology

Geographer and ecologist Franklin Ginn (2014) proposes an ethics based on the emotional entanglement of life, suggesting that connection invites us to care for each other. This perspective complements Fritjof Capra's (1997) concept of the web of life, which describes the interrelationships between psychological, biological, physical, social, and cultural phenomena, providing a foundation for sustainable ecological policies. Capra highlights essential processes such as photosynthesis, nutrient and water cycles, soil formation and conservation, atmospheric gas regulation, global climate control, waste decomposition, and pest and pathogen control. All these processes result from the activity of organisms on Earth.

Biology

Biologist Mark Bekoff (2007) emphasizes the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration to understand various aspects of animal behavior and cognition. Through cognitive ethology—the branch of biology concerned with the influence of consciousness and intention on animal behavior—Bekoff explores the lives of other species, presenting extraordinary stories about animal joy, empathy, pain, shame, anger, and love, and comparing them with recent scientific research that confirms the existence of emotions suggested by common sense and experience for centuries.

Philosophy and ethics

Eduard Kohn (2013) emphasizes that philosophy and anthropology have not yet fully explored how other beings constitute what it means to be human. He asserts that all beings have the capacity to think and discusses how they achieve this. Kohn introduces the concept of the ecology of the self, describing it as follows: « If selves are thoughts and the logic through which we interact is semiotic (the study of signs and symbols and their use or interpretation), then relationship is interpretation ». (2013, p. 83).

In the field of ethics, an interview was conducted with Marta Tafalla (full transcript in Annex 2), a professor of philosophy, ecological ethics, and animal ethics at the University of Barcelona. Tafalla proposes normalizing encounters with wild animals, arguing that we have always coexisted with them. The problem, she says, is that we have eliminated much of the wildlife in cities, creating a human monoculture with little space for domestic animals. She advocates for reclaiming the forgotten and changing attitudes to, at the very least, share space, which requires environmental education to learn how to respect their habitat. A study conducted by the University of British Columbia (2024) published a few months ago demonstrates that wildlife is more sensitive and cautious in the face of human activity.

Donna Haraway (2013) makes philosophical contributions to debates on animal rights and ethics, and how we treat our companion species (domesticated animals). Her book works by making connections, attempting to respond where curiosity and sometimes unexpected care lead. Haraway asserts that our political and ecological situation urgently needs a closer look at interrelationships, to awaken and dramatize sensitivity to extinction, the disappearance of species, and our ways of remembering them. She states, « I do not advocate soul-cleaning through hygienic reformism. I advocate understanding that heterogeneous earthly beings are together in this web forever, and no one gets to be human » (2013, p. 82). Relationships between species have often represented welcoming versions of coexistence. Haraway argues that this usually opposes a policy of excluding nature, advocating for an ethics that is more than betrayed but still largely human.

Architecture

A notable example of architecture within the discipline of multispecies design is permacultural architecture. Through the creation of integrated mimetic systems that allow nature to replant and root itself in urban environments, this approach offers an innovative way to adapt cities with agricultural productive capacities. The environment becomes a tapestry where each thread is vital to the whole (Rothe, 2014).

Anthropology

Martin Ávila (2022) reflects on how humans have repeatedly questioned the nature of the objects around us, pondering what a thing is. Both in nature and in cities, we constantly interpret spaces to make sense of our surroundings and access resources. This practice of interpretation is common to all living beings. Ávila asserts that in urban environments, we share an understanding of how places function based on physical constraints and the agreements we make about various codes and symbols.

Anthropologist Tim Ingold (2011) discusses this conscious exploration of the perception of the environment as a new understanding of movement, knowledge, and descriptions, listing several factors to carry it out: the vitality of materials; the perception and formation of the ground; the blending of Earth and sky in the meteorological world; the experience of light, sound, and feeling; the role of storytelling in integrating knowledge; and the potential of drawing to unite observation with description.

Within anthropology, ethnography helps us understand how humans have been formed and transformed amidst encounters with multiple species. However, it is important to note that in traditional ethnography, humans are the agents around whose actions and intentions the narrative is constructed. Anthropologist Eben Kirksey (2010) discusses the need for multispecies ethnography—a new genre of writing and mode of inquiry that studies the multitude of organisms whose lives and deaths are intertwined with human social worlds, shaped by political, economic, and cultural forces. This approach explores contact zones where the lines between nature and culture have broken down, where encounters between *Homo sapiens* and other beings generate mutual ecologies and co-production niches, fostering what is known as biocultural hope. This exploration raises fundamental questions that serve as the basis for multispecies design: « Which beings thrive and which fail when the natural and cultural worlds collide? Who benefits when species meet? ». (Thalhammer, 2023, p. 67)

Eduardo Viveiros de Castro (2009) uses animistic thought as a fundamental study to understand interspecies relationships, conducting research on how Amazonian people see the world from this perspective. They do not only relate to non-humans as a food source but also as connections in many areas, arguing that one can better understand themselves by trying to see the world through the eyes of other creatures. They use shamanic rituals to make this connection tangible and define who they are by understanding what differentiates them from others.

Sociology

Sociologist Sebastian Abrahamson (2014) asserts that the notions of companion species (domesticated) and their bond with humans have polarized towards a version of pleasant coexistence, playing with the similarity between the terms *pleasant* and *pleasing*.

Nature and culture

Multispecies design promotes harmonious coexistence among humans, animals, and plants, questioning the dominant paradigm of separation between nature and culture. This discipline, aligned with cultural geography—the study of the relationship between culture and place—is considered essential for overcoming the anthropocentric view that has led to environmental degradation and biodiversity loss. Promoting biodiversity and interactions among species can contribute to the resilience of ecosystems in the face of environmental changes, a key aspect for adaptation and survival in a constantly changing world. The interconnection between nature and human civilization can be profound and complex. Ecology not only analyzes nature but also studies the interactions between human society and its natural environment. Social dynamics, political and economic systems, and the human relationship with nature have mutually influenced each other over time.

This relationship has often been conditioned by social factors that have impacted ecological science and sought to justify an ethical relationship with nature. At the same time, ecological science has shaped our perceptions of nature and promoted new ethics, with varying degrees of success (Mitrović, Roth, & Čerina, 2023). Ecologist and visual artist Paula Bruna (2022) explores the relationships between society and its environment, arguing that as humans, it is impossible to completely abandon the anthropocentrism that characterizes us. Thus, she tries to go beyond human limits to approach non-human viewpoints. By catalyzing organic processes and observing their interactions, recording them through photography, illustration, and writing, she creates maps with this information to make them visible and spark debates.

Practices of care, such as the implementation of formal laws like the Rights of Nature, along with the valorization of culture through narratives and social constructions, can contribute to reshaping structural power issues and highlighting relational values, both with the land and with other beings. Lígia Oliveira (2023) invites us to reflect on how to define a good relationship to collectively reconnect with nature. She highlights values such as trust, respect, reciprocity, acceptance, and care. It may seem uncomfortable to

consider these values in the context of a river, a rock, a fish, or a tree, but they are essential for a more integral approach to our work practice.

Questions can be directed to other beings: people, plants, mountains, oceans. What do they need? The willingness to show curiosity and empathy is crucial: to question and think critically. Julie Whitburn (2020) invites us to ask: What would nature do? How would nature design? This reflection involves not only the final result but also the process itself. There are numerous examples of exploration towards specific relationships between a species and humans, such as the crow, Arctic fish, and even slugs that come out at night in domestic gardens in Great Britain⁵.

Philippe Descola (2013) offers a reformulation of the dichotomy between nature and culture. Through the observation and description of communities, he defines four ways of relationship (ontologies): totemism (of Australian Aboriginals, where humans and non-humans are grouped according to their moral and physical properties), analogism (from China, West Africa, Mexico, and Peru, where the world is understood as an infinity of singularities), animism (from the Arctic and the Amazon, where it is believed that non-humans have life), and naturalism (of modern Western culture, where it is understood that only humans have life).

An ethical approach to nature recognizes that all living organisms and ecosystems have intrinsic importance and inherent value. All living beings and their natural environment are interconnected and should therefore be considered as part of an integrated system. This approach postulates that every component of ecosystems has value and that humans should preserve the integrity and stability of these systems, rather than destroy them for personal interests (Descola, Lloyd, & Sahlins, 2013).

In contrast to this ethic, there is the utilitarian ethic, which promotes human dominance over nature and utility as the fundamental principle of human action. According to this perspective, anything that benefits the human being is considered morally permissible. This ethic has its roots in Christianity and other monotheistic religions, which present the human being as the ruler of nature. According to this view, humans should shape an earthly paradise, a civilized landscape that must be protected from the "wild" nature described by Darwin. Nature is perceived as an untamed force that threatens civilized society; civilization is defined as a separation from nature (Oliver, 2021).

⁵ In order of appearance, the references for the mentioned works are: Crow Cosmopolitics (Morley, 2023); Fish Pluralities (Todd, 2014); Sticky Lives (Ginn, 2013).

Personal journey in the discipline

After drafting this brief essay on multispecies design, I would like to share various encounters that have sparked my interest in this field and have provided prior experience for conducting research of this nature.

Feral Drifting with Lonja Wetlands

In July 2023, participating in the workshop "Feral Drifting with Lonja Wetlands: Fragments of More-than-Human Cohabitation" at Lonjsko Polje Nature Park (Croatia), as part of the 18th Venice Architecture Biennale, marked a significant deepening in the discipline of multispecies design. This workshop was organized by the Open Forest Collective (2023) and brought together various participants interested in more-than-human relations.

During this workshop, the dynamics of cohabitation with nature were explored, with special emphasis on the experience of the Lonja wetlands and the river that characterizes them, shown in Figure 4. Through multisensory activities, the aim was to understand and interact with the environment more deeply. One of the highlights was the analysis of the observatories that become part of the landscape, allowing us to better contemplate and understand life in the natural park.

Inspired by local artistic strategies and the movements and rhythms of the wetland creatures, a different perspective was adopted to explore the possibilities of more attentive cohabitation. The space-time was navigated globally and participatively, seeking collective understanding and knowledge that included other non-human beings, primarily using the site's observatories to interact with the landscape and its agents, as shown in Figure 5.

One of the notable outcomes of the workshop, in which professionals from various disciplines participated, was the creation of a game to communicate the simultaneous expressions of life and death in the wetlands, shown in Figure 6. Inspired by the traditional shoemaker's game, it served as a tool to understand the complexity of the wetlands and foster debate about their conservation and understanding. Through the stories generated in this game, reflections were made on the ephemeral nature of life and death in the wetlands and their relationship with other species.

Figure 4. *The Sava River, Lonjsko Polje, Croatia.* ◀

Note. The Sava River flows through the wetlands of Lonjsko Polje Nature Park in Croatia.

Source: (Open Forest Collective, 2023).

► Figure 5. Lonjsko Polje Observatory.

Note. One of the observatories at Lonjsko Polje, designed by architects Mia Roth and Tonči Čerina (2023) for the Croatian pavilion at the 18th International Architecture Exhibition of the Venice Biennale. Source: (Roth & Čerina, 2023).

▼ Figure 6. The Shoemaker's Game of Life and Death.

Note. Development and details of the Shoemaker's Game of Life and Death created by the Fire Group as a result of the Feral Drifting with Lonja Wetlands workshop, conducted as part of the 18th International Architecture Exhibition of the Venice Biennale. Source: Own authorship (2023).

The Vulture Eatery

Another encounter with multispecies design took place on Thursday, March 2024 ,28. It was in the form of a unique experience in the Vall Fosca, Lleida, known as the Vulture Dining Room. This activity, held in the village of Torre de Tamúrcia, provides a fascinating view of the dynamics between the local scavengers and the area's shepherds. The shepherds, aware of the problem of disposing of livestock carcasses, established the Vulture Dining Room as a sustainable solution. Through a brief explanation and a visit to the viewpoint, participants can observe how vultures feed on meat provided by volunteers from the local community center, with remains scattered around, creating a distinctive setting for the activity of these characteristic animals of the region, as shown in Figure 7. Although it is an enriching experience to understand the hierarchy among scavengers, it also sparks debates about their invasive nature and their impact on the local ecosystem.

Figure 7
Remains from the Vulture Eatery

Note. Remains from the Vulture Dining Room found around the natural setting where the activity takes place, in Torre de Tamúrcia, Vall Fosca, Lleida. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Crossover Project subject

During the period from March 19 to April 19, Manuela Valtchanova allowed attendance and participation in certain tutorials she conducted along with Nacho Antón as part of the Crossover Project course for third-year students, focusing on Multispecies Justice: Care and Indifference. These tutorials took place both at the Aigües Road (Collserola) and in the university classrooms. Each group of students (3 to 5 members) addressed various topics related to non-human agents in the Collserola park.

One group explored water scarcity in the park, designing a network suspended in trees to condense air and collect water for local use. Another group focused on protecting raptors like eagles, proposing the colonization of electric poles with mycelium to prevent electrocution. A third initiative addressed light pollution affecting owls, developing an immersive helmet for humans to transmit their nocturnal experience. Bees were another study topic, with a group investigating human pollination as a solution to the decline in local flora.

The fifth group tackled the issue of abandoned cats, proposing the creation of a semi-open leisure park for humans and cats. Microbiology was also a focus, with a group creating candy sculptures to visualize microorganisms in the park. The seventh group concentrated on erosion issues, experimenting with ecosystem creation through interactions between humans, wild boars, and soil. Other projects included a post-apocalyptic viewer to generate visual narratives on pollution and a rave at a landfill to promote waste collection. The final group addressed individual waste, creating a group game to collect and categorize trash found in nature.

Overall, these projects explore interactions between humans and non-human agents in Collserola park, offering creative solutions and generating ethical debates about our impact on the natural environment. A detailed exploration of this experience can be found in Annex 3.

Conclusion

Multispecies design, which involves considering the needs and interactions between species, is fundamental in an increasingly interconnected world. Although design has traditionally been anthropocentric, it is crucial to recognize the importance of coexistence with other living beings. The theoretical framework has been defined by exploring references across various disciplines in the field, using the generation of thematic visual maps which can be found in Annex 4.

Given that humans have left less than 3-2% of the world's ecosystems intact (Carrington, 2021), it is believed that permanent human-made architectures must also prioritize neighboring species. While science cannot accurately predict which species will be among the estimated 25% likely to survive the next mass extinction, there is broad consensus that survival rates after collapse may be linked to two main factors: size and the ability to collaborate with other species, as noted by Harriet Harriss (2023). If any human survives,

it is likely to be the most cooperative, as the ability to collaborate will be a key factor in survival (Mitrović, Roth, & Čerina, 2023).

Anthropologist Anna Tsing (2012) analyzes the relationship between capitalist destruction and collaborative survival in multispecies landscapes, being a prerequisite for continuing life on Earth. She does this by exploring the entire history of a single species of fungus while investigating the concept of companion species (Haraway D., 2013) to take us beyond familiar companions into the rich ecological diversity without which humans cannot survive.

As the world's landmass becomes increasingly uninhabitable, with about 4 million km² of land lost or degraded annually due to desertification (The World Counts, 2024), nature urges us to shift from competition to coexistence.

In this scenario, design is argued to play a crucial role. Designers are presented with the opportunity to create shared spaces that meet the diverse needs of all involved species. This could translate, for example, into hybrid structures in urban parks that not only benefit humans but also provide habitats and resources for local wildlife. This collaboration with nature is an essential response to the climate emergency, which is already pushing different species into unusual proximity to each other (Costa, 2024). Figure 8 artistically represents the idea of a shared space between human and non-human agents, exemplifying the terrace on the 3rd floor of ELISAVA as a specific place where multiple species reside, and for this reason, and understanding the context within a design university, it encourages constant rethinking.

Figure 8. *Non-Human Agents of ELISAVA.* ◀

Note. Illustration created as an artistic representation of the non-human agents inhabiting the 3rd-floor terrace of ELISAVA, according to personal imagination. Source: Own authorship (2024).

The invisible urban animals

The other neighboring beings —the invisible urban animals— that inhabit cities, as well as any other place, experience these environments according to their own perceptual and behavioral capacities. Whether humans wish to communicate with them or not, there are always interpretations of things created by humans from the perspective of these other species. They navigate these spaces using their own skills, adapting to circumstances and utilizing available resources. However, when they encounter a lack or disappearance of essential elements, such as increasingly scarce or non-existent resources, human constructions displace them, disregarding their needs, making them more vulnerable. This vulnerability can have serious consequences, endangering the lives of these species and contributing to the loss of biodiversity (Brussels Sewer Museum, 2024).

In this rupture of interdependencies, life is at risk. The disappearance of these species represents a threat to life, whether human or otherwise. Their extinction and our lack of recognition of their lives signify a setback for life itself. Just as with other common aspects like air, water, or food, to name a few essentials, interdependencies make them possible, as all are formed by mutually constitutive processes. Kriti Sharma (2015) asserts that things only exist due to the dependence on other elements, in a continuum of coexistence with non-living entities (Sharma, 2015).

An approach to rats

Given that none of the 8 billion humans have so far provided a large-scale functional solution to the climate problem caused by our species and fueled by selfishness, it seems reasonable to learn from other, less destructive and more adaptive species for survival. Non-human species, such as rats, have shown remarkable ability to adapt to environmental changes and survive in urban environments (Brussels Sewer Museum, 2024).

Unlike humans, rats generate a much smaller amount of natural waste⁶, feeding on it without wasting anything. For example, an average human (conscious of the often unacknowledged bias caused by excessive Western consumption) produces tons of general waste⁷ over their lifetime, while rats feed on many types of waste. Moreover, when laboratory rats are released into the wild, even those born in captivity quickly adapt back to natural conditions (Brucker, 2023).

Although rats are a specific example of invisible urban animals, many other species inhabit urban environments invisibly and go unnoticed by humans. Many of these species are subterranean, residing in sewers, subway tunnels, and other underground spaces that humans rarely access. These spaces lie beneath our feet, where animals coexist with us and inhabit the city in an exact negative of our reality.

Therefore, it is essential to recognize the importance of these non-human species and understand how our actions affect their lives and their environment. Their presence in urban environments not only enriches biodiversity but also provides environmental benefits, such as waste management. Their survival is crucial for maintaining the health of urban ecosystems, and their adaptability serves as a reminder of the resilience of life in all its forms (Brucker, 2023).

⁶ Waste generated by the body itself.

⁷ This includes not only the waste generated by the body but also any type of waste produced after use by a human.

This research focuses on the sewer system as a type of underground space, and it is in this context where, due to ignorance, lack of interest, or quantity and dissemination (BCasa, 2019), there is a general assumption about rodents—and cockroaches, though to a lesser extent—being the primary species inhabiting these areas. This is why this chapter primarily discusses rodents, as they are the most stigmatized invisible urban animal. However, it is important to consider that invisible urban animals comprise a complex bestiary of beings yet to be discovered, which is the ultimate goal of this research.

The Brussels Sewer Museum and *Rattus*

The following outlines the initial in-depth contact with rats. The research began with a general interest in invisible urban animals and led to a visit to the *Rattus* exhibition (Brussels Sewer Museum, 2024) on March 2024 ,12. This exhibition took place at one of the two sewer museums in Europe and is the only one on the continent that also addresses subterranean urban fauna with a temporary exhibition specifically focused on rodents. This experience provided valuable information about rats and their role in the urban ecosystem.

The exhibition highlighted that rats, like many other non-human species, have developed the ability to adapt to urban environments. Despite their relative invisibility, these species interpret and navigate human constructions according to their own needs and skills. The lack of resources and the disappearance of essential elements make these species vulnerable. Their disappearance represents a threat to biodiversity and life in general, as all species are interconnected and depend on each other for survival (Brussels Sewer Museum, 2024). But how much do we really know about them? Can we achieve a state of peaceful coexistence with rats? (Hinton, 1918).

A meeting was scheduled with Sophie Vanderschueren, who is responsible for the museum's scientific projects. Sophie provided a personalized tour of the museum and a discussion on the water cycle, sewage treatment, and the role of rats in the sewer system. This experience was crucial for a better understanding of the importance of these species in the urban ecosystem. The full transcript of the interview can be found in Annex 5. The temporary *Rattus* exhibition (running from September 2023 ,15, to June ,16 2024) at the Brussels Sewer Museum offers an educational approach to the brown rat, or *Rattus Norvegicus*, highlighting its adaptability to urban environments. Rats inhabit the city's sewer system, where they enjoy constant warmth and humidity and feed on food scraps that reach the sewers. Despite their negative reputation, rats are extraordinarily adapted to the artificial environment of cities and human consumption patterns.

The exhibition aims to dismantle some stereotypes about rats and promote a more peaceful coexistence with these often-maligned creatures through an explanatory and educational tour that delves into many of these aspects, supported by a collection of catalogs and booklets that function as communication tools and theoretical extensions of the discussed points (Figure 9).

The museum also organizes workshops and activities related to the species, such as observing rodent skulls, classifying rodents, thematic storybook reading clubs, puppet making, and an introduction to comic art. Additionally, on February 23, a conference titled "Towards Sustainable Rat Management in the City" was held, discussing the need to manage the presence of rats in a more ethical and sustainable way, rather than exterminating them.

We inquired about obtaining a recording of the conference, but we were informed that the speakers did not wish to share their presentations due to the sensitive nature of the topic in some cities (e.g., Paris), and thus the session was not recorded.

The exhibition concludes with a series of projections by Tomas Jean (*La Minute Sauvage*, 2023). Tomas promotes the observation of wildlife in urban environments, and as part of the activities proposed within the framework of the exhibition, he conducts a workshop titled "On the Lookout!" outside the museum walls, which is presented in the museum's brochures as a discovery of the secrets of the species living in the city center (Brussels) and their remarkable ability to adapt to human activities, construction, and urban development. In addition to this, he will also soon conduct a workshop on the relationship between our food and rats (and what rats eat). Annex 6 contains all the images taken at the *Rattus* exhibition used to draft the presented information, and Annex 7 features the permanent sewer exhibition, which was instrumental in understanding and deciding the type of subterranean space to investigate.

The proposal of a near-citizenship

To conclude the chapter, we address the issue raised by Donaldson and Kymlicka (2018) regarding liminal animals—those that have adapted to living among humans due to the encroachment upon their traditional habitats. They explain that these animals are subjected to a wide range of abuses and injustices, and our relational obligations towards them are often not recognized. The invisibility of these animals not only implies indifference but also delegitimizes their presence in urban environments. We see them as invaders of our territory, which justifies the use of extermination measures.

They also argue that it is essential to understand that many of these animals have no other place to live, and extermination campaigns are morally indefensible and often ineffective. We need to consider the possibility of recognizing these animals as permanent residents of urban environments and ensuring that they can maintain their independence.

► Figure 9. *Communicative Elements of the Rattus Exhibition*.

Note. Catalog, brochure, and tickets from the temporary *Rattus* exhibition held at the Brussels Sewer Museum (Musée des Égouts). Source: Own authorship (2024).

They reflect on the concept of quasi-citizenship (between exclusion and full citizenship) for these invisible urban animals: « One problem we have already pointed out is that these animals are invisible in our everyday worldview. Given the dichotomy we draw between nature and human civilization, urban space is defined precisely in opposition to something wild and natural. And for this reason, we do not see liminal animals, at least not when thinking and talking about how to design and govern our societies » (2018, p. 370). It is emphasized that recognizing their presence and importance in urban ecosystems is crucial, and understanding that their survival is linked to ours. A more ethical and sustainable coexistence with these species is advocated, learning from them and adapting our practices to ensure a more harmonious future for all city inhabitants.

The invisibility of these animals not only implies indifference or negligence but also results in the delegitimization of their very presence. We see them as outsiders or invaders of our human territory, to which they have no right to access, let alone inhabit. Consequently, we create a range of extermination tools to achieve this form of *animal ethnic cleansing* (Donaldson & Kymlicka, 2018). But, as Figure 10 represents, we are likely more similar to rats than we think.

Figure 10
Modulor Rat.

CHAPTER TWO

ON TRACKING SUBTERRANEAN ANIMALS

Introduction to the practice

Tracking subterranean animals is a research area aimed at understanding the dynamics of urban biodiversity and the hidden ecosystems existing beneath our cities. In the subterranean environment, humans rarely interact directly with the species that inhabit it. These creatures, including rodents, insects, and other animals, live their lives in a parallel world, unknown to most surface dwellers. Nevertheless, these animals play an essential role in maintaining urban ecosystems, participating in processes such as waste decomposition (Brussels Sewer Museum, 2024).

The study of subterranean animals in sewers —the named *invisible urban animals*— requires specific tracking methods and technologies adapted to the unique conditions of this type of underground environment, as shown in Figure 11. Through these methodologies, researchers can gather data on the populations, behaviors, and movements of these species, contributing to a deeper understanding of their ecology and interactions with the urban environment.

This chapter delves into the various techniques and approaches used to track subterranean animals, highlighting the challenges and difficulties associated with this research. Case studies will be provided to illustrate how these methodologies have been successfully applied to reveal the complexity and diversity of subterranean life. Furthermore, the importance of recognizing and protecting these species in the context of urban planning and public space management will be discussed, with the goal of fostering a more harmonious and sustainable coexistence between humans and the subterranean animals of the city.

Research in the field of tracking subterranean animals not only offers a more comprehensive view of urban ecosystems but also encourages us to reconsider our perceptions and relationships with these hidden city inhabitants. By exploring subterranean spaces, we can appreciate the biodiversity that sustains urban life and the interdependence among all forms of life sharing the environment of the great city (Costa-Pereira, Remington J., Brett R., & Jetz, 2022).

Study cases on animal tracking

The fascinating history of tracking wildlife through automation with technology begins with *Monique, the space deer* (Movebank, 2024). From the earliest rudimentary techniques to the sophisticated current tracking systems, Ben Goldfarb (2024) explores how technology has changed the way we understand and protect wildlife. This includes the development of the Movebank platform (2024), a key resource for animal tracking researchers. Movebank is a free online archive of wildlife tracking data used by researchers to manage, share, protect, analyze, and archive their data (Pevzner & Carlisle, 2017).

The investigation and tracking of animals, particularly in subterranean environments, have seen remarkable advancements with the application of various technologies and monitoring systems. An example of this progress is the case study of shark tracking near the Bahamas (Welch & Mittermeier, 2023), where a tracking system using satellite receivers has been implemented for uninterrupted tracking of these animals from space. This system promises a greater understanding of shark movements and behaviors, with potential implications for marine life management and ecosystem conservation.

Similarly, in the tracking of aquatic animals, whale tracking has experienced significant advancements thanks to the use of acoustic technologies. A notable example is the use of hydrophones to capture the underwater sounds emitted by whales, allowing scientists to track and study these marine mammals in detail. Project CETI (2024), for instance, is applying advanced machine learning techniques and robotics to interpret and understand the communicative codes of sperm whales. This technology not only allows for locating whales but also studying their social interactions and behaviors through the sounds they emit, facilitating a deeper understanding of their lives and habits. These advancements have important implications for marine conservation, as they provide crucial data for the protection of endangered species and the management of marine ecosystems (Hauer, Nöth, & Barnhill, 2023).

On the other hand, the advancement in the ICARUS project, a global animal tracking platform using satellite technology, is significant in the field of animal tracking technologies. The launch of a new, more efficient satellite receiver is highlighted,

► Figure 11. *Visit to the Barcelona sewer system.*

Note. Photograph taken during the first visit to the Barcelona sewer system on October 2023, 21, an activity organized by BCASA (Barcelona Water Cycle, SA). Source: Own authorship (2024).

allowing for faster and more accurate data collection on the migratory movements of a wide range of species. This system provides a detailed view of animal behavior and migration patterns in real time, playing a key role in ecological and conservation research. The work emphasizes the international collaboration within the project, which brings together researchers from around the world to better understand animal movements and migrations on a global scale (Müller & Avolio, 2023).

Another case study also using satellite technology highlights the use of a network of 100,000 animals connected by trackers, observed from space, to understand animal behavior patterns. This network can be instrumental in predicting events such as volcanic eruptions, extreme weather phenomena, and emerging diseases, demonstrating the potential of tracking technologies for scientific research and natural resource management (Ponsford, 2022).

Current underground tracking technologies

The study and tracking of the movements of underground animals are critical for understanding their behavioral patterns and ecology. Currently, various methodologies are employed to locate and monitor these animals in their underground habitats. These techniques include the Global Positioning System (GPS), Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) localization, acoustic localization, inertial measurement unit (IMU) navigation, and magneto-inductive localization. Each of these methods presents advantages and limitations, varying in terms of accuracy, energy consumption, adaptability to underground environments, and infrastructure requirements.

GPS

The Global Positioning System (GPS) can determine location with an accuracy of 5 meters anywhere in the world. However, from the sensor's perspective, it has the drawback of consuming a lot of energy to obtain these data, especially if the device restarts. Modern receivers must be used with a battery, and in the lowest power mode, they use about 8 milliwatts of energy, meaning that each time location is determined, about 3 milliampere-seconds of energy are consumed, which is a high factor, leading to a short battery life. Additionally, GPS cannot be used underwater or underground and can have large errors when used under thick cover due to signal interference (Khraisat, Al-Khateeb, Abu-Alreesh, Ayyash, & Lahlouh, 2011).

RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) localization

This method, popular in the wireless sensor network community, involves a device capturing the intensity of reference signals (beacons) and using this information, along with a signal loss model, to calculate its location. The advantage of this method is that no additional sensor is needed, as it uses the same radio module the device already has. Furthermore, it allows multiple devices to collaborate in finding their location without needing more equipment. One of the problems with this technique is that obstacles and interference can add a lot of noise to the signals, making the measurement less accurate. This method does not work well underground or underwater because radio signals weaken significantly in these environments (Patwari, Ash, & Kyperountas, 2005).

Acoustic localization

This technique is based on the time it takes for an acoustic signal to reach its destination, generally in the ultrasonic part of the spectrum. Although it can be determined by two-way acoustic communication, it is more common in sensor networks to emit a radio signal and an acoustic signal simultaneously. The time it takes for the acoustic signal to reach its destination is proportional to the distance between sensors but also depends on the ambient temperature as this affects the speed of sound. This method is much more accurate (up to centimeters) than radio signal-based localization, but it has disadvantages such as the need for special machinery and a limited range of a few meters due to the loss of strength of the acoustic wave (Savvides, Han, & Srivastava, 2001).

IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) navigation

A method that allows tracking devices with very high temporal accuracy is inertial navigation. This method uses a triaxial accelerometer and a magnetometer to determine the displacement of the device from an initial position. The main disadvantage is that due to the double integration of the accelerometer signal, errors propagate quadratically, causing the error to accumulate over time. Without a correction method, this error can continue to increase indefinitely. Additionally, devices must operate continuously, generating a large amount of data that must be retrieved in some way. This method has been successfully used underwater (Elkaim, Decker, Oliver, & Wright, 2006).

Magneto-inductive localization

This technique uses low-frequency loop antennas to measure the strength of the magnetic field, enabling precise tracking without interference from soil or water. Animals wear collars with sensors that record the magnetic field intensity, and the data is processed to estimate their position. Although it has a limited range, the technology is simple and inexpensive, with low-energy-consuming receivers. It is used in biology and ecology to study burrowing animals like badgers and moles, as it allows for collecting data on their movements when they leave their burrows. Magneto-inductive localization is effective underground, underwater, and in the air without needing recalibration (Markham, Trigoni, Ellwood, & McDonald, 2010).

A comparison has been made regarding the invasiveness of each technology as a determining factor for their use (Table 2). Additionally, Table 3 compares the main five methods of tracking underground animals presented, considering the principal key performance indicators (KPIs) that are crucial for evaluating which technology is most suitable for the research project.

Table 2
Comparison of the invasiveness of the main methods for tracking underground animals.

	Invasiveness	Method
GPS	Yes	The receivers are placed on the animal.
RSSI	Yes	The receivers are placed on the animal.
Acoustic loc.	Yes / No	A sensor is required if the technology is used as previously proposed (emitting a sound and analyzing when it is received). It is proposed to analyze the sounds emitted by the animals themselves to calculate the distance between the emitter and the receiver (us).
IMU	Yes	The receivers are placed on the animal.
MI loc.	Yes	The receivers are placed on the animal.

Note. The table assesses whether different tracking methods –GPS, RSSI, acoustic localization, inertial measurement unit (IMU), and magneto-inductive localization– are invasive or not. Invasiveness refers to whether the method requires placing devices/intervening on the animal's body or if no intervention is needed. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Table 3
 Comparison of the main methods for tracking underground animals.

	Why it is used	Physical principle	Necessary elements	Advantages	Limitations
GPS	Because it provides very precise localization outdoors.	Uses signals emitted by satellites to calculate the receiver's position through triangulation.	GPS receiver, antenna, GPS satellites.	High precision outdoors.	Ineffective at >1m underground, in buildings, or covered areas.
RSSI	To measure distance based on signal strength.	Measures radio signal strength to estimate the distance between the emitter and the receiver.	Radio emitters and receivers, RSSI sensors.	Low cost and simplicity.	Limited precision and susceptibility to signal interference.
Acoustic loc.	To determine distances using sound.	Uses the propagation of sound waves and the time of arrival to calculate distance.	Acoustic emitters and receivers, microphones.	Effective in mediums where sound propagates well.	Limitations in mediums with high sound absorption or poor acoustics.
IMU	To monitor animal movement and posture.	Uses motion sensors like accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers to measure movements and orientation.	Accelerometers, gyroscopes, magnetometers.	Works anywhere, not dependent on external signals.	Cumulative error in data integration over time.
MI loc.	To locate objects in mediums like water or soil.	Uses magnetic fields to induce signals in specific sensors to calculate location.	Magnetic field generators, magneto-inductive sensors.	Magnetic fields penetrate well in mediums like water and soil.	Limited detection radius and technical complexity.

Note. The table evaluates the main tracking methods presented, including GPS, RSSI, acoustic localization, inertial measurement unit (IMU), and magneto-inductive localization. It describes the physical principles that make them possible, the necessary elements for their operation, the reasons for their use, their advantages, and limitations. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Ethics in tracking

It is crucial to evaluate and address the ethical challenges associated with tracking sewer animals, ensuring that the scientific or conservation benefits justify any potential negative impacts on the animals and their environment. This might involve establishing rigorous ethical protocols, continuously monitoring the animals' welfare, and considering the legal and ethical aspects related to animal research. Donna Haraway (2013) emphasizes the importance of proper ethical consideration in cases where human action negatively affects animals. She highlights the need to kill (or, in this case, track) consciously and intentionally, assuming our position of non-innocence, as opposed to making animals "killable" (trackable) without reflection or purpose. This reflection leads us to question whether the tracking of underground animals is carried out ethically, and whether the humans involved in this task are fully aware of its consequences. A philosophical, political, and social framework is necessary to delve into these ethical issues and assess whether the process is conducted appropriately. By addressing these questions, we can seek ways to improve these practices from an ethical and moral standpoint.

It is also crucial to consider the ethical aspect concerning people who may be involved in sewer activities. We must be aware that this underground environment may be inhabited by homeless individuals (Tierney, 1990) —also known as *mole people*— or by those engaging in various practices within this specific space. Exposing them to tracking technologies may raise relevant ethical questions, including respecting their privacy and dignity, as well as the potential psychological or emotional impact of being subjected to such surveillance. Ensuring that investigations are conducted responsibly and that the welfare and rights of all involved individuals are considered, along with the ethical implications of the data collected and the study's outcomes, is essential. This may include implementing protocols for filtering based on the type of sound and transparently communicating the research objectives and results, focusing solely on the subterranean urban fauna.

Conclusions

Traditional methods of observing animal behavior can influence the subjects' behavior or be biased by the observer. Automatic sensing reduces these problems by standardizing data collection and allowing observation without requiring active and constant involvement. Automatic tracking enables the observation of animals over long periods without interruption, revealing how they interact with each other and their environment. However, carrying devices may alter the animals' behavior. These aspects and others must be considered to select the optimal technology and design an action methodology to achieve ethical tracking practices.

All the methods discussed (except acoustic localization, if modifications are made to the technology used) require capturing animals to place and retrieve devices, which can be very invasive. It is essential to validate automatic data with direct observations to ensure reliability. Clearly defining social interactions based on the animals' natural behavior, not just the collected data, is also crucial (Smith & Pinter-Wollman, 2020).

In summary, radiofrequency-based methods face issues with uncertain and highly attenuating communication channels, making localization difficult or even impossible underwater or underground. Dead reckoning offers excellent short-term precision but suffers from cumulative drift. Magneto-inductive localization, although limited in range, penetrates soil and water with minimal attenuation. Additionally, it has the advantage of consuming very little energy, making it highly useful for animal tracking, but it is invasive and thus not used as a tracking method in this work. In contrast, acoustic localization is precise, cost-effective, and non-invasive. This technique uses the propagation of sound waves to measure distance, placing acoustic receivers at various points. By analyzing the sound emitted by the animal from three different points and triangulating it, we can determine its exact position without inserting devices into the animal's body, making it a non-invasive technology. Moreover, sound has suitable characteristics for this type of project, as it places all species (human and non-human) on the same level of analysis. For these reasons, acoustic localization is the preferred method, detailed in the following chapter.

Part Two

The event:
The Cocktail Party

CHAPTER ONE

ABOUT SOUND

Introduction to the sense

In the context of *Above all that is below*, sound takes on a new dimension. While traditionally studied as an audible phenomenon for humans, in this project it is used as a tool to discover the presence and behaviors of the *invisible urban animals* that inhabit Barcelona's sewers. This involves a deep understanding of key acoustic concepts such as frequency, amplitude, and sound propagation to interpret and categorize the signals analyzed with the Cocktail Party effect.

So, what is the nature of sound? Sound is understood as the transmission of vibrations through an elastic medium such as air, water, or any solid; that is, sound cannot propagate in a vacuum. To be perceptible to the human ear, this transmission of energy must fall between 20 and 20,000 Hz (Garrett, 2020).

Figure 12 shows a schematic representation of sound transmission. The brown dots represent particles of the medium, which vibrate within an elastic medium (e.g., air), while the yellow line indicates the sound source, i.e., what produces the sound (the emitter). Each point oscillates around its resting position, and the frequency of this oscillation determines the sound frequency: 50 oscillations per second correspond to 50 Hz, while 1000 oscillations per second correspond to 1000 Hz. Thus, the vibration is transmitted successively from one particle to another, allowing us to perceive sound. On the other hand, the sound wave is determined by the density of the medium's particles, represented by the sinusoidal wave shown over the points in dark brown. We define wave amplitude as the magnitude of the vibrations that determine the intensity or volume of the sound. It is measured in decibels (dB), with larger amplitudes corresponding to louder sounds. Wave length is understood as the distance between two consecutive points on a sound wave. This length is inversely related to frequency: at higher frequencies, the wavelengths are shorter, and vice versa.

Figure 12
Schematic representation of sound transmission.

Note. Schematic representation of the transmission of sound energy between particles forming an elastic medium, along with the representation of a sound wave to relate particle density to sound.
Source: Own authorship (2024).

Audio is sound that has been processed for transmission, recording, or playback. An audio signal is any sound pressure interpreted by a system. A clear example of this can be found in a recording studio: a singer's live voice is an example of sound, but it becomes audio when the sound vibrations are captured, interpreted, and processed by a microphone. Sound is a constant in our environment, as vibrations continuously occur in elastic media. However, audio, as we perceive it today, is not always present. For instance, when we listen to background music while reading this text through speakers or headphones, an audio signal is being processed to allow us to hear the sound. Thus, while sound is always present, audio only becomes present under certain circumstances.

On the other hand, noise is characterized as an unwanted or uncontrolled sound that can be perceived as annoying, irritating, or disruptive. Often, noise consists of a variety of frequencies and can be generated by sources such as traffic, industrial machinery, electronic devices, or any other non-musical events. The fundamental difference between sound and noise lies in their subjective perception and the purpose of their generation. While sound can be pleasant and desired, noise is generally considered intrusive and unwanted.

Focusing on the concept of sound, it can be described through various characteristics that influence its perception and quality: Timbre is the quality of sound that allows distinguishing between sounds of the same frequency and amplitude but emitted by different sources. It is determined by the combination of harmonic frequencies and their relative intensity.

Duration refers to the length of time a sound lasts. This characteristic is relevant for the perception of rhythms and the distinction between short and long sounds. Finally, temporal spacing is the distribution of time between successive sound impulses. This aspect is fundamental for the perception of rhythm and cadence in music and other artistic forms.

The sound in sewers

The acoustic conditions of sewers are characterized by high reverberation due to the long, narrow tunnels made of hard materials like concrete, which reflect sound, creating prolonged echoes. According to studies such as those by Kirill Horoshenkov (2021), underground sewers provide a certain degree of acoustic insulation from surface noise, but within the system, sound propagates effectively through water and air, increasing reverberation due to the low sound absorption of the materials used. Additionally, the channeling effect of the tunnel design allows sound to travel long distances without dissipating much, as noted in an EPA report (Dan, Skipper, Weimer, & Donovan, 2014) on acoustic technologies for sewer assessment, which mentions that sounds can effectively transmit through these systems, facilitating the detection of anomalies like blockages or leaks. These unique conditions make the sewer system an interesting environment for the application of acoustic inspection technologies.

Integrating sound theory into the project allows for generating knowledge about subterranean urban fauna and their relationships with the urban environment. This opens the door to new practices in multi-species urban planning, where city design considers the needs and interactions of living beings, including those not visible to the naked eye. Sound theory has applications across a wide range of fields, including music, sound technology, medicine, and industry. Designing optimized acoustic systems is a complex and multidisciplinary area that encompasses physical, psychological, and technological aspects. Understanding these fundamental principles is crucial for the effective application of acoustic concepts in various practical applications. Psychoacoustics, for example, is the discipline that studies how the brain processes and interprets sound stimuli. This discipline provides a deeper understanding of how we perceive sound and how factors such as intensity, frequency, and duration influence our auditory experience (Garrett, 2020).

Sound is chosen as the analytical tool for this project not only because it serves as an instrument for exploring and understanding natural environments, but also because it can act as a change agent in the perception of the relationship between living beings, including humans and subterranean urban fauna, to promote systemic change in the

city. In this new perspective, sound theory is redefined as a tool that transcends the boundaries between humans and other living beings.

An example of the generative use of sound in sewers is the film *Mimic* (Del Toro, 1997). In this film, sound is prominently used to intensify the narrative of a pandemic caused by mutant cockroaches in the sewers of New York City. Dr. Susan Tyler creates a biological species (the Judas species) to eliminate the plague, but these creatures evolve and become a new threat to humans. The film uses sound to heighten tension, such as when an autistic child replicates the creatures' sounds with spoons, reflecting how sound can reveal the hidden presence of dangers beneath the city. Darkness and sounds, like the unsettling murmur of moving creatures or the echoes in the underground tunnels, become key generative tools for creating an atmosphere of suspense and terror. This use of sound in the film underscores its importance by demonstrating how acoustic elements can enrich the understanding and experience of subterranean spaces.

In this research project, the application of Kalman filter technology (a linear method used by NASA) was proposed, but its use is not feasible for this study. Our senses are complementary and highly integrated, similar to NASA's sensors on their space robots, which include GPS, accelerometers, and vision, among others. However, all these sensors are imperfect and have some form of error. The Kalman filter automatically adjusts the weighting given to each of these sensors to determine a location or state with greater accuracy. For example, our perception of being in a place is based on both what we see and the information we receive from GPS. The filter adjusts the importance given to each source of information according to its accuracy at each moment (Li, Li, Ji, & Dai, 2015).

This concept of sensory complementarity is reflected in the example from the book *Nunca sabrás a qué huele Bagdad* (Tafalla, 2011), which discusses anosmia, or the absence of smell, and how other senses compensate for this lack. In a noisy and crowded environment, we not only use hearing to identify who is speaking to us but also rely on sight to better understand what is being said. This sensory integration, however, would not be possible if we had only one sense.

In the context of sound as a generative tool, it is important to understand that the theory behind the Kalman filter cannot be applied in the same way when only one sense is available. Thus, this work explores how sound can generate knowledge and experience in the absence of other sensory sources, highlighting its unique importance and limitations when not complemented by other types of perception.

Within the framework of the project *Above all that is below*, sound becomes an equalizing tool, acting as a democratizing element that does not prejudice appearance or behavior, while also revealing what lies beneath the city's surface, with the aim of addressing certain ways to manage it. It is proposed to conduct an acoustic survey of the subterranean city before implementing other actions to reinvent the shared environment, understanding the interrelation between the environment and the agents that inhabit it. The next chapter provides an in-depth definition of the sound tracking technology used in the research project.

CHAPTER TWO

ABOUT THE DECIPHERMENT

This chapter presents the technology used to achieve the stated objectives. This technology is based on two fundamental methods: the Cocktail Party Effect and sound triangulation for precise localization of sound sources. The former performs the separation and classification of individual sounds in noisy environments, facilitating their detailed analysis. On the other hand, acoustic triangulation allows us to accurately determine the position of each identified sound source, adding a spatial dimension that enables tracking. The operation of this technology is detailed below, using as an explanatory case the experimentation conducted in two controlled areas (the author's residence and that of the neighbor in the lower apartment) on May 2024 ,15, functioning as a scenography that evokes the comparison between the subsoil (referred to in this specific case as the First Floor) and the surface of the large city (referred to as the Second Floor).

The technology. System modeling

To model and visualize the technology for tracking subterranean animals, the Object Process Methodology (OPM) has been applied. This methodology has enabled a design process adapted to the project's needs. OPM is an integrated framework for modeling complex systems, combining the structural and behavioral aspects of a system into a single coherent representation. It involves creating diagrams that describe the objects in the system, their characteristics, and the essential processes affecting these objects. This methodology facilitates the understanding, design, and analysis of complex systems, providing a global view that integrates static and dynamic information. It is particularly useful in fields such as systems and data engineering, where clear and effective communication between various disciplines is crucial for optimizing design and engineering.

In OPM diagrams, three main components are distinguished: objects, represented by rectangles, which can be tangible or intangible; processes, represented by ovals indicating transformations or activities that modify the aforementioned objects; and relations, which are either of necessity, represented by a line with a circle indicating that an object or process is required for the completion of another process, or of result, represented by a hollow arrowhead indicating that a process leads to an object or another process, showing the sequence of transformations within the system (Dori, 2002).

Figure 13 schematically and essentially shows the OPM diagram applied in the context of the research, where the initial sound is the object to be processed using the Cocktail Party Effect to classify it into various sound groups based on the emitter, requiring the sound in a necessity relationship. Subsequently, the categorized groups are processed by triangulating these sounds to obtain the exact position of the emitters.

Figure 13
General diagram of the Object Process Methodology (OPM).

- Tangible / intangible **object**
- Transformation **process** of the object
- ... is necessary for ...
- ▶ ... results in ... (*yields*)

Note. General diagram showing the essential Object Process Methodology (OPM) of the project, where sound is processed resulting in the formation of sound groups and the determination of their position. Objects and processes are represented respectively by rectangles and ovals, while necessity and result relationships are shown with lines and arrows. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Subsequently, Figure 14 provides an expansion of the general diagram, showing the system in detail to identify each subprocess involved in implementing the technology for the Cocktail Party Effect. Each subprocess is described as follows: first, the recorded sound is read and digitized using three microphones⁸, a recorder, and a computer; then, each sound group is categorized by Software 1, the Python code specifically designed to achieve optimal classification, where the Cocktail Party Effect is applied; once the sound groups are obtained, the sound triangulation process is performed using Software 2, code to identify the initial moment (zero time - t_0)

⁸ To triangulate sounds in a two-dimensional plane (2D cartography), at least three microphones are needed to calculate the time differences of arrival of the sounds, thus defining two circumferences that will intersect at a single point to determine the exact position of the emitter (Liaquat et al., 2021).

of each categorized sound from the three audio sources (t_{01} , t_{02} , t_{03}); next, the same code calculates the elapsed time (Δt) between each initial moment (t_{01} , t_{02} , t_{03}), obtaining Δt_{12} and Δt_{13} , and the distance difference (Δd) between them, obtaining Δd_{12} and Δd_{13} ; finally, it calculates the position (x , y) of the sounds in a 2D plane relative to each microphone through triangulation, to obtain the exact position of each emitter. The triangulation of sounds and position calculation, using Software 2, is discussed in depth in the subsection "The Triangulation of Sound Sources".

Figure 14
Expansion of the general diagram to identify the subprocesses.

Note. In the expanded diagram, it is shown how the initial sound (SO) undergoes various subprocesses including capture and digitization, categorization into sound groups, identification of the initial moments of each sound, calculation of elapsed time, and finally, calculation of sound positions. Each of these subprocesses is carried out using different components such as microphones, a recorder, a computer, and various software programs, following the necessity and result relationships defined in the OPM methodology. Source: Own authorship (2024).

The Cocktail Party effect

The Cocktail Party Effect, initially described within the field of auditory psychology, refers to humans' ability to focus on a single conversation in a noisy environment with multiple speakers. This skill has been adopted by data science and signal processing to address problems of sound source separation in complex audio recordings (Duong, 2019). In the context of analyzing sounds recorded in both controlled zones, the Cocktail Party Effect provides a theoretical and practical basis for developing algorithms capable of isolating and identifying different sound sources within a mixed recording, as visually represented in Figure 15.

Figure 15

Schematic representation of the application of the Cocktail Party effect to a mixed audio signal.

Note. Figure showing a mixed audio signal processed through the Cocktail Party Effect, resulting in various audio signals categorized by source. The categorization before the asterisk illustrates the different sources producing the sound to communicate the origin of the mixed recorded audio.

Source: Own authorship (2024).

The methodology employed in Software 1 to apply the Cocktail Party Effect to an audio recorded in a specific environment is as follows: first, the sound is recorded capturing all environmental noises, which are then digitized and converted into audio; next, source separation algorithms (in this case, Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Blind Source Separation (BSS)) are used (Lin & Tsung, 2006); using pattern recognition algorithms, the separated sounds are categorized, identifying various sources (such as animals, water, vehicles); finally, the audio is post-processed to classify the different sound sources (emitters) and visualize the results, ensuring that any ethical considerations related to privacy and minimal intervention in the animals' habitat are addressed.

Blind Source Separation (BSS) is a signal processing technique aimed at separating a mixture of audio recordings into its original sources without prior knowledge about the nature of the emitters or the mixture itself. This technique is particularly relevant in environments with specific characteristics (such as sewers), where multiple sound sources may overlap, creating a dense and challenging acoustic panorama to decipher. In the context of this project, BSS is applied to break down the composite recording into individual components, such as running water noise, sounds produced by animals, and other environmental or mechanical noises. This can be achieved through the use of algorithms like Independent Component Analysis (ICA), which decomposes the mixed signal into statistically independent components (Fischer, Caversaccio, & Wimmer, 2020).

To perform the Cocktail Party Effect using a Python coding system, a code (referred to as Software 1) has been generated that, firstly, applies the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to the WAV audio file loaded onto the computer. FFT is a mathematical tool used to analyze signals (in this case, sounds) and decompose them into their component frequencies. It also cleans the sound with a Notch filter, functioning as a selective blocker that attenuates the specific unwanted frequency, leaving the rest of the signal intact, thus removing hums (known as noise) to produce a clean audio with identified specific noises. Figure 16 exemplifies the comparison between the original signal (in WAV format) and the filtered signal obtained after applying FFT and the *Notch* filter.

Figure 16
Comparison between the original signal (WAV) and the filtered signal.

Note. The figure shows, exemplified using original data recorded in the corridor of the Second Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 17-minute (1000-second) segment, the resulting filtered signal after applying the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and the Notch filter to the recorded WAV audio signal from the omnidirectional microphone situated to the right of the recorder, setting a specific frequency of 43Hz. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Next, the three filtered WAV files are simultaneously read and a figure is generated with the respective sound waves and another with the spectrograms, as shown in Figure 17, to visually identify specific sounds based on the highest frequencies. To categorize the events, understood as each of the species' sounds in the recorded space-time, a specific threshold is first established based on the waveform's width using the mathematical tool called standard deviation (SD/STD), to understand how variable or consistent the data series is, in this case referring to the sound signal's volume, as exemplified in Figure 18. Each time this established threshold is crossed, the sound becomes an individual event to be subsequently categorized according to the sound's nature (emitter species).

Figure 17
Resulting spectrograms from filtering three WAV audio signals.

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the Second Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 17-minute fragment (1000 seconds), the resulting spectrograms of the three filtered audio sources for each of the three microphones located in the controlled experimentation area, with the first two being omnidirectional microphones and the third being the integrated microphone of the Zoom H5 recorder. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 18. *Threshold determined with respect to waveform amplitude to identify and categorize events.* ◀
Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the Second Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 30-second fragment, the threshold determined at a value of 5 (according to amplitude, in multiples of the standard deviation), to identify events occurring at a specific time. Source: Own authorship (2024).

It is important to mention that due to the temporal limitations of this research, an automated cataloging of the emitting species of each sound group could not be employed. Instead, this process was performed manually, as it was conducted in a controlled environment where the nature of each emitter was previously known. However, it is noteworthy that advanced methods currently exist, especially in the field of machine learning, which allow this task to be automated with high precision.

One of the most notable systems in this field is the *Wildlife Animal Sound Identification System*, also known as WASIS (2018). This system uses pattern recognition techniques and classifiers trained with large volumes of acoustic data to automatically identify animal species from the sounds they emit. Machine learning methods applied in this context often include algorithms such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which are particularly effective in processing images and audio and have proven to be very useful in species recognition from environmental sounds. Researchers like Stowell and Plumbley (2014) have demonstrated the effectiveness of CNNs in classifying bird sounds, while other studies have explored the use of hybrid models that combine supervised and unsupervised techniques to improve identification accuracy (Desai, Lehman, Munson, & Lawrence, 2018). These technologies not only increase the efficiency of the cataloging process

but also open new possibilities for large-scale analysis of acoustic data in biodiversity and ecological studies. Therefore, in future research, it would be highly beneficial to incorporate these methodologies for automated cataloging, enabling faster and more accurate identification of emitting species, thus maximizing the scientific value of the collected data.

Figures 19 and 20 show the individually categorized events for each of the two controlled areas, to subsequently measure the start time of each. The complete code (Software 1) used to achieve these steps can be found in Annex 8, with the respective explanations for each line of code.

First floor

- Agent 01 (Domestic dog)
- Agent 02 (Human)

2024-05-15 18:00:00 to 18:16:66

Second floor

- Agent 03 (Human)
- Agent 04 (Human)

2024-05-15 18:00:00 to 18:16:66

► Figure 19. Classification of sound groups from the first floor.

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 17-minute (1000 seconds) fragment, an identification of the events thanks to Software 1, and a manual categorization of the two agents inhabiting the controlled area during the time of the study. Source: Own authorship (2024).

▼ Figure 20. Classification of sound groups from the second floor.

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the Second Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 17-minute (1000 seconds) fragment, an identification of the events thanks to Software 1, and a manual categorization of the two agents inhabiting the controlled area during the time of the study. Source: Own authorship (2024).

In conclusion, the application of the Cocktail Party effect to audio recordings in environments such as sewers is an effective tool for identifying and categorizing various ambient sounds. Using the mentioned process, it is possible to decompose complex audio signals into individual components automatically, as well as categorize the nature of the emitting species using machine learning techniques.

The sound source triangulation

Next, we explore in detail the process of triangulating sounds in an exemplified (fictional) case, using the technique employed to determine the exact position of sound sources (the emitters: the *invisible urban animals*). This methodology consists of several key stages, from the exact placement of the microphones to solving the system of equations to obtain the precise coordinates of the emitter.

According to the technology proposed by Kraljevic & Russo (2020) and Chung & Chou (2022), a 2D study plane is considered. A 1000 x 700 grid of the controlled area where the experiment takes place is created, delimited in an 11.4 m x 4 m space, so the resulting coordinates of the emitter will have a margin of error of up to 1 cm. The position of microphone number 2 (x_1, y_1), the central one, is (650,10), considering its exact location on the map of the area drawn on the same grid. The coordinates where the other two microphones are located ((x_2, y_2) and (x_3, y_3)) must also be determined. To calculate the distance that should be between them to have a suitable resolution for the analysis, the sensitivity of the microphones used, which in this case is > 1 millisecond, is considered. The time increment (Δt) concerning the speed (v) of sound in the air (value of 343.2 m/s, considering that the ambient temperature in the sewer was calculated to be 20°C using a digital environmental thermometer when installing the microphones) and the distance considered between each pair of microphones (x) must also be considered. A distance of 2 m was determined⁹ both for the characteristics of the material (the microphones must be able to receive sounds at this distance and the wiring must allow their installation) and for the characteristics of the room.

Verifying that microphones 1 and 3 are correctly positioned 2 m linearly from microphone 2, microphone 1 is placed to the left of it, with its coordinates being (450,10), and microphone 3 to the right, at (850,10), considering the space of the controlled experiment area. It is also

⁹ To determine this value, when collecting data from the first test with the microphones, the time factor was considered, and it was identified that the time resolution was 2 milliseconds. To know the spatial resolution they have, this error of 2 milliseconds must be considered and the following equation must be made: $\Delta t \cdot v = x$, being $0.686 = 343.2 \cdot 0.002$ m. This result shows that there is a spatial resolution of 0.68 meters for the considered electronics. It is the minimum distance the microphones must be separated.

important to synchronize the microphones to ensure they all start recording at the same time. The technique used for synchronization was to use a single recorder with the three microphones directly connected to it, so the recording starts from a single device with a single recording button.

After these preliminary steps to the recording, and once it is done, the start of the events previously identified using the Cocktail Party effect must be identified for each microphone. These starts are designated as tn_1 , tn_2 , and tn_3 , with n being the event number and the numbers in the subscript indicating each of the three microphones. Once the events are identified with their respective arrival times, the start time differences (Δtn) of these are calculated relative to a specific time in the recording (taken as a reference, always with a value of 0). Next, the speed (v) of sound in the air, previously defined, is used to convert the time differences into distance differences. The distance differences determined for the three microphones for a specific event, along with the exact position of the three, are used to obtain the position of the specific emitter (x, y) of the sound group being exemplified (n). This process is called triangulation and has been carried out with Software 2, which can be found in full in Annex 9, with respective operational instructions. The development of this software is based on the triangulation methodology proposed and validated by Li & Deng (2016).

In the following figures, the individual analysis of the previously selected events can be seen, as the identification and categorization process was carried out manually. In future studies, it is intended to automate this process to achieve a more precise behavior analysis and to allow the sound mapping to show the specific path taken by the agent. It is also relevant to mention that the recording was carried out in two areas where the agents being tracked were previously determined, maintaining the anonymity of the inhabitants. Additionally, no photographs of the First Floor housing were taken, nor is the layout or location shown in subsequent maps. Thus, in Figures 21,22,23,24 i 25, the calculation of the sound arrival time concerning a specific moment in time is presented for each of the five identified events on the first floor.

Figure 21
Calculation of arrival times for event 1 (first floor).

[1]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 164.30:

- A** - Microphone 1 = 0.0066 seconds = 6.6 milliseconds
- B** - Microphone 2 = 0.0104 seconds = 10.4 milliseconds
- C** - Microphone 3 = 0.0155 seconds = 15.5 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 4-second fragment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to second 164.30 of the recording, corresponding to agent 01. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 22
Calculation of arrival times for event 2 (first floor).

[2]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 319.80:

- A** - Microphone 1 = 5.4 milliseconds
- B** - Microphone 2 = 10.3 milliseconds
- C** - Microphone 3 = 15.9 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024, 15, corresponding to a 4-second fragment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to second 319.80 of the recording, corresponding to agent 01. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 23
Calculation of arrival times for event 3 (first floor).

[3]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 457.0:

- A** - Microphone 1 = 4.8 milliseconds
- B** - Microphone 2 = 10 milliseconds
- C** - Microphone 3 = 15 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024, 15, corresponding to a 2.5-second fragment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to second 457.0 of the recording, corresponding to agent 02. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 24
Calculation of arrival times for event 4 (first floor).

[4]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 760.50:

- A - Microphone 1 = 10 milliseconds
- B - Microphone 2 = 15.4 milliseconds
- C - Microphone 3 = 21 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024, 15, corresponding to a 2.5-second fragment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to second 457.0 of the recording, corresponding to agent 02. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figure 25
Calculation of arrival times for event 5 (first floor).

[5]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 938.55:

- A - Microphone 1 = 6 milliseconds
- B - Microphone 2 = 9.5 milliseconds
- C - Microphone 3 = 14.6 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024, 15, corresponding to a 2.5-second fragment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to second 938.55 of the recording, corresponding to agent 01. Source: Own authorship (2024).

Figures 26 ,27 ,28 ,29 and 30 show the triangulation performed using Software 2 for each of the five events analyzed on the First Floor, with the aim of determining the exact position of the two occupants of the space:

Figure 26
Triangulation of event 1 (first floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 4-second fragment, the triangulation of Event 1 relative to second 164.30 of the recording, corresponding to agent 01. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 27
Triangulation of event 2 (first floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 4-second fragment, the triangulation of Event 1 relative to second 319.80 of the recording, corresponding to agent 01. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 28
 Triangulation of event 3 (first floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second fragment, the triangulation of Event 3 relative to second 457.0 of the recording, corresponding to agent 02. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 29
 Triangulation of event 4 (first floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second fragment, the triangulation of Event 4 relative to second 760.50 of the recording, corresponding to agent 02. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 30
Triangulation of event 5 (first floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the hallway of the First Floor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second fragment, the triangulation of Event 5 relative to second 938.55 of the recording, corresponding to agent 01. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Next, Figure 31 displays the complete sound map of the First Floor, featuring five identified events that allow for tracking the inhabitants of this specific space-time and analyzing their behavior. The changes in their positions within the residence can be observed.

Figure 31
Rastreament acústic del Primer Pis.

First floor

- Agent 01 tracking (Domestic dog)
- Agent 02 tracking (Human)

2024-05-15 18:00:00 to 18:16:56

Note. This figure illustrates the location of the agents based on the arrival times at the different microphones, thereby enabling precise tracking of the movements of the inhabitants on the First Floor.
 Source: Own autorship (2024).

Regarding the Second Floor, Figures 32 ,33, and 34 show the calculation of sound arrival times in relation to specific moments, for each of the three identified events carried out by agents 03 and 04.

Figure 32
Calculation of arrival times for event 6 (second floor).

[6]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 164.0:

- A - Microphone 1 = 1.8 miliseconds
- B - Microphone 2 = 7.3 miliseconds
- C - Microphone 3 = 13.1 miliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Second Floor corridor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second segment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to the 164.0 second mark of the recording, corresponding to agent 03.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 33
 Calculation of arrival times for event 7 (second floor).

[7]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 164.0:

- A** - Microphone 1 = 18.7 milliseconds
- B** - Microphone 2 = 13 milliseconds
- C** - Microphone 3 = 7.5 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Second Floor corridor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second segment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to the 320.0 second mark of the recording, corresponding to agent 04.
 Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 34
Calculation of arrival times for event 8 (second floor).

[7]

Arrival time of the sound relative to 825.0:

- A - Microphone 1 = 17.85 milliseconds
- B - Microphone 2 = 13.4 milliseconds
- C - Microphone 3 = 10.5 milliseconds

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Second Floor corridor (Barcelona) on May 2024, 15, corresponding to a 3.0-second segment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to the 825.0 second mark of the recording, corresponding to agent 03.

Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figures 35 ,36 and 37 show the triangulation performed using Software 2 for each of the three events analyzed on the Second Floor, aiming to determine the exact position of the two inhabitants of the space:

Figure 35
Triangulation of event 6 (second floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Second Floor corridor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second segment, the triangulation of Event 6 relative to the 164.0-second mark of the recording, corresponding to Agent 03. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 36
Triangulation of event 7 (second floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Second Floor corridor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 2.5-second segment, the triangulation of Event 7 relative to the 320.0-second mark of the recording, corresponding to Agent 04. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 37
 Triangulation of event 8 (second floor).

Note. The figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Second Floor corridor (Barcelona) on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 3-second segment, the triangulation of Event 8 relative to the 825.0-second mark of the recording, corresponding to Agent 03. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Next, Figure 38 displays the complete sound mapping of the second floor, with three identified events that allow for tracking the inhabitants of this specific space-time and analyzing their behavior. Changes in their positions within the residence can be observed.

The subsequent development of the sound maps, contrasting the first and second floors, and proposing alternative scenographies with the subsequent theory, is found in "Part Three: The Sound Mapping".

Figure 38
Acoustic tracking of the second floor.

Second floor

- Agent 03 tracking (Human)
- Agent 04 tracking (Human)

2024-05-15 18:00:00 to 18:16:56

Note. This figure illustrates the location of the agents based on arrival times at different microphones, thus enabling precise tracking of the Second Floor inhabitants' movements.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Conclusion

This chapter has accurately defined the technology used for the complete deciphering of sounds. The technology comprises two main components: the application of the Cocktail Party effect and sound triangulation. The Cocktail Party effect is used to categorize and separate various groups of sounds in noisy environments. This technique allows for detailed identification and analysis of individual sounds, facilitating a clear understanding of acoustic interactions. Once the sounds have been classified, triangulation is employed for each of these sounds to determine the exact position of the emitters. This process involves measuring the time differences of sound arrival at multiple microphones, allowing for precise calculation of each sound source's location. In summary, the combination of both processes constitutes an effective and essential technology for achieving the objectives of the research project, addressing the challenges of acoustic analysis in complex environments. The next chapter will detail the design process of the artifact that will record the sounds, as well as the necessary tests and adjustments to ensure optimal performance.

THIRD CHAPTER

ABOUT THE ARTIFACT

In this chapter, the selection and protective design of the microphones used for tracking the invisible urban animals are developed. The complexity of this project lies in the need to capture faint and subtle sounds from the sewers of the city of Barcelona, which requires specific precision and sensitivity in the devices used. The first step in the design process was to identify the specific requirements for the three microphones and the recorder to obtain the audio files. This includes omnidirectionality, precision, and sufficient battery autonomy to analyze a space for a determined period. A key aspect of the project was the design of the microphones' encapsulation to ensure their protection and durability. The encapsulation must protect the recorder hardware against the animals inhabiting the environment, considering that rats gnaw on any kind of material, while maintaining optimal sensitivity for sound capture. Additionally, the microphones and recorder must be elevated off the ground, as the floor is damp and there is a possibility that the water level may rise in certain specific sections, potentially covering and damaging the used material.

The functional prototype

For the first functional prototype, high-quality microphones were not used because the objective was simply to obtain audio files from three different microphones in a controlled and confined environment (the hallway of the author's residence) to test the functionality of the analysis technology (Software 1 and 2), arranged in the same manner as shown in the maps from the previous chapter. Therefore, the decision was made to use three Arduino KY-038 type microphones (basic omnidirectional Arduino microphones, the datasheet of which can be found in Annex 10, along with the necessary Arduino code to use them correctly) connected to an Arduino Due via a breadboard, which in turn was connected directly to the personal computer. Figure 39 shows one of the microphones used. As the knob located on the small green structure of the microphone board is turned, the threshold value at which they start to hear can be adjusted, following the indications of the incorporated LED.

Figure 39
Arduino KY-038 microphone

Arduino-compatible KY-038 condenser microphone. This sensor includes an integrated amplifier that allows for sound detection with adjustable sensitivity via a potentiometer. Commonly used in sound detection projects and acoustic monitoring applications. Source: Own autorship (2024).

All connections between the microphone and the Arduino Due are made through the breadboard, using the materials shown in Figure 40: the 5V reader, since the microphone requires 5V to operate, thus the 5V output of the Arduino Due board is connected to the [+] input of the breadboard; the ground (Ground - GND), which is the point where these 5V are applied, connecting to the [-] of the breadboard; and the Analog In (AI), connecting any AI_n input of the Arduino Due board to the analog output (AO) of the microphone in question, as detailed in Figure 41. The AO connection of the microphone is used instead of the digital (DO) because it sends a range of intensities, instead of sending a binary signal (based on whether it receives sound or not) as the digital does. The functional test with the three Arduino microphones was carried out in a controlled area, with the microphones placed 2 meters apart, as shown in the experimental setup in Figure 42.

Figure 40. *Materials used in the first functional prototype.* ◀

Note. The materials used in the first functional prototype installed in the hallway of the author's home. It consists of three Arduino KY-038 microphones, a breadboard, an Arduino Due, and wiring. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 41

Connection of the microphones, Arduino Due, breadboard, and computer.

Detailed connection of the three microphones and the Arduino Due connected to the PC via the breadboard. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 42

Installation of the first functional prototype.

Note. Installation of the first functional prototype in the hallway of the author's home. The microphones are placed 2 meters apart, and the PC is used as their power source to provide an instant visualization of the sound captured through the Arduino. Source: Own autorship (2024).

The simultaneous visualization of the sound captured by two microphones (microphone 1 and microphone 2) on a computer screen, using the mentioned Arduino code, demonstrates a difference in the arrival time of the sound of a hand clap. This time difference is crucial for the triangulation of sounds, as illustrated in Figure 43 in yellow. Subsequently, these data are transferred to a TXT file using the CoolTerm program, as shown in Figure 44. This file can be imported into Python for the necessary tests with Software 1 and Software 2, thus facilitating a deeper and more detailed analysis of the captured data.

Figure 43
 Visualization of the sound arrival time difference in the first functional prototype.

Note. Example of a specific categorized sound, in this case, a hand clap. The graph generated by Arduino shows the capability to record and visualize the difference in the sound arrival time at two microphones (microphone 1 and microphone 2). This information is crucial for the subsequent triangulation of the sound's position. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 44
 Exporting captured sound data to a TXT file using coolTerm.

Dades Coolterm 07042024.xlsx			
Mil·lsegons	Micròfon 1 (M01)	Micròfon 2 (M02)	Micròfon 3 (M03)
35873	786	819	873
35875	782	821	872
35877	784	821	872
35878	787	821	873
35880	782	821	872
35882	788	823	871
35883	785	821	872
35885	786	820	873
35886	787	821	872
35888	787	821	871

Note. The data captured by the microphones are transferred to a TXT file using the CoolTerm program. This file can be imported into Python, enabling the necessary tests with Software 1 and Software 2 for a deeper and more detailed analysis of the recorded sound data. Source: Own autorship (2024).

The design of the tracking artifact

After validating the technology used for triangulation with basic Arduino microphones, it was determined that the devices to be used would be Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones (Figure 45). This decision was based on recommendations obtained from the AVisual Pro store, experts in audiovisual equipment rental, who were specifically consulted about experimentation in the sewers. These experts recommended these microphones, of which two units were rented, along with a tripod for each, the corresponding cabling, and a 32 GB SD card. The technical specifications of these can be found in Annex 12.

For the central recorder with an integrated microphone, to which the two aforementioned microphones will be connected, it was recommended to rent the Zoom H5 Handy Recorder (Figure 46), which meets the specific needs of the project and its suitability for the technical requirements needed for precise sound capture in specific environments like the sewers. It stands out for its recording quality, flexibility of use, and compatibility with various accessories, making it an ideal choice to ensure maximum reliability and quality in the recorded data. This recorder aims to optimize sound capture and ensure that the obtained acoustic information is accurate and useful for subsequent analysis.

The Zoom H5 is a four-track portable audio recorder, ideal for capturing sounds with high sensitivity through the integrated microphone on top. It records audio on SD cards in mp3 and WAV formats at 48kHz/24bit. It features two XLR/TRS Combo Jacks with gain controls, pad, and phantom power, along with a built-in speaker. Equipped with a belt clip, tripod mount, and MS decoder for stereo recording, it's perfect for outdoor videography. It runs on two AA batteries, offering over 15 hours of autonomy, and includes built-in effects like compression and limiting. The screen displays recording time, battery level, and audio quality. Environmental noise control is crucial to avoid saturation and distortion. It supports SD and SDHC cards up to 32 GB and includes pre-recording and auto-recording options to ensure no take is missed. This device was rented from the Grover platform for two weeks to conduct the tests, from which all the mentioned technical information was obtained.

Figure 45
Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones.

Note. The omnidirectional Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones, recommended by audiovisual equipment experts at AVisual Pro, were selected for experimentation in the study area.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 46
Zoom H5 portable recorder.

Note. The Zoom H5 Handy Recorder, rented for experimentation, was used as the central unit to connect the Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones. Source: Own autorship (2024).

A special protective design was created for the portable recorder, as it is the most sensitive device due to its buttons and screen. According to experts from AVisual Pro, the cabling is highly durable and difficult to damage, even if an animal were to bite it. It is made from high-resistance materials and designed to withstand adverse conditions, just like the Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones, which are intended for outdoor use.

The protective design for the recorder includes a tripod that elevates it from the sewer floor, thus avoiding direct contact with moisture and dirt. Additionally, the recorder is placed inside a perforated, black-painted box, allowing easy access for extraction and handling. This box features a fitted opening for connecting the two external microphones, preventing foreign objects from entering, and another opening on top for using the integrated microphone. Figure 47 shows the process of creating the box. This, combined with the tripod legs, gives it a discreet appearance similar to a small espionage device (*baby spy bug*), ensuring optimal protection of the recorder in a specific environment like the sewer. The final device is shown in detail in Figures 48 and 49.

Figure 47
Process of creating the device protection.

Note. The process of manufacturing the protective case for the portable recorder. The perforated, black-painted box allows the device to be elevated on a tripod, ensuring its integrity and functionality while protecting it from the sewer environment. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 48
The recording device.

Note. Complete recording device with the Zoom H5 portable recorder mounted on a tripod and protected inside a perforated, black-painted box, allowing secure connections for external microphones while maintaining access to the integrated microphone. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 49
Detail of the recording device protection.

Note. Detail of the opening for the integrated microphones of the Zoom H5 recorder, showing the perforated box with enough space to allow the microphones to exit, ensuring efficient protection and complete functionality. Source: Own autorship (2024).

In the scope of sound research in specific environments such as sewers, it is crucial to ensure the protection and functionality of the recording devices used. To this end, the protection of the device has been designed with the following mitigation plan in mind, aiming to address and minimize the risks associated with the use of the Zoom H5 Handy Recorder and Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones in adverse conditions.

Risk identification

- **Physical damage from impact:** The recorder and microphones may suffer damage from accidental impacts or falls.
- **Environmental interference:** The sewer environment may present humidity, dust, and other contaminants that could affect the equipment's performance.
- **Accidental manipulation:** The recorder's buttons and screen could be accidentally manipulated, altering the settings or interrupting recordings.
- **Damage from local fauna:** The presence of animals poses a risk of bites or other physical damage to the cables and equipment components.

Mitigation strategies

Physical protection

- **Protective case:** A perforated, black-painted case (for purely aesthetic purposes) with enough space to allow access to connectors and adequate ventilation protects the Zoom H5 recorder. The case is designed to open and close easily, allowing for safe and quick handling of the equipment.
- **Elevating tripod:** The use of a tripod elevates the recorder from the ground, reducing exposure to moisture and other contaminants in the sewer. Additionally, the tripod provides stability and prevents damage from impacts.
- **Fitted openings:** The case's openings are precisely designed to allow the connection of external microphones while preventing the entry of unwanted elements, ensuring the integrity of the connections.

Durable materials

- **Robust cabling:** The cables used are made from durable materials, designed to withstand animal bites and adverse environmental conditions. This ensures that the cables are not easily damaged, maintaining connection and audio quality.
- **Microphones designed for outdoor use:** The Sennheiser ME66-K6 microphones are specifically designed for outdoor use, offering resistance to harsh environmental conditions and ensuring optimal audio capture.

Protection against accidental manipulation

- **Compartment design:** The protective case is designed to limit direct access to the recorder's buttons, preventing accidental manipulation and maintaining the established settings.
- **Rubber feet:** The rubber feet of the tripod help prevent the accidental movement of the device, providing a solid and stable base.

Implementation and monitoring

- **Regular inspections:** Periodic inspections will be carried out to ensure that the protective case, tripod, and all equipment components are kept in optimal condition.
- **Functionality tests:** Before each recording session, tests will be conducted to ensure that the equipment is working correctly and that the settings have not been accidentally altered.
- **Post-operative reviews:** After each operation, all components will be checked for potential damage or wear, and necessary repairs or replacements will be implemented immediately.

The installation in the Barcelona sewer system

An in-person consultation was conducted with the Barcelona City Council through the Citizen Service Office in Les Corts - OAC. During this consultation, approval was obtained for the feasibility of installing a series of sensors at different points within the Barcelona sewer system, according to the project's specifications as a student from a university in Barcelona. To gain approval for this occupation of *public* space, the application shown in Figure 50 had to be completed. The full application can be found in Annex 13.

Once the application was accepted, contact was made with Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua (BCasa), the entity responsible for scheduling the sewer installation. They called us to establish a date convenient for both parties. It was proposed to install the sensors on May 28th at 11:00 AM and to remove them the next day, May 29th at 9:00 AM, to align with the availability of the technicians on those days. Annex 14 contains the documents that had to be signed, stating that BCasa assumed no responsibility for any damage to the equipment.

Figure 50
Application for a public space occupation permit.

Note. Application for a public space occupation permit, issued by the Barcelona City Council and processed on April 2024 ,16. Source: Own autorship (2024).

The installation was carried out at Passeig Sant Joan, number 91, where the entrance to the visitable section of the Barcelona sewer system is located, as shown in Figure 51. The microphones were placed in the main corridor, at a distance of 2 meters apart, as previously established. Figure 52 shows the placement of microphones 1 and 2, and Figure 53 shows the placement of microphone 3.

Figure 51
Location of the installation site.

Note. Entrance door to the visitable section of the Barcelona sewer system, located at Passeig de Sant Joan, number 91. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 52
Placement of microphones 1 and 2.

Note. Placement of microphones 1 and 2 in the specific section of the Barcelona sewer system where the experiment was conducted, granted by the Barcelona City Council for May 28 and 2024 ,29.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 53
Placement of microphone 3.

Note. Placement of microphone 3 in the specific section of the Barcelona sewer system where the experiment was conducted, granted by the Barcelona City Council for May 28 and 2024 ,29.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

The following day, after the installation, the device was retrieved. The second microphone was found on the ground, and its protective casing was damaged, as seen in Figure 54. However, the recorder remained intact, demonstrating the effectiveness of the protective design implemented. Another issue detected was damage to the cabling, as shown in Figure 55, caused by rodent bites. Although the cabling did not suffer functional damage, it did show structural damage that could have become serious had the experiment lasted longer.

Figure 54
Superficial Damage to the Protection of Microphone 2.

Note. Superficial damage to the casing of Microphone 2, specifically to the exterior paint, indicating movement caused by a large creature in the sewer. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 55
Superficial damage to the cabling.

Note. Superficial damage to the cabling, specifically to the exterior protection, showing signs of bites likely caused by a rodent. Source: Own autorship (2024).

The damage to the cabling could have been mitigated or eliminated if specific cable protections had been used. An effective solution would have been to cover the cables with 2-meter-long cable protectors, available in specialized stores. These protectors are designed to resist impact and wear, providing an additional layer of security against physical damage. Using this type of protection would not only increase the durability of the cabling but also ensure the continuity of the electrical connection, which is essential for the proper functioning of the recording equipment. Additionally, installing these protectors is simple and accessible, representing a minimal investment compared to the potential costs of repairing or replacing damaged cables. Therefore, incorporating this preventive measure is a recommended practice to ensure the integrity and effectiveness of equipment in future projects.

The data collected during this sewer experiment consisted of a one-hour recording, even though the recorder's capacity is considerably higher. The impact on Microphone 2 was likely the cause of the recording being interrupted. Despite this, being located next to a stream, only the sounds of the water were captured, making it impossible to record the footsteps of animals that were evidently present, as the noise of the water masked them. Figure 56 presents a categorized individual event (a specific water sound) in the first 17-minute segment (chosen to exemplify this analysis) to perform the relevant triangulation and verify that the location of the source (in this case, the water) was from the stream next to it. The opaque squares found in the section from the start up to 200 seconds were generated manually, as they correspond to the installation time until we fully exited the sewer. The exit time was considered the point at which the analysis recording begins, to avoid it being biased by the noises we made. The same procedure used in the apartment soundscape was followed, and Figure 57 shows the calculation of the arrival times of this specific event, while Figure 58 presents the relevant triangulation. From this experiment, it can be concluded that for future investigations, it is important to place the microphones in tunnels where there are no streams (of which there are many, as informed by the technicians who accompanied us during the installation). Additionally, it is noted that we can obtain a one-hour meditation session with recorded water sounds, which are quite relaxing.

Figure 56.
Classification of sound groups in the sewer.

Note. This figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Barcelona sewer on May 2024 ,28, corresponding to a 17-minute (1000 seconds) segment, the identification of an event taken as an example using Software 1, corresponding to agent 01 (the water), the only agent identified in the controlled area during the study period. Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 57.
 Calculation of arrival times for event *1 (Barcelona sewer).

[*1]

Sound arrival time relative to 480.0:

- A - Microphone 1 = 7 milliseconds
- B - Microphone 2 = 2 milliseconds
- C - Microphone 3 = 9.8 milliseconds

Note. This figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Barcelona sewer on May 2024 ,28, corresponding to a 2.5-second segment, the calculation of the arrival time (milliseconds) relative to the 480.0-second mark of the recording, corresponding to agent 01 (the water).
 Source: Own autorship (2024).

Figure 58
 Triangulation of Event *1 (Second Floor).

Note. This figure shows, using the original data recorded in the Barcelona sewer on May 2024 ,28, corresponding to a 2.5-second segment, the triangulation of Event *1 relative to the 480.0-second mark of the recording, corresponding to agent 01 (the water). Source: Own autorship (2024).

This demonstrates that the noises captured in the recording from the Barcelona sewer correspond to the water flowing in the stream located next to the placement of the microphones.

Third Part

The looks:
The sonic cartography

The intersection between space and sound

Sound mapping employs a variety of techniques for collecting sound data, including on-site audio recordings, acoustic sensors (microphones), and geolocation technologies (sound triangulation). These sounds can be categorized according to their source, intensity, frequency, and location, and are then mapped into visual representations. The methodology involves creating sound maps to reveal and analyze the interaction between sound and space. Brandon LaBelle's book *Sonic Agency: Sound and Emergent Forms of Resistance* (2018) provides a theoretical framework for understanding the political and social implications of sound. LaBelle argues that sound, due to its invisible nature, can foster new forms of resistance and create unlikely publics where mutuality and dissent can occur. This approach emphasizes the importance of listening and auditory experience as a link to contemporary social crises and the reimagining of civic spaces. Additionally, the notion of invisibility that LaBelle (2018) discusses is particularly relevant to this study, exploring how sounds can make invisible presences and activities of agents in an urban environment visible. In the context of this project, *invisible urban animals* become present through their sounds.

One of the key references in this field is the concept of *Acoustic Ecology*, proposed by Raymond M. Schafer (1983), which laid the theoretical foundations for the study of the soundscape. Schafer developed sound maps that revealed the diversity and complexity of sounds present in natural and urban environments, thus establishing the groundwork for future research in this area. His representations provide a tangible understanding of the richness and variability of sounds in specific environments. Another significant initiative in this field is *Cities and Memory* (2014), a collaborative project that collects sound recordings from around the world and organizes them into an interactive online map. Each recording is associated with a specific geographic location, allowing users to explore and compare the soundscapes of different regions and cultures.

The third part of *Above all that is below* focuses on proposing a symbolic (assumed) sound map as a representative scenography of the underground and surface of the big city—the complete urban landscape. This duality, as a hypothetical example, can contribute to projecting what the development of the proposed practice in the research project can offer. The physical connection between the two levels is a key element in the proposed map, being a scenographic configuration that allows for a deeper understanding of the interrelationship between different urban elements. Figure 59 shows the juxtaposition of the sound maps of the First and Second floors created in Part Two, to exemplify the physical connection in this duality.

As this cartography undergoes iterations in the subsequent subchapters, it exemplifies how it can serve as an operational tool to rethink future cities by visualizing the densification of spatial interactions in the urban landscape.

Figure 59
Simple sound mapping of the first and second floors overlaid.

First and second floor

- Agent 01 tracking (Domestic dog)
- Agent 02 tracking (Human)
- Agent 03 tracking (Human)
- Agent 04 tracking (Human)

2024-05-15 18:00:00 to 18:16:56

Note. The figure shows, using original data recorded in the corridors of the First and Second Floors on May 2024 ,15, corresponding to a 17-minute fragment, the triangulation of events performed by four agents. Source: Own autorship (2024).

The action: The hypothetical sound map

Just as the invitation to this Cocktail Party suggests, it is important to acknowledge that these pages represent the beginning of a long, solid, and undoubtedly exciting investigation. Therefore, as we reach the final part of this work, a hypothetical sound map is presented as an example of what the proposal—with effort, iterations, and time—could generate.

The scenario takes place in 2029, on a very hot June 21, at nine in the morning. The location is the same as the one used in the underground experiment, at Passeig de Sant Joan number 91 (55.0'23°41"N 13.5'10°2"E), analyzing a radius of 40 meters from these central coordinates. Figure 60 shows the specific location in the city, as well as the installation of the sewer system in Barcelona. This has been defined by Pascual, J. (2020) in a study on rats in the metropolitan area, being one of the few accessible documents regarding the sewer network's location. After firsthand experimentation in Barcelona's underground, it has been demonstrated that the network is much more complex than what this map illustrates.

The setup includes an underground installation of 35 microphones, spaced two meters apart, and 11 portable recorders (Zoom H5 type). It is assumed that the microphones used are of the highest possible quality and can record sounds nearly inaudible to the human ear¹⁰. The recording lasts 12 hours (until nine at night the same day), and the identified sounds—using improved Software 1 and 2—are triangulated to obtain the emitter's position every second, resulting in accurate tracking.

To generate the proposed sound map, a specific code is first defined—representing the identity of the agents—where sound groups are categorized by species, not by individual subjects. This means that each movement line belongs to a specific agent, but the color coding classifies species in general. This approach is established because, later, when the maps span months, it will be essential to see the sound groups classified by the nature of the subject to understand their behaviors and needs for rethinking the city. By adopting this practice, all species become equally important, as they are coded in the same way without giving more importance to one in particular, becoming 2D vectors instead of being represented by their size or hierarchy in the food chain. Additionally, the proposed sound map does not account for sound elements (such as frequency, timbre, volume) because this would propose a hierarchy among species, giving more importance to a

¹⁰ It is recommended to visit the Instagram of the user *@chausseurdesons* as a reference for the assumed practice, in terms of materials used and sound editing results to isolate specific sounds.

pigeon over a mosquito merely due to its body size, thus exacerbating the invisibility of already generally invisible species due to these factors. On the other hand, the coding does consider agent pauses, which is why the graphical elements communicating this factor need to be adapted to the various forms of movement and temporality that could be tracked.

Figure 60
Location for the hypothetical sound map.

Note. Specific location for the hypothetical sound map, with Passeig de Sant Joan number 91 being the central point from which the space is analyzed, up to a radius of 40 meters.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

In the hypothetical sound map, the urban surface, visible (located 29 meters above sea level), allows for tracking the agents living there using conventional non-subterranean technologies (GPS, cameras, etc.), while the underground, invisible (situated 26 meters above sea level), is made visible through the technology proposed in Part Two, converting identified sound into cartographic data. The agents in this hypothetical case include pigeons, cockroaches, humans, rats, subterranean flies (as sewer technicians reported they are numerous), and dogs (domestic, of course). Figure 61 shows the hypothesized sound mapping.

Thanks to the visual representation of the triangulation of sounds from specific agents over the course of 12 hours, we can identify various supposed behavior patterns. For example, pigeons make pauses in green areas of the defined section, while humans make pauses at the bus stop and before crossing pedestrian crossings. It can also be seen that humans and subterranean animals (rats, cockroaches, and flies) exhibit similar behavioral characteristics, as the sewer conduit and the pedestrian sidewalk are on the same Y-axis.

The hypothetical sound map serves to identify points of densification where there is direct and indirect coexistence between species. By identifying these specific areas, based on a future with real data, dialogues can be established about how these urban spaces are aware of these hidden realities. Creating maps where all agents are situated on the same level, and exploring an urban reality where the flows of life are the factor around which cities are rethought, seems to be an ethical, and undoubtedly more conscious, approach to coexisting in a shared space.

Figure 61. *The hypothetical sound map.* ▼
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Elevation: 29m

Elevation: 26m

THE PATH

THE GOSSIP

Now that the first Cocktail Party of many has concluded, it is time to analyze the points of improvement and celebration that will contribute to making the next edition a better version. In this review of the event, we first address the aspects to work on, focusing on the limitations faced during this period.

Firstly, the time constraint has been a decisive factor in the project, affecting the experiments conducted in Part Two. Additionally, lengthy procedures with the City Council have prevented a detailed analysis of the experimentation in the underground environment, as initially planned. Nevertheless, successfully carrying it out is a cause for celebration, considering that the project duration was three months.

On the other hand, a limitation has been technological. Due to both economic reasons and time constraints, it was not possible to access equipment specifically adapted to the conditions of the experimentation. It would have been necessary to have several days of testing different types of microphones and recorders to determine which provided the best results. Furthermore, the fact that the equipment was rented for specific days prevented exploring all its possibilities and testing it in various environments.

Another identified limitation has been the field of knowledge. Although both multispecies design and sound tracking technologies are areas of interest, basic self-learning periods were required to carry out the experimentation. Considering the time limitation for conducting the work, this factor significantly influenced the expected results. However, now that it has concluded, it can be said that a basic but promising level of expertise has been achieved for future experimentation in the field.

After mentioning the limitations, points of improvement are proposed for future work, intended to be conducted within the framework of the PhD program in Experimental Sciences and Technologies offered by UVic-UCC.

The first point of improvement is the optimization of Software 1 (the Cocktail Party effect) so that the categorization of specific events is performed optimally using machine learning techniques that allow for the identification and classification of the sound of each animal according to its species. Additionally, efforts should be made to improve Software 2 to automate the arrival time of each sound, thereby achieving complete sound triangulation every second.

This way, a fully automated underground tracking technology can be developed, allowing for the creation of sound maps of larger areas.

Another area for improvement is the definition of the sound map as a graphical document. Although time limitations have constrained the complexity of defining the proposed sound map, the goal is to cover larger areas of the city and even create a map that other species can read. Just as people become aware of the complexity of the urban environment, the same should happen from the other side, as ignorance is reciprocal. What if these invisible beings were aware of human dynamics of habitation? This is a fascinating question to continue exploring.

After addressing the limiting factors and areas for improvement, it is important to highlight the celebration. The achievement of making agents visible through non-invasive underground tracking technology has been accomplished!

But why is this important? Because it may influence the growth of future urban environments? And if it can, what is possible, what is probable, and what is desirable?

To answer the hypothesis (and, consequently, the other questions), it is important to understand the context in which it arose. James Auger (2013) talks about alternative presents or lost futures when exploring various development possibilities, opening the door to the question "What if?" (based on speculative design) and replacing it with "Why are things the way they are?". This question acknowledges the interconnection between the past and present, providing a framework for critiquing the present and suggesting possible futures. This is the logic behind *Sobre(tot) el que hi ha sota*.

It is through debate and the identification of limitations that currently hinder diversity in designs that methods in the discipline can be changed to adapt to the current situation, offering innovative alternatives. Often, these innovations come from uncomfortable, unpleasant, or, for some, boring places. But it is from these places that one must push the machinery to explore them, understand them, make them visible, and thus comprehend the complexity of the shared common space.

It is essential to know the totality of a space to be able to design it and, even more, to design changes within it. Therefore, any type of visibility of the invisible can condition the growth of the specific environment. The visibility of invisible urban animals may influence the development of the urban environment, whatever that may imply. A radical change in the near future is not necessary, but small steps can lead to long-term changes, so that the change is ultimately systemic.

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Annex

Annex 1. The 6W method

Who

- **Field of Knowledge:** Transversal.
 - Engineering, Industry, and Construction, specializing in Engineering Design.
 - Arts and Humanities, specializing in Product Design.
- **Research Area:** Product Engineering.
- **Specialty or Discipline:** Data Engineering.
- **Theme:** Multi-species Design.
- **Study Topic:** Visualizing the underground of urban environments.
- **Study Area:** Underground of Barcelona.
- **Subjects of Study:**
 - Subterranean Urban Animal Inhabitants (Invisible) – Species Types.
 - Surface Urban Human Inhabitants (Visible) – Visualization of the Subsoil.
 - Data Engineering – Methods and Systems of Audio and Tracking.
- **Researcher's Position:** Data Engineering, non-invasive perspective.

What

- **Issue:** Lack of knowledge about subterranean urban fauna and the subsoil of large cities, coupled with the exponential growth of wildlife in metropolises.
- **Study Problem:** Describe the interaction between urbanites (species cataloging, tracking, and visualization).
- **Main Question:** Can the visibility of invisible urban animal inhabitants influence the growth of future urban environments?
- **Hypothesis:** Making subterranean urban fauna visible in contemporary large cities allows for constant dialogue with the species inhabiting them and raises awareness about urban growth from a multi-species design perspective.

Where

- **Geographical Space:** Urban Subsoil.
- **Location:** Physical Space.
- **Study Area:** The Barcelona sewer system as a case study.
- **Scope:** Area of interest between subjects.

When

- **Temporal Framework:** Present. 10 years prior.
- **Theoretical Framework:** References from various disciplines related to multi-species design.
- **State of the Art:** References to technologies for tracking subterranean animals.

Why

• **Importance and Relevance:** Regarding conservation in general, the public is interested in animal behavior (BBC, 2023). This research aims to incorporate the plan for subterranean fauna into the daily management of the city. Currently, there is no comparable method for locating underground animals. It could represent a radical change in city structuring, with consequences that might offer an open field for knowledge and reflection on the contemporary metropolis.

• **Personal Justification:** There is a need for contemporary critical discourses on multi-species lifestyles to generate debates on more-than-human design. By examining subterranean urban fauna, we can introduce alternative scenarios that question the division between surface and subsoil in the hypermodern city, thereby reconstituting the ways we coexist with non-human inhabitants of the metropolis.

How

• **Research Methodology:** The methodology follows a mixed approach (qualitative and quantitative).

Annex 2. Marta Tafalla interview

April 2024 ,19. [5:00 PM]

Cristina Sanuy: - Good afternoon, Marta, thank you for your time. I came across your work through an article (Costa, 2024) published in *El Periódico* a couple of weeks ago about the wild animals living in Barcelona. I thought it would be very interesting to speak with you because a few months ago, I started a project at ELISAVA (within Elisava Research) on multi-species design, and since your work is closely tied to animal ethics and care for other species in urban environments, it would be very helpful to know your perspective on the subject. Could you explain what you cover in the animal ethics course you teach at the UAB?

Marta Tafalla: - Good afternoon, Cristina. Well, I've been working in animal ethics for many years, it's one of the main research areas I focus on. My background is in philosophy, and I constantly try to understand how other species relate to us and how we should relate to them. I study how we interact, what we do wrong, and what we could do better. I've published several works on the topic. In this course, which is at the master's level, we delve into animal ethics, but specifically within the context of ecological ethics. We link the two themes: how to think about our relationship with animals in the context of global warming, mass extinction, pollution, etc., always trying to understand that there is a very close relationship between animal ethics and ecological ethics. We start from foundational issues found in classical philosophical texts on animal rights and ecological ethics, moving towards more concrete, applied issues. We also look at what scientists say about these topics.

C: - I've seen that ecofeminism is also a concept you work with, which fits within this theme.

M: - Yes, ecofeminism provides a very good theoretical framework. One of the challenges with ecological ethics and animal ethics is finding theoretical frameworks that help you accurately describe the problems and then seek solutions. And it's not so easy to find good theoretical frameworks. I think that some of the more well-known ones are not as good as we might think—at least from my perspective, of course. For me, ecofeminism is a theoretical framework that helps to understand the interconnections between forms of violence against animals and forms of violence against people. Moreover, it links this to the ecological crisis. It helps you see the relationships and interactions between these issues, and personally, that helps me a lot to think and construct a global framework.

If you're interested, there are some excellent texts on this topic. What's your academic background?

C: - I'm an industrial design engineer and product designer. I'm currently pursuing a master's degree in academic research at ELISAVA, with plans to start a PhD in multi-species design at UVic-UCC next year. My master's thesis is being conducted through Elisava Research and focuses on the underground of Barcelona and the animals that inhabit this space—particularly the sewer system. I'm researching how the visibility and understanding of these animals could influence future urban growth. When we design future cities, we often overlook the animals that inhabit these spaces beneath the city, and there's an entire world we are unaware of. In large metropolises, there is no direct connection between the surface and the underground, but if such a connection—this communication—existed, we could envision urban futures where multi-species design plays a significant role. To achieve this, I propose installing microphones at a specific point within Barcelona's sewer system to identify and visualize the species that inhabit this environment. It's a subject about which we have very little information—we know there are rats and cockroaches, but we are largely unaware of the subterranean urban fauna (what I call invisible urban animal inhabitants) that live in large metropolises. This might be due to an innate aversion we have towards these creatures, and it's this lack of knowledge and aversion that also prevents us from questioning what life exists beneath our feet. The project's goal is to use the sounds recorded by these microphones to create maps of the movements of the animals that approach the installation—as a method of tracking and identifying the different species that are recorded. This is achieved through software we've developed using computational language. What I particularly like about this project is how sound can be used to generate illustrations, narratives of anticipation, and speculative fiction. By relying on sound alone, we can understand what life exists down there, but we can also tap into a creativity that isn't the same as what we would have if we also had visual input. I aim to create a storytelling framework about what more-than-human relationships could occur in future urban environments. I hope I've explained myself well.

M: - Yes, absolutely. It's a very intriguing topic. But why does this interest you, specifically?

C: - It interests me because last year, I did my double degree final project within the field of speculative urban futures, and during the summer, I participated in a workshop on multi-species design in Croatia. It was at a time when I wasn't sure what I liked, and I was introduced to these two topics, which I had never heard of before, and I loved them so much that today I envision a professional future focused on them. Also, I've always been very interested in the themes of fear, rejection... and I often thought that it's great

to consider other species, but generally, we don't talk about those that elicit an innate aversion in us. An aversion we take for granted and don't question.

M: - Are you thinking, for example, about the mass poisoning of rats that takes place in big cities?

C: - Yes. Not only that, but it's a topic I do touch on, yes. In fact, a couple of weeks ago, I visited the sewer museum in Brussels and spoke with a biologist who specializes in rats. We discussed the ethics behind the mass extermination of these animals. I find it very interesting to question and debate these issues, and I have a hard time finding information on the subject. Generating this information myself seems exciting to me. I also wanted to mention that I've seen you've written a book called *Nunca sabrás a qué huele Bagdad* about the absence of one of the five senses, and knowing that the goal of my project is to generate narratives/imaginings using only one sense, what are your thoughts on this comparison?

M: - Well, that's because I don't have a sense of smell. You know, there's a small portion of the population that suffers from anosmia (in my case, it's congenital), and it's been studied a lot: when you're missing a sense from birth, you don't notice its absence because, to you, the world is just that way. But when you compare it with people who do have a sense of smell, you realize their experience of the world is completely different. So, in this novel I published, I tried to explain anosmia through literature, but later, in the philosophy classes I teach, what I try to do is promote this reflection that, in a way, we take for granted that the world is as we perceive it, but there could be many things we don't perceive. For example, there are many animals that communicate with infrasounds or ultrasounds that we can't hear. It also seems that there's a spectrum of light we don't see, colors we don't perceive... I mean, there are things in the world—not esoteric things, but real things—that we don't perceive, and we don't realize that we're not perceiving them. Radioactivity, for example, is very dangerous, but human senses can't detect it. So, for me, it's an important topic because our relationship with the world is based on what we perceive, and it's very difficult for us to think about things we don't perceive.

C: - How interesting. What do you think about the project I mentioned to you?

M: - I'm a bit surprised. Why are you interested in this, and what exactly do you want to achieve? When you contacted me via email talking about multi-species urbanism, I thought you wanted to do something different. I'm mentioning this because, let's say, there's growing interest in the fact that there's a lot of wildlife moving into cities, and this leads to questions about how to redesign cities to reduce accidents involving these

animals. I thought you would bring up the typical issue of birds crashing into glass windows of buildings, and how we can prevent that or reduce the risk. I thought you were going more in that direction, where there's a lot of work being done, a lot of debate, and a lot of literature. So what you're proposing has caught me a bit off guard. I'm not exactly sure where you're headed with this, whether it's more of an artistic speculative reflection, or if you actually want to stop rats from being killed.

C: - No, not at all. Rats are just one of the animals that can be found in the sewers of big cities, but that's not where my focus lies. There's a whole ecosystem living underground, and I'm interested in it as a whole. When you ask me what goal I have, I mentioned multi-species urbanism because within this emerging line of research at ELISAVA on speculative design for future urban environments, speculation can come from many angles: you can speculate from the most technical engineering (like understanding sustainability in new smart buildings), to what would happen if there were a drone war or if animals lived more closely with humans in these future cities. I think there's a lot of debate missing about which species will inhabit these new cities, but also about those that already live there and we still don't understand. A couple of days ago, I was reading a doctoral thesis by someone who talked about the subterranean Barcelona from an architectural perspective, about how the sewer system and utilities were constructed—you, as a human, go there, detonate, and build kilometers and kilometers of space without considering who is inhabiting that space or who might inhabit it once this giant network of tunnels and empty spaces is created. This is where I see the potential, and maybe I'm the only one who sees it, and others don't, which is why I'm very interested in your opinion.

M: - Well, it's definitely an intriguing approach. I mean, it's both original and unusual. But it's true that it ties into this whole idea of the world we don't see, right? What's happening underground, where in nature, underground, we also don't see what's happening. When you're in a forest, you see what's on the surface, and underground there's a lot going on that we have no idea about because, until very recently, we hadn't started studying it. Now, it's becoming understood that this life that's creating humus in rural environments is very important. You're adding a more reflective layer about how, in cities, we live on the surface, and understanding what's happening underneath, where species that live there, like in the forest, mix with others that are there because these human installations have created a different kind of space than what exists in nature. We have a whole set of neighbors living beneath us that we don't see, but who are also urban. They take advantage of our waste, the nooks and crannies we've created where they can hide...

C: - Yes, exactly. One of the things I also want to include is the debate on animal ethics. Why are all the technologies developed so far to track underground animals invasive?

They always end up being chips, collars, etc. I'm approaching this technology through sound, which isn't invasive to them.

M: - That's very interesting.

C: - I wanted to ask you how animal ethics is addressed in a project where the animals in question elicit disgust from us.

M: - In your case, it's very difficult, because consider that in Spain, we still have bullfighting. I mean, we're talking about animals that are very close to us, very intelligent, very emotional, and they're tortured with public money. A significant part of society agrees with this, and most of society eats animals too. So, when the level of insensitivity is so high, rats—poor things—are like the lowest priority. You know what I mean? It's very difficult. Because if people are buying very intelligent animals at the supermarket every day—animals that could often be pets and that have had horrible deaths—and they don't care at all, we're not even talking about the poor rats. Or other types of invertebrates that might be there, creatures that cause disgust... it's a huge issue. They're killed in very painful ways... but there's no sensitivity about this, none at all. Except for the animal rights movement, of course. Understanding how disgust is related to ethics, knowing that we don't even have ethics for an animal we consider intelligent, imagine what little ethics there would be for an animal that causes revulsion. Have you read *Zoopolis* (Donaldson & Kymlicka, 2018)? Because I think it's a very good book for you. Especially the final part, which talks about coexisting with other species in cities, and about mice. I can also recommend *Animal Crisis* (Crary & Gruen, 2022). Both books are among the best on animal ethics from the philosophy discipline. They're classic texts on this subject, masterpieces, because they offer a theory on how to coexist with animals, delving deeply into detailed issues: what rights we should grant them, differences between species, how to address practical issues of coexistence...

C: - Thank you so much, I'll make a note of them. I saw that in 2014 you were in parliament and managed to get a ban on animals in circuses in the country. It made me think about my childhood memories of circuses, always with animals. I think of the *Gran Circo Universal*, where they paraded a greyhound as if it were a fantastic being, and how we could ride on an elephant in the middle of the city. This is a very obvious topic regarding animal ethics, like bullfighting, but with my subject, it's harder for me to see it clearly. Probably because I don't consider myself an expert who can speak from a critical perspective.

M: - In ethics, there's a centuries-old tradition of pondering what you're saying. There's an accumulation of theories, and it's complex to consider oneself knowledgeable enough

to speak about ethics. But of course, it all comes down to diving into it. It takes time. I also understand that, because of your background, it might seem a bit distant to dive into certain readings. I would recommend that you read the classic philosophy texts on animal ethics, more general philosophy that can help you speak about it from this discipline. For example, *Animal Liberation* (Singer, 1975) is one of them. It's not a book I particularly like, but many people consider it one of the great texts on animal ethics; everyone has read it. And even though I don't like it, I believe it's a must-read. It's a theory about how we should relate to animals, an attempt to understand how we're doing it wrong. I think the explanation is somewhat superficial, but he offers an explanation of why we have such a bad relationship with animals and makes some proposals, analyzing specific cases (animal farming for food, experimentation) and offering broader, more general reflections. It's a very easy book to read, to get into, and it presents a strong philosophical theory of animal ethics. However, as I said, I don't really like how it's organized, and many people (especially nowadays, since this book is from the 70s) consider it weak, but at the time, it was—and still is—a classic text. Another author you could look into is Tom Regan, who was one of the first to articulate a theory of animal rights. What I mentioned about Peter Singer is all animal ethics work, but it's not a theory of rights, whereas Tom Regan did attempt to articulate a theory in itself. He has several books—I'm not sure if they're all translated—among which I'd highlight *Empty Cages* (Regan, 2005). Both come from philosophy and are solid, classic texts that anyone entering these topics has read, discussed, and has an opinion on. I'd suggest you read these and see how they resonate with you. If you also want to read something introductory on ecofeminism, there's a very nice book called *Claves Ecofeministas* (Puleo, 2019) by Alicia H. Puleo, a philosopher from the University of Valladolid. This book is very introductory, it's short, and it gives you the main keys to the movement. Maybe this can help you build a more extensive and solid theoretical framework.

C: - Absolutely, thank you. The topic of ecofeminism is closely tied to animal ethics, and I know I need to delve deeper into it, but I've hardly touched it. I've read a lot about feminism, but not much related to ecology.

M: - Well, let me know what you think. For me, it was a discovery that significantly changed my theoretical framework because I struggled to find a comprehensive framework that could tie together all the topics I wanted to address—animals, the ecological crisis, and human rights, while also being sensitive to issues of gender and class. I wanted to include so many things that it became complicated. It's very challenging because there are many ecological theories that focus heavily on the ecological crisis but don't address other topics or don't tackle them well enough. Or they don't consider things that are important to me, like issues of gender, social class, racism... Or animal ethics theories that don't

connect either. So, finding a theoretical framework that ties everything together is very important, and once you have it, it really opens your eyes because you start to see how everything feeds into each other, and it's very enlightening.

C: - How interesting. I also noticed that you talk a lot about veganism. I found an interview (Sobrevivir al Descalabro, 2023) you did last year where they introduced you with hashtags: ecofeminism, veganism, dualism, and rewilding. How do you experience veganism?

M: - I see that here, vegan diets are often poorly done because there's a lack of experience. Veganism in Asia has a longer tradition, though it's been very minor here. I think sometimes people jump into it without consulting a nutritionist, a professional who knows what they're doing and can help you. That's when you risk having health issues if you don't do it properly. It's been more of an obsession for me in recent years because the human population is so large, and the number of animals we raise for food is astronomical. It distorts the functioning of ecosystems. It's madness.

C: - Do you have any reading recommendations on veganism?

M: - There's a bestseller by psychologist Melanie Joy called *Why We Love Dogs, Eat Pigs, and Wear Cows* (Joy, 2011)... something like that. It's a pretty well-known book, but it's very good. It mainly discusses the issue of animal abuse. There's also another book called *Regenesis* (Monbiot, 2022) by a well-known British biologist, George Monbiot, which focuses more on the ecological impact. The issue of mistreatment is there, but the main focus is the impact of such a large human population consuming animals. Both are very interesting.

C: - That's great. Veganism is a topic that's been covered so much that sometimes I struggle to choose what to read. Recommendations from people knowledgeable on the subject are always very helpful to me.

M: - Yes, veganism is growing a lot due to increasing awareness of animal suffering and because now the impact of this movement on global warming, biodiversity loss... is much better understood. Many people in science are working on this, which is fairly recent because it used to be more of an ethical and moral issue, but now more and more biologists and ecologists are studying it. The people talking about it and researching it are changing. It's great that this new discourse comes from professionals in these fields who have switched to a strict vegan diet, and when you ask them, they say they did it because of climate change. In fact, going back to your project, you're reminding me of a

horror movie called *Mimic* (Del Toro, 1997), by Guillermo del Toro, set in the sewers. It's very well made; I don't like horror films because they scare me, but this one was recommended to me because it's aesthetically curious. I'll summarize it for you: it's a story where there's been a pandemic, and to find a cure, they modified an insect/animal. Later, they abandon it, and a new form of life develops in the sewers. It's not a gory film; it's a different kind of horror. I found it very interesting. A strange being appears that's bad and chases humans (the typical story), but aesthetically it's fascinating because it plays with what happens underground, in places we don't see. It's a few years old, but it's well made. I won't say much more, but I think you'll find the visuals very interesting.

C: - How interesting. In fact, I want my work to have a visual outcome, based on the animals that imagination generates from the sounds recorded in the sewers.

M: - At first, I was a bit thrown off because I didn't quite grasp what you want to do. It's so original that it's a bit hard to understand. In this world of multispecies design, there's still a lot to be done. I mean, there are things out there, but not that many, really. If you research the people working on Critical Animal Studies, you'll see they're doing the most diverse things you can imagine because, of course, each species is a world of its own, and so is each place on the planet.

C: - Thank you for the conversation, Marta. It's been very pleasant.

M: - Thank you. You're delving into a very surprising topic. I'm very interested to see what will come out of this journey.

Annex 3. Crossover Project subject

The teacher Manuela Valtchanova allowed attendance and participation in certain tutorials during some of the sessions she taught alongside Professor Nacho Antón within the framework of *Multispecies Justice: Care and Indifference*. These sessions took place both on the Carretera de les Aigües (Collserola) and in the university classrooms.

Intermediate presentations of the Crossover Project subject in Collserola (I).
Source: Manuela Valtchanova (2024).

During the period from March 18th to April 19th (the date of the final presentations), the students' process of approaching multispecies design was explored in depth. The close monitoring of the nine projects being developed, based on explorations of relationships with non-human agents in Collserola Park, provided insights into educational practices in this field, the methodology to follow, potential improvements, questions that arose in each tutorial, and different perspectives from various disciplines.

Intermediate presentations of the Crossover Project subject in Collserola (II).
Source: Manuela Valtchanova (2024).

The projects undertaken were highly diverse, allowing for deep exploration of each one with different methodologies, as reflected in the final results. One of the student groups (comprising 3 to 5 participants) chose water as their non-human agent. They approached this element by exploring the current water scarcity in Collserola Park—a problem affecting many other areas of the city as well, of course. To address this issue, the group proposed a series of networks attached to trees in strategic locations that would collect air condensation and instantly convert it into liquid water. Amidst debates about the potential uses of this generated water (irrigation, providing water for local animals, or letting it fall randomly into nature), alternative methods for transporting water to the park (such as sweat or urine from hikers/passersby), and the ethics behind it, or even the most suitable materials for the chosen process, the students created a material by mixing organic and chemical elements. They developed a porous biopolymer that could be crafted manually. This material was dried over the networks formed by the palm trees (native to the area) to achieve a rigid, mesh-like structure that filled the frames along the Carretera de les Aigües.

Final presentation of the water group.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Eagles were another non-human agent selected. After concluding that the electrocution of eagles on power poles in the most populated streets of the area was a real problem, the two women in this group explored different methods to either deter the birds or make these charged poles more habitable. Proposals such as installing speakers to scare these large birds away, creating nests out of non-conductive materials placed on these structures, and even developing a platform that would separate the electrical wires to allow eagles to fly between them without triggering a fatal discharge, were eventually set aside. Instead, they proposed colonizing the poles and electrical cables with mycelium,

a non-conductive and luminescent fungus, which would allow the birds to safely inhabit this area situated between houses and enthusiastic cyclists.

Continuing with birds, another species that emerged in the projects was the tawny owl, which, like the eagles, suffers from the light pollution of the area, especially between the houses. Confident from the beginning about their final solution to this problem, the women in this group created a helmet designed to provide immersive experiences for humans. This helmet aimed to make people experience the distressing sensation that these animals face once night falls in this semi-natural environment. The helmet functioned using an Arduino that triggered various light stimuli with LEDs of different colors, along with integrated headphones that gave instructions for a series of activities to achieve the final state of disorientation they aimed to convey.

Final presentation of the owl group.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

Continuing with the theme of flying animals but venturing into the world of insects, there is the group focused on bees. This group of girls initially chose plants as their non-human agent, inspired by the idea of an herbalist. They conducted in-depth research on the pollination of certain pre-selected plant species (such as the strawberry tree and others) and concluded that there was another non-human agent at play: the bee, which also

caught their interest. Using the concept of human pollination as their study subject (how humans can pollinate compared to animals that naturally do so), due to the potential risk of extinction of certain plant species in the area, they developed a kit allowing humans to pollinate. They considered various factors, such as collecting pollen by hand, mimicking the bees' *modus operandi*, and providing instructions for the activity. Behind this well-intentioned product/activity lies a complex ethical dilemma. How many bees can one human effectively replace? Are we taking jobs away from the bees? Can care turn into a form of violent and invasive action in this case?

Cats were the next non-human agent. This group aimed to raise awareness about domesticated cats that become feral again due to being abandoned by their human owners. With a clear and confident proposal to build a cat colony in a specific spot in Collserola Park to raise awareness, they discussed the idea of a living museum and even a safari. Undoubtedly, this was the project with the most questionable ethics—from the idea of capturing feral cats or those from colonies to enclose them in this fenced park, to charging visitors an entrance fee to maintain this small business. Ultimately, they decided to propose a sort of semi-open leisure park, with designed spaces where humans and cats could freely interact from both perspectives. The debates that arose during the tutorials were quite interesting.

Mid-term presentation of the cat group.
Source: Manuela Valtchanova (2024).

There was a group that chose microorganisms as their subject of study. The members decided from the outset to analyze samples of different microorganisms collected in the areas around the Carretera de les Aigües using a microscope. Inspired by the forms they

discovered, they wanted to create something that would make these microorganisms visible to the people who frequent the park. They thought that creating large-scale sculptures and placing them in strategic locations in the park would be a good way to achieve this goal. After several sessions debating the best material to use—an ephemeral, biodegradable material—they decided to make the sculptures out of candy, so that various creatures in the park could lick them until the last particle was gone, or so that environmental conditions would eventually make them disappear if not. Placing mirrors beneath the much-enlarged sculptures contributed to human and some animal interaction, creating a curious semi-erotic game. However, how does the intimacy of microorganisms get affected when they are made visible on such a greatly exaggerated scale? Is this truly an act of care?

The wild boar was another non-human agent that, like the bees, appeared later in the selection process. This group focused on erosion as their subject of study, given that the Carretera de les Aigües is a place where a significant number of visitors are on two wheels. The students initially decided to understand and create a structure that would be the negative of an erosion pattern they identified, made of a biodegradable mesh on which nature could grow. They realized that working directly on the erosion might be more interesting, and thus began to explore the application of fungus cultures in eroded environments, and even how to grow any kind of flora in this specific spot. Eventually, they decided to mechanize the human body (human-machine) so that it could, through stakes that allowed the optimal insertion of pre-made soil balls composed of water, excrement, and seeds, and with the help of wild boars to further erode the land (this is where they come in), create new ecosystems in spaces where little growth is usually expected.

Detail of the mid-term presentation of the wild boar group.
Source: Own autorship (2024).

The most engineering-focused group concentrated on the viewfinders located at various lookout points along the Carretera de les Aigües. They took pollution as their non-human agent and decided to develop a post-apocalyptic viewfinder that functioned as a machine for visual narratives. Using various interchangeable filters that simulated pollution caused by airplanes, cars, and other factors, they invited the creation of collage-like photographs of the Barcelona skyline, sparking the creation of speculative stories about the city's hyper-polluted future.

Mid-term presentation of the post-apocalyptic viewfinder group.
Source: Manuela Valtchanova (2024).

Continuing with the theme of waste, we encounter the group that chose landfills as their subject of investigation. After understanding that there are various landfills scattered throughout Collserola Park, and being a large group sharing a common interest in techno music, they decided to organize a rave. A rave within the landfill, aimed at promoting waste collection while also motivating participants enough to produce a successful project. By designing costumes and managing all aspects of the event, they created a solid starting point for blending an activity typically considered 'unpleasant' with a space of joy and celebration.

Mid-term presentation of the landfill-rave group.
Source: Manuela Valtchanova (2024).

Finally, sticking with the theme of waste, this group chose ‘individual’ litter—the trash found scattered in nature. With a clear focus on the concept of *hyper-objects*, they developed a group game to promote litter collection while also educating participants on the reasoning behind each *objet trouvé*. After several iterations on the game’s dynamics, they arrived at a compelling proposal: a set of three tubes strapped to the back for categorizing collected waste (plastic, paper, and glass), combined with an instruction booklet, a long tape for wrapping objects and creating a series of interactive, real-life maps, and stakes to mark litter-objects.

Mid-term presentation of the *hyper-objects* group.
Source: Manuela Valtchanova (2024).

Annex 4. Conceptual map of the multispecies design referents

GEOGRAPHERS

**SARAH
WHATMORE**

Geographer

**FRANKLIN
GINN**

Geographer

Cultural geography:

The study of the relationship between culture and place.

Materialism:

A tendency to consider material possessions and physical comfort as more important than spiritual values. Nothing exists except matter and its movements and modification.

The strangeness of their life causes fascination, fear and disgust in the aquarium visitor.

The new ways of approaching the nexus between bio (life) and geo (earth), and for that the livingness of the world, are:

Science studies

Technology studies

Performance studies

Politic studies

Captivity and killing causes awkwardness in being together in multispecies entanglements. Studies the differential vulnerability reshaped by being drawn together.

«We are interested in chreatures that bite, sting, fascinate but repulse us, and that must die so that other can live. In those awkward chreatures that not fit the off-the-shelf ethics».

The paper argues for looser mappings of relationality and ethics that attend more fully to the distance between species.

Bestiary of companion species in the domestic garden, in contrast with existing literature papers that explore gardening`s darker aspects.

Understand the life of giant isopods in an aquarium in Japan. Life at depth on the cold, dark ocean floor, eating dead fishes.

Reconstitute the ways we live with non-humans. Describe an ethics based on the relational entanglement of life.
We are conected = We are invited to care

SCIENTISTS

MARC BEKOFF

Biologist

ALEX ZAHARA

Scientist

Comparing Western and Inuit cosmologies differentially inform particular relationships with the inhuman «trash animals».

Waste and wasting exist within a complex set of historically embedded and contemporaneously contested neo-colonial structures and processes.

Through waste, we bequeath a set of politically, historically, and materially constituted relations, structures, norms and practices with which future generations must engage.

Humans have developed sophisticated technologies to squirrel away our discards, and by doing so, to squirrel away «trash animals». **Zero tolerance approach = Vermin Control**

Stresses the importance of interdisciplinary research and collaboration for coming to terms with various aspects of animal behaviour and cognition.

A blending of extraordinary stories of animal joy, empathy, grief, embarrassment, anger and love with the latest scientific research confirming the existence of emotions that common sense and experience have long implied.

Cognitive ethology:

Branch that is concerned with the influence of conscious awareness and intention on the behaviour of an animal. Is the unifying science for understanding the subjective, emotional, empathic, and moral lives of animals. «Understanding them we will understand ourselves».

Explores animal joy, sorrow and empathy, from a scientific point of view, studying social communication in a wide range of species.

How we view animals

How we treat animals

- Who are we in the grand scheme of things?
- What is the role science (science sense) plays in our understanding of the world in which we live?
- What does it mean to «know» something?
- What are other ways of knowing and how do they compare to what we call «science»?
- What are the uses of anecdotes and anthropomorphism in forming studies of animal behaviour?
- Are other minds really all that private and inaccessible?
- Can a non-human animal be called a person?

DESIGNERS

MICHELLE WESTERLAKEN

Interactive Designer

DANIEL J. METCALFE

Designer

GIONATA GATTO

Product Designer

HUGH DUBBERLY

Graphic Designer

Concept of Ecosofia in an speculative design project.

Environmental contamination through the engagement of human and vegetable perspectives.

Research addresses the physical and socio-cultural requirements to more biodiverse human habitats.

Inclusion of a greater diversity of wild animals within human dominated habitats to:

Adress the erosion of biodiversity

Adress the humankind's alienation from nature

Insights of practice work +
Theoretical framework
=
Principles and tools for multispecies design

Advancing decolonial design aims to generate interspecies harmonies rather than reinforcing oppressive relations.

To examine environmental issues by considering a more-than-human viewpoint can introduce alternative scenarios compared to those envisioned through technocentric approaches.

Transdisciplinary tactic: to follow plant collectives across multiple sites and actors that populate their life.

This makes designers to think sustainably by cultivating relations of reciprocity in the multispecies landscapes of the Anthropocene.

Descriptions of design and development processes in every discipline.

Proposes interesting questions: How do we minimize risk while also maximizing creativity?

Biodiversity Erosion:
Encapsulates the notions of habitat and species loss, habitat degradation and habitat fragmentation.

Need of critical contemporary discourses on:

Climate change

Planetary boundaries

provoke

to reject our ways of living and create more desirable alternatives

«Design may have an active role in mitigating the erosion of biodiversity. There is a growing need for a design practice capable of responding to the needs of wild animals».

PHILOSOPHERS

DONNA HARAWAY

Biologist, Philosopher

JAKOB VON UEXKÜLL

Biologist, Philosopher

VINCIANE DESPRET

Philosopher

ISABELLE STENGERS

Philosopher

26 chapters that answer 26 questions to never look at the animal companions the same way again.

Instead of dividing and classifying, we must be bridge-makers (a situated practice).

A monograph that does not point away to a new science. A stroll to unfamiliar worlds: worlds strange to us but known to other creatures. Varied as the animals themselves.

Argues that behaviours we identify as separating humans from animals do not actually properly belong to humans. She does so by exploring incredible and often funny adventures about animals and their involvements with researchers, farmers, etc.

«We must blow a fancy soap bubble around each creature to represent its own world. When we step into these bubbles the familiar meadow is transformed. New relationships appear and a new world comes into being».

«I must accept not to feel free to speak and speculate in a way that would situate others. I must acknowledge the fact that my own practice and tradition situate me on one side of the divide, the side that characterized «others» as animists.»

Let us not committed to the mechanistic theories (like zoologists or physiologists) consider the nature of machines.

Contextual, artistic, scientific and activist practices in diverse sites of exploration.
«Practice and process».
Then a new space for action and imagination is activated, radically realistic.

Philosophical contributions to debates about animal rights and ethics and how we treat our companion species (dogs and more).
«It is a book that works by making connections, by trying to respond where curiosity and sometimes unexpected caring lead» (p.301).
«I`m not advocating cleaning the soul by hygienic reformism. I`m advocating the understanding that earthly heterogeneous beings are in this web together for all time, and no one gets to be Man» (p.82).
«Our political and ecological situation urgently needs a closer look into interrelations, to also spark and dramatize a sensibility for extinction, the disappearance of species as well as our ways of remembering them».

Makes the reader enter a process that confronts them with new habits of making and thinking, and familiarizes them step-by-step with a semiotic-material reality that affords an infinite number of possibilities. So that they assume, test and rehearse other modes of being, distinguished by their capacity to entwine special types of awareness, feeling, perception, and thought, and thereby have their share in creating collective and collaborative vistas and sites for learning to live and die well together.

It comprises everything from personal anecdotes to discussions of philosophers conducted in the impenetrable academia. It makes unexpected, enlightening connections between questions we would rather not answer through the use of material in the stories.

The mythological figures serve as an effective linking tool, they draw connections between both ancient and contemporary practices, provided they all experiment with terrestrial, sympoetic collaborations. The stories gather up the complexes and keep the edges open and greedy for surprising new and old connections.
The context is a timespace that transcends temporalities and spacialities.

Incorporates a narrative perspective that draws attention to the underneath, behind, and beside of the Earth and its mythological and biological entities and practices.

It expresses refusal to be drawn into a «simplistic binary logic» that seeks to define clearly each possible use of an animal as acceptable or not. «Kill responsibly». Practical proposals for laboratory animals. Also PigeonBlog: there is no innocent position regardless how well-intended it might be, rather only situated practices, which are more or less responsible. It always depends on which pigeons, how many and grouped into which ecological and interspecific relations.
«Intimacy without conspiracy».

Claims that accepting the presence of animals with a capacity to respond, not merely to react, will bring us closer to them while still recognizing that we can never feel their pain or speak for them.

DOMINIQUE LESTEL
Philosopher

MICHEL ONFRAY
Philosopher

Qualitative Phenomenological Research Design:
 When grounded in the operational framework of the phenomenological approach, the interpretation of animal life acquires a much more robust character than is usually supposed. This discipline seeks to understand and describe the universal essence of a phenomenon. The approach investigates the everyday experiences of a human being while suspending the researcher's preconceived assumptions about the phenomenon. It studies lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences.

It is opposed to realist-Cartesian paradigm in which most ethology operates.

*See book (+ index).

Travel Diary of the North Pole

Ethnography:
 Descriptive study of popular culture.

Constructivism:
 Theory that says learners construct knowledge rather than just passively take information. As people experience the world and reflect upon these experiences, they build their own representations and incorporate new information into their pre-existing knowledge (schemas).

JOHANNA CAPLIURE
Art critic, Philosopher

FRITJOF CAPRA
Physicist, Philosopher

Sets a scientific language to describe interrelationships and interdependence of psychological, biological, physical, social and cultural phenomena (the «web of life»).

Provides extraordinary new foundations for ecological policies that will allow us to build and sustain communities without diminishing the opportunities for future generations.

Anticipation Storytelling (Despret) + Speculative Fiction (Donna Haraway)

Physics and mysticism to define a new vision of reality.

Scientists have challenged conventional views of evolution and the organization of living systems and have developed new theories with revolutionary and social implications. It is a synthesis of recent scientific breakthroughs of other explanations of the properties of organisms, social systems and ecosystems.

Beyond speculating about its potential, it stands as a reservoir of living, present and shared possibles.

Construction of possible worlds through a fiction political theory placed in the margins of what we call Gaia/Cthulucene.

ANTHROPOLOGISTS

EDUARDO KOHN

Anthropologist

EBEN KIRKSEY

Anthropologist

JON HENRIK ZIEGLER

Anthropologist

Sees landscapes as ongoing materialisation of multispecies mutuality.

Shows how the introduction of high-yielding rice and pentecostalism have led to interruptions in these carefully coordinated temporalities.

Ethnographic atlas of extensive terraced irrigation, by two actions:

Anthropocentric story of human control of plants and animals.

How humans and non-humans are entangled through relations of mutual responsiveness.

- Which beings flourish, and which fail, when natural and cultural worlds collide?
- What happens when organisms are enlisted in the schemes of biotechnology and biocapitalism?
- In blasted landscapes that have been transformed by multiple catastrophes, what are the possibilities of **biocultural hope**?
- **Who benefits when species meet?**

Multispecies ethnographers are studying contact zones where lines separating nature from culture have broken down, where encounters between Homo Sapiens and other beings generate mutual ecologies and coproduced niches.

It is a recipe book of messianic dreams, environmental nightmares, and modest sites of biocultural hope. It is panels, round tables and events in art galleries. A para-site (para-ethnographic field site) where anthropologists and their interlocutors came together to discuss matters of common concern.

Ethnography about how the human has been formed and transformed amidst encounters with multiple species of plants, animals, fungi and microbes. It is important to note that in an ethnography, human beings are the agents around whose actions and intentions the story is written. Now creatures previously appearing on the margins of anthropology have been pressed into the foreground in recent ethnographies.

To answer these questions, **multispecies ethnographers** (a new genre of writing and mode of research, that studies the host of organisms whose lives and deaths are linked to human social worlds, and how these are shaped by political, economic and cultural forces) are collaborating with artists and biological scientists to illuminate how diverse organisms are entangled in political, economic, and cultural systems. Biological and cultural research trajectories (for example, bioartists make tactical interventions to invoke contagious fears - «Paranoia Bugs», by Marnia Johnston).

He stresses that anthropology has not yet fully explored how other beings constitute what it is to be human.

He indicates that trees (and other beings) have the ability to think and discuss how they accomplish this.

Ecology of selves

«If selves are thoughts and the logic through which they interact is semiotic, then relation is interpretation» (p.83).

Semiotics (the study of signs and symbols and their use or interpretation) to state that all beings can represent, produce and interpret signs.

Treating selves as objects and being unable to see beyond oneself or one's kind is the cause of not understanding the interconnectedness of nature.

Annex 5. Sophie Vanderschueren interview

12 de març, 2024 [11h]

SOPHIE VANDERSCHUEREN
Coordinatrice de projets de médiation scientifique
T. +94 43 279 2(0) 32 – sophie.vanderschueren@brucity.be
Pas présente le vendredi
VILLE DE BRUXELLES
Culture, jeunesse et sports
Musée des Egouts – Riolenmuseum
Porte d’Anderlecht
www.bruxelles.be • www.brussel.be • Suivez-nous sur les réseaux sociaux

It was a 45-minute interview. The earlier segments were not recorded correctly, but I took notes in my notebook afterward, and these are included in the corresponding section of the report. The original interview was in English, translated into Catalan according to our interpretation.

Sophie Vanderschueren: – So, the *Here starts the sea* exhibition explains that sewers are not trash cans, to raise awareness of the fact that: no, you cannot pour frying oil down the drain, you cannot dispose of many of the products used for cleaning or doing – I don’t know what else at home. Some people also throw things on the street, and with the rain or wind, these things end up in the sewers, or old medicines that are no longer used, they cannot be disposed of without considering where they will end up. Many people flush them down the toilet. Also, a lot of people use baby wipes, flush them down the toilet, and cause huge complications when they reach the water treatment plants. They block the whole system, so it’s a mess. And, of course, toxic substances like solvents, paints—many people also flush these down the toilet. It’s important to raise awareness about this and to explain that there are alternatives for disposing of these products, so we explain where they should be thrown away. We also want to make it clear that in a normal system, our wastewater from homes or streets goes to large sewer collectors and then to treatment plants. There, it’s cleaned again, but not everything can be cleaned. There are many products, like paint, for example, that need to be cleaned in a specific way. Many products are not cleaned here, but after going through the cleaning process, they return to the sand, and the clean water returns to the sand, but the water is not %100 clean. What happens when it rains heavily is that the sewer collectors also fill up with rainwater, so it’s a mix of wastewater and rainwater. The system becomes completely saturated, and then we have these river overflows. Without first going through the treatment station, it overflows with everything inside, with the wipes, with the paints, with the plastic items that people throw on the ground. With everything. That’s why we raise awareness about the treatment plants.

Cristina Sanuy: – That’s interesting. In Barcelona, we don’t have much publicity about the effects of this.

S: – What river is there in Barcelona?

C: – Well, we have two rivers surrounding Barcelona, the Besòs and the Llobregat.

S: - Here we raise awareness about urban rivers. The water goes into the sewer system, goes to the treatment plant, and then returns to the river, and then it goes to the ocean. It's not a closed system. But our drinking water comes from the Meuse River, which is a river here in Belgium. There are various places where they collect water from this river. We have... this water collector. We have others, but this is the largest. And then in Modave, they don't take water from a river, but from an aquifer, which is already almost potable, with all the layers it has passed through. But this way, the water comes from there, it has to travel through underground pipes to get to Brussels. There it stays in the Brussels system where they store the drinking water, and then it goes to all the city's residents.

C: - Yes, in Barcelona, we have something similar. At the treatment plant, they treat this wastewater, and they clean it again. They perform another treatment.

S: - But then you're always reusing the same water, as I understand it. That's really smart. From what I know, treating wastewater to make it potable again would be a much higher cost. And also, you really take water from the rivers, and you don't put it back into the rivers, so how... I mean, if we constantly took the water but didn't return it, I think it would have problems for the river's diversity as well. So...

C: - Okay. I haven't delved too deeply into the water issue yet.

S: - I have a visit now. So, if you still have questions, you can always send me an email with your question, and I'll answer it as best as I can.

C: - Thank you. I have one last question: Do you know any expert I could contact? Someone who researches the animals living in the sewers?

S: - I think I should refer you to the administration responsible for the environment. It's *Brussels Environment*. They have a water department, where they also manage the river sediment that flows here. They aren't sewer experts; that's *Vivaqua*, but as I said, I think they would have different answers than what you're looking for. *Brussels Environment* has experts in biodiversity, aquatic systems, but I can't think of anyone... I mean, the experts I know are river experts, but not really in river diversity. But then you have the biodiversity department, but they aren't specifically aware of what's in the sediment, I think. But both have websites with a lot of information, so I think you can start there. They also have, like, emails or forms you can fill out, and they are quite responsive. So, if you have questions, they will be very attentive.

C: - Thank you very much. I'll ask them.

S: - I'm sorry I can't help more. These are questions we're not used to. If something or someone comes to mind, I'll contact you.

C: - Please do, thank you.

S: - Great! So now you can simply go to the other building, and there you can start the full visit.

C: - Thank you very much. Goodbye!

Annex 6. Images of the temporary exhibition

TU AS UNE DENT CONTRE MOI ?
Je suis capable de ronger à peu près tout et n'épargne qu'il y a même occasion la face antérieure de mes incisives à une dureté de 65 sur l'échelle de Mohs.

En compression, le diamant a une dureté de 10, la porcelaine 7, l'acier 5,5, le cuivre 3 et les ongles, en fait 2,2.

WIL JE ME AAN DE TAND VOLEN!
Ik kan het wel alles smijgen met mijn tanden. Het grootste nadeel is natuurlijk dat mijn tanden heel hard zijn en dat ik er niet mee kan spelen.

* Het belangrijkste: diamant heeft een hardheid van 10, porselein 7, staal 5,5, koper 3 en je vingertoppen slechts 2,2.

Les objets rongés laissent parfois des traces. Observez les traces de ces matériaux sur le dent. Vous devriez trouver des résidus à leur surface: plastique, bois, bois dur, cuivre, dentelle...

Algemeen: Voorwerpen nemen een beetje weg, maar ik heb mijn tanden niet nodig. Er zijn namelijk maar weinig materialen die bestand zijn tegen mijn tanden. Het belangrijkste: diamant, staal, koper, tin, zilver, goud, zilver...

Diamant
porcelaine
porselijn
copper
koper
ongles
vingertoppen
MOHS

POURQUOI EST-CE QUE J'AI LES DENTS ORANGES?
Il y a de très nombreuses raisons de cela. Les dents sont faites de dentine et de pulpe dentaire. La dentine est un matériau très dur et résistant. La pulpe dentaire est un tissu vivant et sensible.

MAIS POURQUOI EST-CE QUE J'AI LES DENTS ORANGES?
C'est parce que les dents sont faites de dentine et de pulpe dentaire. La dentine est un matériau très dur et résistant. La pulpe dentaire est un tissu vivant et sensible.

TU?

VIE BEN JE, RATTUS?

RATTUS LAB

Annex 7. Images of the permanent exhibition (*Brussels Sewer Museum*)

DÉRATISEUR

Un métier qui ne date pas d'hier.

Ernest Henry Gilson, Le chien terrifié et le rat, 1875, Wellcome Collection.
Ernest Henry Gilson, Un terrifié en le rat, gravure, 1875, Wellcome Collection.

Gravure d'après Vischer Cornelis (1879-1890), Un dératiseur à l'œuvre. Wellcome Collection.
Gravure naar Cornelis Vischer (1829-1890), Een rattenbestrijder in de werf. Wellcome Collection.

Fernand Pelez de Cordova (1820-1899), Un singe déguisé en dératiseur, dessin et aquarelle 1853, Wellcome Collection.
Fernand Pelez de Cordova (1820-1899), Een aap vermomd als rattenveger, tekening en aquarelle 1853, Wellcome Collection.

Jan Jans van der Vlist, Dératiseur, gravure, ca 1810, Wellcome Collection.
Jan Jans van der Vlist, Rattenbestrijder, gravure, ca 1810, Wellcome Collection.

RATTENBESTRIJDER:

Een job van alle tijden.

S.O.S!

LA VIE ANIMALE DANS LES ÉGOUTS

LE RAT N'EST PAS LE SEUL OCCUPANT DU RÉSEAU.
EN EFFET, CE MILIEU POURTANT AGRESSIF SEMBLE CONVENIR
PARFAITEMENT À CERTAINES ESPÈCES ANIMALES.
IL N'EST PAR EXEMPLE PAS RARE D'Y CROISER DES LIMACES,
DES MOUSTIQUES, DES GRENOUILLES, ET POURQUOI PAS
DES ALLIGATORS...

En début de parcours, certains égouts qui récoltent les eaux claires des réseaux présentent un taux de pollution peu élevé qui convient aux batraciens comme la grenouille.

Le réseau d'assainissement, dans sa vaste étendue, compte de nombreuses zones inondées irrégulièrement. L'eau qui y stagne forme un habitat idéal pour les larves de moustiques.

Et les alligators ?

"il y a des alligators dans les égouts de New-York. A l'origine, ramenés en ville comme animaux de compagnie, ils ont ensuite été chassés des appartements trop étroits par les toilettes, colonisant ainsi les égouts dont ils ont fait leur domaine."

Cette histoire est connue de tout le monde, elle prend parfois même place à Bruxelles. Il s'agit pourtant d'une légende urbaine, collective et anonyme.

Mais sait-on jamais ?...

Service des Égouts. Illustrations J.J. Maquaire

DE FAUNA VAN DE RIOOL

DE RAT IS NIET DE ENIGE BEWONER VAN HET RIOOLSTELSEL.
BEPAALE DIERSOORTEN VOELEN ZICH BLIJKBAAR IN HUN NOPJES IN DIT
NOCHTANS AGRESSIEVE MILIEU. NIET ZELDEN TREF JE ER BIJVOORBEELD
DIEREN AAN ZOALS SLAKKEN, MUGGEN, KIKKERS, EN ZELFS ALLIGATORS...

Bepaalde rioolleidingen, die vooraan in het stelsel zijn gelegen en het helder water uit de goten opvangen, vertonen een geringe vervuilinggraad, wat naar de zin is van amfibieën zoals de kikker.

Het rioleringsnet telt, in zijn uitgestrektheid, talrijke gebieden die op onregelmatige wijze overstromen. Het water dat er blijft stilstaan, vormt een ideale habitat voor muggenlarven.

En de alligators?

*"Er leven alligators in de riolen van New York.
Ze werden oorspronkelijk meegebracht naar de stad
als gezelschapsdier, werden vervolgens uit de veel
te kleine appartementen verjaagd via de toiletten,
en hebben sindsdien hun intrek genomen
in de riolen."*

Iedereen kent dit verhaal.
In sommige versies speelt
het zich zelfs af in Brussel.
Het is echter een stadslegende.
Hoewel...

Rioleringsdienst. Illustraties J.J. Maquaire

Annex 9. Software 1

@author: csanuy

#####

#libraries to import

```
import pandas as pd #data manipulation and analisis
import numpy as np #numerical operations
import os #interaction with the operative system of the computer
from scipy.io import wavfile #read and generate WAV filters
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt #plot graphs
```

%% 01:

#Code to read WAV files and plot graphs of the sound waves and respective spectrograms. Files without filtering.

Define the ubication of the WAV files in the computer folders

```
base_path = os.path.expanduser("~/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so")
wav_files = [
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Primer Pis_Tr1.WAV'), #Omnidirectional microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Primer Pis_Tr2.WAV'), #Tie microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Primer Pis_TrLR.wav'), #Recorder microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Segon Pis_Tr1.WAV'), #Omnidirectional microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Segon Pis_Tr2.WAV'),#Tie microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Segon Pis_TrLR.WAV'),#Recorder microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Clavegueram_Tr1.WAV'),#Omnidirectional microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Clavegueram_Tr2.WAV'),#Tie microphone
    os.path.join(base_path, 'Clavegueram_TrLR.WAV')#Recorder microphone
]
```

Read the WAV file

```
for wav_file_path in wav_files:
    # Check if the file exists
    if not os.path.isfile(wav_file_path):
        raise FileNotFoundError(f"No such file: '{wav_file_path}'")
    sampling_rate, audio_data = wavfile.read(wav_file_path)
```

Set the length of the file

```
duration = 1000 #seconds
num_samples = duration * sampling_rate
audio_data_10s = audio_data[:num_samples]
time_array = np.arange(num_samples) / sampling_rate
```

Create a figure to ensure that all plots are aligned with a Gridspec Layout

```
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10 ,15))
gs = fig.add_gridspec(2 ,2, width_ratios=[0.05 ,1], height_ratios=[1 ,1], hspace=0.3, wspace=0.02)
#the grid is 2x2
```

```

# Draw the sound wave as the first figure
ax_wave = fig.add_subplot(gs[0,0])
ax_wave.plot(time_array, audio_data_10s_wave)
#Write the title and labels for the drawing
ax_wave.set_title('Ona de so del fitxer WAV original')
ax_wave.set_xlabel('Temps [s]')
ax_wave.set_ylabel('Amplada')

# Draw the spectrogram as the second figure
ax_spec = fig.add_subplot(gs[0,1], sharex=ax_wave) #shares axis X with the first figure
spec, freqs, bins, im = ax_spec.specgram(audio_data_10s_wave, NFFT=1024, Fs=sampling_rate,
noverlap=512)
#Write the title and labels for the drawing
ax_spec.set_title('Espectrograma del fitxer WAV original')
ax_spec.set_xlabel('Temps [s]')
ax_spec.set_ylabel('Freqüència [Hz]')

# Add a legend for the spectrogram
cax = fig.add_subplot(gs[1,1])
fig.colorbar(im, cax=cax, label='Intensitat [dB]') #indicates intensity in decibels

#Adjust the layout
plt.setp(ax_wave.get_xticklabels(), visible=False)
plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.1) #espai entre les dues figures

plt.show()

```

%% 02

#Code to clean the sound with FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) and spectral analysis techniques. Obtaining figure and spectrogram.

```
# Apply FFT
```

```
audio_data_fft = fft(audio_data_segment)
```

```
# Identify the main noise frequencies
```

```
# Calculate the power spectrum
```

```
power_spectrum = np.abs(audio_data_fft) ** 2
```

```
# Find the frequency bands
```

```
freqs = np.fft.fftfreq(len(audio_data_fft), 1/sampling_rate)
```

```
# Identify the main noise frequencies by finding the indices where the power spectrum exceeds a certain threshold
```

```
threshold = np.max(power_spectrum) * 0.1 # lliurar al %10 del valor màxim de l'espectre de potència
```

```
indices = np.where(power_spectrum > threshold)
```

```
main_noise_freqs = freqs[indices]
```

```
# Remove identified noise frequencies
```

```
# Create a mask to remove noise frequencies within a given range
```

```

cleaned_audio_fft = audio_data_fft.copy()
for noise_freq in main_noise_freqs:
idx = np.where((freqs > noise_freq - 5) & (freqs < noise_freq + 5)) # 5Hz interval above and below each
identified frequency
cleaned_audio_fft[idx] = 0

# Turn on the inverse FFT to get the clean signal
cleaned_audio_data = ifft(cleaned_audio_fft).real

# Create a time array for the seconds defined above
time_array = np.arange(start_sample, start_sample + num_samples) / sampling_rate

# Draw the sound waves of the original signal and the net
fig, (ax_orig, ax_clean) = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(10, 15), sharex=True)

ax_orig.plot(time_array, audio_data_segment, label='Original', color='#543719')
ax_orig.set_title('Senyal Original'),
ax_orig.set_ylabel('Amplada')

ax_clean.plot(time_array, cleaned_audio_data, label='Filtrada', color='#543719')
ax_clean.set_title('Senyal Filtrada'),
ax_clean.set_xlabel('Temps [s]')
ax_clean.set_ylabel('Amplada')

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

%% 03

Code that performs a NOTCH type filtering to eliminate frequencies around 43Hz. Draw the original and filtered sound wave and the respective spectrograms.

Design a notch filter to remove frequencies around 43 Hz with a bandwidth of 2 Hz

```

center_freq = 43.0 # Frequency
quality_factor = 2.0 / 43.0 # Bandwidth
b, a = iirnotch(center_freq, quality_factor, sampling_rate)

```

Apply the notch filter

```

filtered_audio_data = filtfilt(b, a, audio_data_10s)

```

Create a time matrix

```

time_array = np.arange(num_samples) / sampling_rate

```

Draw the original and filtered sound wave

```

fig, (ax_orig, ax_filt) = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(10, 15), sharex=True)

```

```

ax_orig.plot(time_array, audio_data_10s, label='Original')
ax_orig.set_title('Ona Sonora Original')
ax_orig.set_ylabel('Amplada')

```

```
ax_filt.plot(time_array, filtered_audio_data, label='Filtrada', color='orange')
ax_filt.set_title('Ona Sonora Filtrada (43 Hz)')
ax_filt.set_xlabel('Temps [s]')
ax_filt.set_ylabel('Amplada')
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Draw the spectrogram for the filtered signal

```
fig, (ax_orig_spec, ax_filt_spec) = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(10, 15), sharex=True)
```

```
ax_orig_spec.specgram(audio_data_10s, NFFT=1024, Fs=sampling_rate, noverlap=512)
ax_orig_spec.set_title('Espectrograma de la Senyal Original')
ax_orig_spec.set_ylabel('Freqüència [Hz]')
```

Ensure that there are no zero values in the spectrogram matrix to avoid dividing by zero

```
Pxx, freqs, bins, im = ax_filt_spec.specgram(filtered_audio_data, NFFT=1024, Fs=sampling_rate,
noverlap=512)
```

```
Pxx[Pxx == 0] = np.finfo(float).eps # Replace the zeros with a very small value
```

```
ax_filt_spec.imshow(10 * np.log10(Pxx), aspect='auto', origin='lower',
                    extent=[bins.min(), bins.max(), freqs.min(), freqs.max()])
ax_filt_spec.set_title('Espectrograma de la Senyal Filtrada (43 Hz)')
ax_filt_spec.set_xlabel('Temps [s]')
ax_filt_spec.set_ylabel('Freqüència [Hz]')
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

%% 04

Code to visualize the FFT (not used, just to validate that in the previous code the FFT has been applied correctly)

Activate the FFT of the original and filtered signal.

Convert time domain signals to frequency domain.

```
fft_orig = np.fft.fft(audio_data_10s)
fft_filt = np.fft.fft(filtered_audio_data)
freqs = np.fft.fftfreq(len(fft_orig), 1/sampling_rate)
```

Draw the FFT of the original signal and the filtered one in the same drawing

```
plt.figure(figsize=(6, 15))
plt.plot(freqs[:len(freqs)//2], np.abs(fft_orig)[:len(freqs)//2], label='Original')
plt.plot(freqs[:len(freqs)//2], np.abs(fft_filt)[:len(freqs)//2], label='Filtrada', color='orange')
plt.title('FFT del senyal original i del filtrat')
plt.xlabel('Freqüència (Hz)')
plt.ylabel('Magnitud')
plt.legend()
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```

%% 05

```
# Code to obtain sound wave with threshold and categorized events

# Calculate the mean and standard deviation of the filtered audio signal
mean_val = np.mean(filtered_audio_data)
std_dev = np.std(filtered_audio_data)
threshold = mean_val + 4 * std_dev # Threshold set as 4 times the standard deviation above the mean

# Identify the pieces that exceed the selected threshold
peaks, properties = find_peaks(np.abs(filtered_audio_data), height=threshold)

# Group peaks by time using DBSCAN
peak_times = peaks.reshape(-1,1) / sampling_rate
db = DBSCAN(eps=0.1, min_samples=1).fit(peak_times) # eps is the maximum distance between points per second
labels = db.labels_

# Create time vector in seconds
time = np.arange(num_samples) / sampling_rate

# Draw the sound wave with the peaks and groups categorized
plt.figure(figsize=(6,15))
plt.plot(time, filtered_audio_data, label='Àudio filtrat')

for label in np.unique(labels):
    label_peaks = peaks[labels == label]
    plt.plot(label_peaks / sampling_rate, filtered_audio_data[label_peaks], 'o', label=f'Cluster {label}')

plt.axhline(y=threshold, color='r', linestyle='--', label='Lindar')
plt.axhline(y=-threshold, color='r', linestyle='--')
plt.title('Àudio filtrat amb esdeveniments categoritzats')
plt.xlabel('Temps [s]')
plt.ylabel('Amplada')
plt.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(1,1.05), loc='upper left', ncol=3) # Position the legend outside the graphic
plt.tight_layout(rect=[1,0.85,0,0]) # Adjust the layout to make room for the legend
plt.show()

print("Índex dels esdeveniments categoritzats:", labels)
```

%% 06

```
# Code to get the three sound waves from the three recordings, with the threshold marked and the events, for comparison. It is decided not to use it to categorize the clusters.

def process_wav_file(wav_file_path, center_freq, quality_factor, threshold_factor, start_time, end_time):
    sampling_rate, audio_data = wavfile.read(wav_file_path)

    # Extract the audio data between the seconds start_time and end_time
    start_sample = int(start_time * sampling_rate)
```

```

end_sample = int(end_time * sampling_rate)
audio_data = audio_data[start_sample:end_sample]

# Apply notch filter
b, a = iirnotch(center_freq, quality_factor, sampling_rate,
padlen = min(2, len(audio_data) - 1)
filtered_audio_data = filtfilt(b, a, audio_data, padlen=padlen)

# Calculates the mean and standard deviation of the filtered audio signal
mean_val = np.mean(filtered_audio_data)
std_dev = np.std(filtered_audio_data)
threshold = mean_val + threshold_factor * std_dev

# Identify peaks that exceed the threshold
peaks, properties = find_peaks(np.abs(filtered_audio_data), height=threshold,
return sampling_rate, filtered_audio_data, peaks, std_dev

def cluster_peaks(peaks, sampling_rate, eps=0.014):
    peak_times = peaks.reshape(-1,1) / sampling_rate
    db = DBSCAN(eps=eps, min_samples=1).fit(peak_times)
    labels = db.labels_

    return labels

# Index each of the categorized clusters/events, with different colors
def match_clusters(peaks1, peaks2, labels1, labels2, sampling_rate, time_threshold=0.014):
    unique_labels1 = np.unique(labels1)
    unique_labels2 = np.unique(labels2)

    common_labels = []
    unmatched_labels1 = set(unique_labels1)
    unmatched_labels2 = set(unique_labels2)

    tree2 = cKDTree(peaks2.reshape(-1,1) / sampling_rate)

    for label1 in unique_labels1:
        cluster_peaks1 = peaks1[labels1 == label1].reshape(-1,1) / sampling_rate
        dists, indices = tree2.query(cluster_peaks1, k=1)

        if np.isscalar(dists):
            dists = [dists]
            indices = [indices]

        for dist, idx in zip(dists, indices):
            if dist <= time_threshold:
                label2 = labels2[idx]
                if label2 in unmatched_labels2:
                    common_labels.append((label1, label2))
                    unmatched_labels1.discard(label1)
                    unmatched_labels2.discard(label2)

```

```

        break

    return common_labels, list(unmatched_labels1), list(unmatched_labels2)

# Update these paths to the correct file locations on the system
wav_file_path1 = '/Users/cris/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so/Primer Pis_Tr1.WAV'
wav_file_path2 = '/Users/cris/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so/Primer Pis_Tr2.WAV'
wav_file_path3 = '/Users/cris/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so/Primer Pis_TrLR.WAV'

# parameters
center_freq = 43.0 # Center the frequency of the notch filter
quality_factor = 2.0 / 43.0 # Quality factor for a 2 Hz bandwidth
threshold_factor = 5 # Threshold factor for peak detection
start_time = 0 # Start time in seconds
end_time = 1000 # Final time in seconds
eps = 0.014 # DBSCAN parameter to group by seconds
time_threshold = 0.014 # Time threshold for matching clusters in seconds

# Process WAV files
sampling_rate1, filtered_audio_data1, peaks1, std_dev1 = process_wav_file(wav_file_path1, center_freq,
quality_factor, threshold_factor, start_time, end_time)
sampling_rate2, filtered_audio_data2, peaks2, std_dev2 = process_wav_file(wav_file_path2, center_
freq, quality_factor, threshold_factor, start_time, end_time)
sampling_rate3, filtered_audio_data3, peaks3, std_dev3 = process_wav_file(wav_file_path3, center_
freq, quality_factor, threshold_factor, start_time, end_time)

# Cluster peaks
labels1 = cluster_peaks(peaks1, sampling_rate1, eps)
labels2 = cluster_peaks(peaks2, sampling_rate2, eps)
labels3 = cluster_peaks(peaks3, sampling_rate3, eps)

# Match the clusters
common_labels, unmatched_labels1, unmatched_labels2 = match_clusters(peaks1, peaks2, labels1,
labels2, sampling_rate1, time_threshold)

# Generate image/figure
fig, (ax1, ax2, ax3) = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(15, 12), sharex=True, sharey=True)
time_axis1 = np.arange(len(filtered_audio_data1)) / sampling_rate1 + start_time
time_axis2 = np.arange(len(filtered_audio_data2)) / sampling_rate2 + start_time
time_axis3 = np.arange(len(filtered_audio_data3)) / sampling_rate3 + start_time

colors = plt.cm.tab10(np.linspace(10, 1, 0))

# Define a function to represent each signal with its peaks and clusters
def plot_signal(ax, time_axis, signal, std_dev, peaks, labels, title):
    ax.plot(time_axis, signal / std_dev, label='Filtered Audio')
    for label in np.unique(labels):

        if label < 10: # Legend (10 color blocks)
            label_peaks = peaks[labels == label]

```

```

        color = colors[label % 10]
        ax.plot(label_peaks / sampling_rate1 + start_time, signal[label_peaks] / std_dev, 'o',
label=f'Cluster {label}', color=color)
    else: # Color remaining clusters but do not include in the legend
        label_peaks = peaks[labels == label]
        color = colors[label % 10]
        ax.plot(label_peaks / sampling_rate1 + start_time, signal[label_peaks] / std_dev, 'o',
color='#543719')
    ax.axhline(y=threshold_factor, color='r', linestyle='--', label='Threshold')
    ax.axhline(y=-threshold_factor, color='r', linestyle='--')
    ax.set_title(title)
    ax.set_ylabel('Amplitude (in multiples of std)')
    ax.label_outer()

plot_signal(ax1, time_axis1, filtered_audio_data1, std_dev1, peaks1, labels1, 'Filtered Audio Signal 1 with
Clustered Events')
plot_signal(ax2, time_axis2, filtered_audio_data2, std_dev2, peaks2, labels2, 'Filtered Audio Signal 2
with Clustered Events')
plot_signal(ax3, time_axis3, filtered_audio_data3, std_dev3, peaks3, labels3, 'Filtered Audio Signal 3
(mono_output.wav) with Clustered Events')
ax3.set_xlabel('Time (seconds)')

```

Design the caption

```

handles, labels = [], []
for ax in [ax1, ax2, ax3]:
    for handle, label in zip(*ax.get_legend_handles_labels()):
        if 'Cluster' in label and label not in labels and len(labels) < 10: # Include only the first ten clusters
            handles.append(handle)
            labels.append(label)

```

Define the position of the legend

```

fig.subplots_adjust(left=0.3, right=0.95, top=0.95, bottom=0.05)
fig.legend(handles, labels, loc='center left', ncol=1, bbox_to_anchor=(0.5, 0.0), fontsize='small')

```

Synchronize zoom and pan between subframes

```

def on_xlim_changed(event_ax):
    for ax in [ax1, ax2, ax3]:
        if ax != event_ax:
            ax.set_xlim(event_ax.get_xlim())
    plt.draw()

```

```

def on_ylim_changed(event_ax):
    for ax in [ax1, ax2, ax3]:
        if ax != event_ax:
            ax.set_ylim(event_ax.get_ylim())
    plt.draw()

```

```

ax1.callbacks.connect('xlim_changed', on_xlim_changed)
ax2.callbacks.connect('xlim_changed', on_xlim_changed)
ax3.callbacks.connect('xlim_changed', on_xlim_changed)

```

```

ax1.callbacks.connect('ylim_changed', on_ylim_changed)
ax2.callbacks.connect('ylim_changed', on_ylim_changed)
ax3.callbacks.connect('ylim_changed', on_ylim_changed)

plt.show()

```

%% 07

Classification of sounds (CODE USED TO SEPARATE THE SOURCE AND CALCULATE ARRIVAL TIMES)

```

def apply_threshold(signal, threshold):
    # Apply the threshold and return only segments that exceed the threshold
    mask = np.abs(signal) > threshold
    return signal[mask], mask

# Parameters
center_freq = 43.0
quality_factor = 2.0 / 43.0
start_time = 0
end_time = 1000
downsample_factor = 10

# Define the thresholds for each signal (Mic.1, Mic.2 and Mic.3)
thresholds = [5000 ,25000 ,25000]

wav_file_paths = [
    '/Users/cris/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so/Primer Pis_Tr1.WAV',
    '/Users/cris/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so/Primer Pis_Tr2.WAV',
    '/Users/cris/Desktop/TFM/Proves de so/Primer Pis_TrLR.WAV'
]

# Process and track each audio file
fig, axes = plt.subplots(len(wav_file_paths), 1, figsize=(18 ,12)) # Adjust the size of the figure to fit all plots

for i, wav_file_path in enumerate(wav_file_paths):
    print(f"\nProcessing WAV file {i+1}...")

    time_axis, filtered_audio_data, downsampled_sampling_rate = process_wav_file(wav_file_path,
center_freq, quality_factor, start_time, end_time, downsample_factor)

    # Apply amplitude threshold
    filtered_audio_data_thresholded, mask = apply_threshold(filtered_audio_data, thresholds[i])
    time_axis_thresholded = time_axis[mask]

# Generate variations of the audio signal to have multiple components
def generate_variations(signal, n_variations):
    variations = []
    for i in range(n_variations):
        noise = np.random.normal(0.01 ,0, signal.shape)
        variations.append(signal + noise)

```

```

return np.array(variations).T

# Generate initial variations
audio_matrix = generate_variations(filtered_audio_data_thresholded, 5)

# Apply ICA to separate sources
ica = FastICA()
sources = ica.fit_transform(audio_matrix)
n_components = ica.components_.shape[0]

# Scales the separate sources to match the amplitude of the original signal
for j in range(n_components):
    sources[:, j] = sources[:, j] * (np.max(np.abs(filtered_audio_data_thresholded)) / np.max(np.
abs(sources[:, j])))

# Trace base audio and separate source
axes[i].plot(time_axis_thresholded, sources[:, 4], label='Separated Source 5', color='#543719')
axes[i].plot(time_axis, filtered_audio_data, label='Base Audio', color='#543719', alpha=0.5)
axes[i].set_xlabel('Time (seconds)')
axes[i].set_ylabel('Amplitude')
axes[i].legend()
axes[i].grid(True)
axes[i].set_title(f'Separated Source 5 and Base Audio for {wav_file_path}')

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Annex 10. Software 2

```
@author: csanuy  
''''''
```

libraries to import

```
import numpy as np # numeric operations  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt # plot graphs
```

%% 01

```
# Base grid with transparent background, of the First and Second Floors.
```

```
# Create the figure and axis
```

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(3.5 ,10))
```

```
# Draw the grid
```

```
ax.set_xlim(1140 ,0)
```

```
ax.set_ylim(400 ,0)
```

```
ax.grid(True, which='both', linestyle='--', linewidth=0.5)
```

```
# Define axis labels
```

```
ax.set_xticks(np.arange(100 ,1141 ,0))
```

```
ax.set_yticks(np.arange(100 ,401 ,0))
```

```
ax.xaxis.set_major_formatter(plt.FuncFormatter(lambda x, _: f'{x:.0f}'))
```

```
ax.yaxis.set_major_formatter(plt.FuncFormatter(lambda y, _: f'{y:.0f}'))
```

```
# Set grid lines in increments of 10
```

```
for y in range(10 ,400 ,0):
```

```
    ax.axhline(y, color='gray', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.1)
```

```
for x in range(10 ,1140 ,0):
```

```
    ax.axvline(x, color='gray', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.1)
```

```
# Axis labels
```

```
ax.set_xlabel('Distància (cm)')
```

```
ax.set_ylabel('Distància (cm)')
```

```
# Graph title
```

```
ax.set_title('Triangulación de la Posición del Emisor de Sonido')
```

```
# Save graphic as PNG with transparent background
```

```
plt.savefig('/Users/cris/Desktop/triangulacion_emisor.png', transparent=True)
```

```
# Show graph
```

```
plt.show()
```

```

# %% 02
# Scenography of the flats

# Microphone coordinates (in cm)
micros = np.array([
    [10 ,450],
    [10 ,650],
    [10 ,850]
])

# Noise arrival time (in sec): DEFINE ACCORDING TO THE CALCULATION PERFORMED
t = np.array([0.0105 ,0.0134 ,0.01785])

# Speed of noise (in m/s): Normal conditions
v = 343.2

# Convert arrival times to distances (in cm)
d = t * v * 100

# Calculate the coordinates of the emitter (intersection of the circles)
x_inter = (micros[0 ,0] + micros[0 ,1] + micros[0 ,2]) / 3
y_inter = (micros[1 ,0] + micros[1 ,1] + micros[1 ,2]) / 3

# Create the figure and axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(3.5 ,10))

# Draw the grid
ax.set_xlim(1140 ,0)
ax.set_ylim(400 ,0)
ax.xaxis.set_major_locator(plt.MultipleLocator(100))
ax.yaxis.set_major_locator(plt.MultipleLocator(100))

# Show grid lines in increments of 10
for y in range(10 ,400 ,0):
    ax.axhline(y, color='gray', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.1)
for x in range(10 ,1140 ,0):
    ax.axvline(x, color='gray', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.1)

# List of colors of the circles
colors = ['#FF8#', '0000B0000', '#FF7F50']

# Draw the circles around each microphone with corresponding colors
for i in range(len(micros)):
    circle = plt.Circle((micros[i, 0], micros[i, 1]), d[i], color=colors[i], fill=False, linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5,
label=f'Micro {i+1}')
    ax.add_artist(circle)
    # Mark the position of the microphones with the same color of the circle
    ax.plot(micros[i, 0], micros[i, 1], marker='o', markersize=5, color=colors[i], label=f'Micro {i+1}')

```

```

# Delete grid lines only
ax.grid(False)

# Axis labels
ax.set_xlabel('Distància (cm)')
ax.set_ylabel('Distància (cm)')

# Save graphic as PNG with transparent background
plt.savefig('/Users/cris/Desktop/triangulacion_emisor.png', transparent=True)

plt.show()

```

%% 03

Sewer system of Barcelona (section of the installation)

Draw the grid

```

ax.set_xlim(1000 ,0)
ax.set_ylim(800 ,0)
ax.xaxis.set_major_locator(plt.MultipleLocator(100))
ax.yaxis.set_major_locator(plt.MultipleLocator(100))

```

Set grid lines in increments of 10

```

for y in range(10 ,800 ,0):
    ax.axhline(y, color='gray', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.1)
for x in range(10 ,1000 ,0):
    ax.axvline(x, color='gray', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.1)

```

List of colors of the circles

```

colors = ['#FF8#', '0000B0000', '#FF7F50']

```

Draw the circles around each microphone with corresponding colors

```

for i in range(len(micros)):
    circle = plt.Circle((micros[i, 0], micros[i, 1]), d[i], color=colors[i], fill=False, linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5,
label=f'Micro {i+1}')
    ax.add_artist(circle)
    # Mark the position of the microphones with the same color of the circle
    ax.plot(micros[i, 0], micros[i, 1], marker='o', markersize=5, color=colors[i], label=f'Micro {i+1}')

```

Draw the map (set the start and end coordinates of the line manually)

```

x_start, y_start = 20 ,0 # initial coordinates
x_end, y_end = 20 ,1000 # final coordinates
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

```

```

x_start, y_start = 70 ,0
x_end, y_end = 70 ,1000
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

```

```

x_start, y_start = 120 ,0
x_end, y_end = 120 ,1000

```

```

ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 170 ,0
x_end, y_end = 170 ,50
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 170 ,190
x_end, y_end = 540 ,1000
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 170 ,50
x_end, y_end = 600 ,1000
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 170 ,190
x_end, y_end = 170 ,1000
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 220 ,0
x_end, y_end = 220 ,25
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 323 ,252
x_end, y_end = 660 ,1000
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 299 ,200
x_end, y_end = 750 ,0
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 323 ,252
x_end, y_end = 800 ,33
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 220 ,25
x_end, y_end = 299 ,200
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 450 ,1000
x_end, y_end = 430 ,960
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 430 ,960
x_end, y_end = 380 ,940
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

x_start, y_start = 380 ,940
x_end, y_end = 280 ,1000
ax.plot([x_start, x_end], [y_start, y_end], color='#543719', linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)

```

```
# Delete grid lines only
ax.grid(False)

# Axis labels
ax.set_xlabel('Distància (cm)')
ax.set_ylabel('Distància (cm)')

# Save graphic as PNG with transparent background
plt.savefig('/Users/cris/Desktop/triangulacion_emisor.png', transparent=True)

plt.show()
```

Annex 11. Fitxa Tècnica Micròfon KY-038

KY-038 Microphone sound sensor module

Contents

1 Picture	1
2 Technical data / Short description	1
3 Pinout	2
4 Functionality of the sensor	2
5 Code example Arduino	3
6 Code example Raspberry Pi	4

Picture

Technical data / Short description

Digital Out: You can use a potentiometer to configure an extreme value for the sonic. IF the value exceeds the extreme value it will send a signal via digital out.

Analog Out: Direct microphone signal as voltage value

LED1: Shows that the sensor is supplied with voltage

LED2: Shows that a magnetic field was detected

Pinout

Functionality of the sensor

The sensor has 3 main components on its circuit board. First, the sensor unit at the front of the module which measures the area physically and sends an analog signal to the second unit, the amplifier. The amplifier amplifies the signal, according to the resistant value of the potentiometer, and sends the signal to the analog output of the module.

The third component is a comparator which switches the digital out and the LED if the signal falls under a specific value.

You can control the sensitivity by adjusting the potentiometer.

Please notice: The signal will be inverted; that means that if you measure a high value, it is shown as a low voltage value at the analog output.

This sensor doesn't show absolute values (like exact temperature in °C or magneticfield strenght in mT). It is a relative measurement: you define an extreme value to a given normal environment situation and a signal will be send if the measurement exceeds the extreme value.

It is perfect for temperature control (KY-028), proximity switch (KY-024, KY-025, KY-036), detecting alarms (KY-037, KY-038) or rotary encoder (KY-026).

Code example Arduino

The program reads the current voltage value which will be measured at the output pin and shows it via serial interface.

Additional to that, the status of the digital pin will be shown at the terminal which means if the extreme value was exceeded or not.

```
// Declaration and initialization of the input pin
int Analog_Eingang = A0; // X-axis-signal
int Digital_Eingang = 3; // Button

void setup ()
{
```

KY-038 Microphone sound sensor module

```

pinMode (Analog_Eingang, INPUT);
pinMode (Digital_Eingang, INPUT);

Serial.begin (9600); // Serial output with 9600 bps
}

// The program reads the current value of the input pins
// and outputs it via serial out
void loop ()
{
  float Analog;
  int Digital;

  // Current value will be read and converted to voltage
  Analog = analogRead (Analog_Eingang) * (5.0 / 1023.0);
  Digital = digitalRead (Digital_Eingang);

  //... and outputted here
  Serial.print ("Analog voltage value:"); Serial.print (Analog, 4); Serial.print ("V, ");
  Serial.print ("Extreme value:");

  if(Digital==1)
  {
    Serial.println (" reached");
  }
  else
  {
    Serial.println (" not reached yet");
  }
  Serial.println ("-----");
  delay (200);
}

```

Connections Arduino:

digital Signal	= [Pin 3]
+V	= [Pin 5V]
GND	= [Pin GND]
analog Signal	= [Pin 0]

Example program download

[ARD_Analog-Sensor](#)

Code example Raspberry Pi**!! Attention !! Analog Sensor !! Attention !!**

Unlike the Arduino, the Raspberry Pi doesn't provide an ADC (Analog Digital Converter) on its Chip. This limits the Raspberry Pi if you want to use a non digital Sensor.

To evade this, use our *Sensorkit X40* with the *KY-053* module, which provides a 16 Bit ADC, which can be used with the Raspberry Pi, to upgrade it with 4 additional analog input pins. This module is connected via I2C to the Raspberry Pi.

It measures the analog data and converts it into a digital signal which is suitable for the Raspberry Pi.

So we recommend to use the KY-053 ADC if you want to use analog sensors along with the Raspberry Pi.

For more information please look at the infosite: [KY-053 Analog Digital Converter](#)

KY-038 Microphone sound sensor module

!! Attention !! Analog Sensor !! Attention !!

The program uses the specific ADS1x15 and I2C python-libraries from the company Adafruit to control the ADS1115 ADC. You can find these here: [<https://github.com/adafruit/Adafruit-Raspberry-Pi-Python-Code>] published under the BSD-License [Link]. You can find the needed libraries in the lower download package.

The program reads the current values of the input pins and outputs it at the terminal in [mV].

Additional to that, the status of the digital pin will be shown at the terminal to show if the extreme value was exceeded or not.

```
#####
### Copyright by Joy-IT
### Published under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported License
### Commercial use only after permission is requested and granted
###
### KY-053 Analog Digital Converter - Raspberry Pi Python Code Example
###
#####

# This code is using the ADS1115 and the I2C Python Library for Raspberry Pi
# This was published on the following link under the BSD license
# [https://github.com/adafruit/Adafruit-Raspberry-Pi-Python-Code]
from Adafruit_ADS1x15 import ADS1x15
from time import sleep

# import needed modules
import math, signal, sys, os
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)
GPIO.setwarnings(False)

# initialise variables
delayTime = 0.5 # in Sekunden

# assigning the ADS1x15 ADC
ADS1015 = 0x00 # 12-bit ADC
ADS1115 = 0x01 # 16-bit

# choosing the amplifying gain
gain = 4096 # +/- 4.096V
# gain = 2048 # +/- 2.048V
# gain = 1024 # +/- 1.024V
# gain = 512 # +/- 0.512V
# gain = 256 # +/- 0.256V

# choosing the sampling rate
# sps = 8 # 8 Samples per second
# sps = 16 # 16 Samples per second
# sps = 32 # 32 Samples per second
# sps = 64 # 64 Samples per second
# sps = 128 # 128 Samples per second
# sps = 250 # 250 Samples per second
# sps = 475 # 475 Samples per second
# sps = 860 # 860 Samples per second

# assigning the ADC-Channel (1-4)
adc_channel_0 = 0 # Channel 0
adc_channel_1 = 1 # Channel 1
adc_channel_2 = 2 # Channel 2
adc_channel_3 = 3 # Channel 3
```

KY-038 Microphone sound sensor module

```

# initialise ADC (ADS1115)
adc = ADS1x15(ic=ADS1115)

# Input pin for the digital signal will be picked here
Digital_PIN = 24
GPIO.setup(Digital_PIN, GPIO.IN, pull_up_down = GPIO.PUD_OFF)

#####

# #####
# main program loop
# #####
# The program reads the current value of the input pin
# and shows it at the terminal

try:
    while True:
        #Current values will be recorded
        analog = adc.readADCSingleEnded(adc_channel_0, gain, sps)

        # Output at the terminal
        if GPIO.input(Digital_PIN) == False:
            print "Analog voltage value:", analog, "mV, ", "extreme value: not reached"
        else:
            print "Analog voltage value:", analog, "mV, ", "extreme value: reached"
            print "-----"

        sleep(delayTime)

except KeyboardInterrupt:
    GPIO.cleanup()

```

Connections Raspberry Pi:

Sensor

digital signal	= GPIO 24	[Pin 18 (RPI)]
+V	= 3,3V	[Pin 1 (RPI)]
GND	= GND	[Pin 06 (RPI)]
analog signal	= Analog 0	[Pin A0 (ADS1115 - KY-053)]

ADS1115 - KY-053:

VDD	= 3,3V	[Pin 01]
GND	= GND	[Pin 09]
SCL	= GPIO03 / SCL	[Pin 05]
SDA	= GPIO02 / SDA	[Pin 03]
A0	= look above	[Sensor: analog signal]

Example program download

[KY-038_Microphone_sensor_module_RPi](#)

To start, enter the command:

KY-038 Microphone sound sensor module

```
sudo python KY-038_Microphone_sensor_module_RPir.py
```

Annex 12. Fitxa Tècnica Micròfon ME66-K6

ME 66

Microphones | Back-Electret Microphone Head Suitable for K6 and K6P Powering Modules

Cat. No. 003284

General Description

The ME 66 is a short gun microphone head designed for use with the K6 and K6P powering modules. It is especially suitable for reporting, film and broadcast location applications and for picking up quiet signals in noisy or acoustically live environments as it discriminates against sound not emanating from the main pick-up direction. Matt black, anodised, scratch-resistant finish.

Pictured with K6 powering module and cable (available separately)

Features

- Super-cardioid/lobar pick-up pattern
- Highly directional
- Low inherent self-noise
- High sensitivity
- Wide frequency response
- Delivery includes: 1 ME 66

Recommended Accessories

- MZW 66 foam windshield
- MZW 66 pro foam windshield

Cat. No. 003704

Cat. No. 003712

Technical Data

Pick-up pattern	super-cardioid/lobar
Frequency response	40 – 20,000 Hz ± 2.5 dB
Sensitivity (free field, no load) (1 kHz)	50 mV/Pa ± 2.5 dB
Nominal impedance	200 Ω (with K6)
Min. terminating impedance	1 kΩ (with K6)
Equivalent noise level	
A-weighted (DIN IEC 651)	10 dB
CCIR-weighted (CCIR 468-3)	21 dB
Max. SPL (1 kHz)	126 dB (THD = 1 %)
Dimensions	∅ 22.5 x 221 mm
Weight	65 g

Profile

Super-cardioid/lobar (short gun) microphone head suitable for K6 and K6P powering modules. Frequency response 40 – 20,000 Hz ± 2.5 dB, sensitivity (free field, no load) 50 mV/Pa ± 2.5 dB at 1 kHz, nominal impedance 200 Ω (with K6), min. terminating impedance 1 kΩ (with K6), equivalent noise level A-weighted 10 dB, CCIR-weighted 21 dB, max. SPL 126 dB at 1 kHz (THD = 1 %), dimensions ∅ 22.5 x 221 mm, weight 65 g.

Annex 13. Fitxa de sol·licitud d'ocupació a la via pública

Una vegada emplenat i guardat el document al vostre ordinador, haureu de continuar en funció de les instruccions del tràmit.

Ajuntament de Barcelona

SOL·LICITUD DE LLICÈNCIA
D'OCUPACIÓ DE LA VIA PÚBLICA

V P

Districte: L'Eixample	1. Núm. d'Arxiu:	2. Núm. Expedient:
3. Dades del sol·licitant:		
Cognoms i nom sol·licitant o raó social: Cristina Sanuy Hereter		DNI/CIF: [REDACTED]
Adreça: [REDACTED]	Núm.: [REDACTED]	Portal: [REDACTED] Escala: [REDACTED] Pis: [REDACTED] Porta: [REDACTED]
Població: Barcelona	Codi postal: [REDACTED]	Tel.: [REDACTED]
4. Dades del representant i de notificació:		
Cognoms i nom del representant: -		DNI/CIF: -
Adreça: -	Núm.: -	Portal: - Escala: - Pis: - Porta: -
Població: -	Codi postal: -	Qualitat representació: -

El que subscriu, les dades del qual consten en el requadre 3,

Manifesta: Que acompanya la documentació preceptiva per tramitar la sol·licitud de **Llicència d'ús comú especial de la Via Pública** per a l'activitat i/o instal·lació que s'esmenta als requadres 6 i 7, i

Sol·licita: Que se li atorgui l'autorització per realitzar l'activitat i/o instal·lació descrita.

Que, quan comuniqui formalment haver realitzat els treballs i/o instal·lacions necessaris, es giri, si s'escau, la reglamentària vista de comprovació, autoritzant-lo a exercir l'activitat amb les característiques indicades al requadre 10.

Firma del Sol·licitant:

Barcelona, 16 de abril de 2024

Atenció, no signeu digitalment aquest document.

- Tramitació sense certificat digital: imprimiu dues còpies del document i signeu-lo manualment.
- Tramitació amb certificat digital: més endavant signareu digitalment el formulari on s'annexarà aquest document.

"Les dades identificatives que figurin en les instàncies seran incloses en un fitxer automatitzat, del qual és titular el Registre General de l'Ajuntament i Registres descentralitzats de cada dependència dependents orgànicament dels Sectors d'Actuació i dels Districtes corresponents, amb la finalitat d'enregistrar les entrades de documents en la Corporació Municipal, i atendre la petició del ciutadà, i donar-los el tractament d'acord amb la Llei Orgànica 15/1999, de 13 de desembre, de protecció de dades de caràcter personal. L'òrgan que resolgui la instància, donarà compliment, de manera concreta, als extrems que contempla l'article 5 de la LOPD. L'interessat podrà exercir els drets d'accés, rectificació, cancel·lació i oposició davant dels òrgans destinataris de la instància encarregats de tramitar la seva sol·licitud." / "Los datos identificativos que figuren en las instancias quedarán incluidos en un fichero automatizado cuyo titular es el Registro General de l'Ajuntament y Registros descentralizados de cada dependencia adscrita orgánicamente a los Sectores de Actuación y de los Distritos correspondientes, con el fin de registrar las entradas de documentos en la Corporación Municipal, y atender la petición del ciudadano, y darles el tratamiento de acuerdo con la Ley Orgánica 15/1999, de 13 de diciembre, de protección de datos de carácter personal. El órgano que resuelva la instancia dará cumplimiento, de manera concreta, a los extremos que contempla el artículo 5 de la LOPD. El interesado podrá ejercer los derechos de acceso, rectificación, cancelación y oposición ante los órganos destinatarios de la instancia encargados de tramitar su solicitud."

5. Emplaçament: Passeig de Sant Joan	Núm.: 91	Portal: - Escala: - Bloc: - km: -
6. Tipus d'ocupació: Ocupació dins el clavegueram situat a l'emplaçament.	7. Tipus de gestió: Nova llicència	
8. Documentació adjunta: 1, 2, 4, 10, 11, 12, 23.	9. Nom anterior titular: -	

10. Característiques de l'ocupació:		
LONGITUD (m): 4	AMPLADA (m): 0.3	SUPERFÍCIE (m): 4*0.3
INSTAL·LACIÓ (M/F): Mòbil		MODEL INST.: Projecte
(Mòbil o Fixa)		(Projecte o Referència Model)
HORARI DE 09:00 A 13:00 I DE 14:00 A 18:00	DURADA: DE 29/04 A 01/05	TEMPORADA: (A/S/T/M): M (E/H/V/F): H
(Any/Sem/Trim/Mes+Estiu/Hivern/Vigílies/Fires)		
AMPLADA MÍNIMA DE PAS LLIURE (m): 3.2	AMPLADA VORERA (m): 3.2	DISTÀNCIA A LA CANTONADA (m): 2.4
(la més propera)		
TIPUS DE VETLLADOR (T/S/C): Closa	NOMBRE DE VETLLADORS: -	SITUACIÓ PASSEIG (S/N): Passeig
(Terrassa/Semi-closa/Closa)	(1=1 taula+4 cadires)	(Passeig o Andana Central)
MOTIU (Només Reservades i Senyals):	ESTACIONAMENT (Només Reservades): -	
(Núm. de Llicència o Matricula)	(Indicar L/B: en Línia o Bateria)	
PRODUCTES A LA VENDA: -	MOBILIARI URBÀ AFECTAT: Clavegueram	

NORMES PER COMPLIMENTAR LA FITXA TÈCNICA:

Requadres 1 i 2: No complimentar (Reservat per a l'Administració).

Requadre 3: COGNOMS I NOM DEL SOL·LICITANT O RAÓ SOCIAL: Escriure el nom del peticionari.

Requadre 5: EMPLAÇAMENT: Senyalar carrer i número de la instal·lació o de la finca davant la que se situarà aquesta.

Requadres 6 i 7: TIPUS D'OCUPACIÓ I TIPUS DE GESTIÓ: Ha d'escriure, amb la mateixa denominació de la instància, el tipus d'activitat i de gestió que se sol·licita. Exemple: «Quiosc Periòdics» i «Renovació».

Requadre 11: PLÀNOL DE L'EMPLAÇAMENT (Escala 1:200): Ha de grafiar-se, acotant en ell, en una escala 1:200, la finca davant la que s'ubicarà la instal·lació, totes les dimensions que ha indicat a l'apartat 10 de la instància, així com el mobiliari urbà de l'entorn (bústies, cabines, quioscos, etc.).

Exemple:

Requadre 12: No ho complimenti.

Districte: Eixample	1. Núm. d'Arxiu:	2. Núm. expedient:
3. Cognoms i nom del sol·licitant o raó social: Cristina Sanuy Hereter		
5. Emplaçament: Passeig de Sant Joan	Núm. 91	Portal: - Escala: - Bloc: - Km: -
6. Tipus d'ocupació: Ocupació dins el clavegueram situat a l'emplaçament.	7. Tipus de gestió: Nova llicència.	

11. Plànol de l'emplaçament (Escala 1:200)

S'acotaran: amplada vorera, amplada lliure de pas, amplada calçada, la instal·lació, la distància a la cantonada més propera i el mobiliari urbà de l'entorn.

12. Informe tècnic:	Data:
.....
.....
Vist i Plau Cap Nucli O. Via Pública	El Tècnic

Imatge i Serveis Editorials - 2013 / Mod. 209

Annex 14. Documentació per a la instal·lació

**Ajuntament
de Barcelona**

Serveis Urbans i Manteniment de l'Espai Públic
Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua, SA
Direcció General

Acer, 16
08038 - Barcelona
T. 932 896 800
www.bcasa.cat

Nom: Cristina Sanuy Hereter
Entitat: Elisava, Escola Universitària de Disseny i Enginyeria de Barcelona

Us adjuntem condicions de col·laboració:

Requeriments del servei:

- Gravació sonora durant 24h. al clavegueram de Barcelona
- El dia de la gravació serà del 28 al 29 de maig.

Condicions:

1. **Obligació de conèixer i respectar les normes de seguretat** a la xarxa de clavegueram per part de tots els assistents.
2. **El material generat serà exclusiu per a finalitats acadèmiques**, només es podrà utilitzar en l'àmbit de la docència, així ni el centre acadèmic ni els alumnes podran fer ús del material en cap altre context ni es podrà divulgar i/o facilitar a tercers, restant prohibida la seva comercialització.
3. D'acord amb l'article 8 de la Llei 37/2007, de **reutilització de la informació del sector públic**, ha de complir les següents condicions generals:
 - que el contingut de la informació no sigui alterat
 - que no es desnaturalitzi el sentit de la informació
 - que es citi la font: "Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua, SA, Ajuntament de Barcelona"
 - que s'esmenti la data de l'última actualització
4. **Cristina Sanuy és responsable del material tècnic deixat al clavegueram durant 24h.** i assumeix tots els riscos existents. En cap cas Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua es farà responsable de desperfectes o danys materials.

Anul·lació:

Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua, SA pot retardar o cancel·lar la col·laboració en els següents casos:

1. Activació de l'alerta de pluja o necessitats del servei.
2. Si no s'ajusta el Pla de Treball autoritzat prèviament per Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua, SA.
3. Si el sol·licitant no respecta les normes de seguretat a la xarxa de clavegueram.

Declaro estar informada de les normes de seguretat i els riscos existents. Accepto haver llegit i entès les condicions establertes en aquest document.

Signatura i data:

28/05/2024
Cristina Sanuy Hereter

**Ajuntament
de Barcelona**

Serveis Urbans i Manteniment de l'Espai Públic
Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua, SA
Direcció de Planificació i Innovació

Azer, 10
08038 Barcelona
Telèfon: 932 896 820
www.bcasa.cat

Rev. 0

Data: 25 d'octubre de 2023

INFORMACIÓ ALS VISITANTS EN MATÈRIA DE PREVENCIÓ A LA XARXA DE CLAVEGUERAM

En compliment del deure de coordinació d'activitats i amb la finalitat de reduir les possibilitats d'un accident/incident, us informem dels riscos presents a les nostres instal·lacions i de les normes de seguretat que cal seguir durant les visites i en cas d'emergència.

Amb aquest objectiu us lliurem la documentació següent perquè la tingueu en compte:

- Normes de seguretat i riscos existents a la xarxa de clavegueram
- Actuacions en cas d'emergència: visites a la xarxa de clavegueram

Us recordem que aquestes normes són de compliment obligat per a totes les persones visitants.

Específicament, us informem que heu de tenir en compte aquests punts:

- **S'ha de portar pantalons llargs i màniga llarga mentre es fan visites a l'interior de dipòsits, clavegueram i altres llocs que puguin estar bruts d'aigües residuals.**
- **S'han de portar sabates tancades amb sola de goma i cal evitar les sabates amb talons.**
- **Per accedir al clavegueram s'ha de disposar de casc de seguretat.**
- **S'ha d'informar si hi ha persones amb discapacitats o sensibles, per tal de valorar si es pot fer la visita de forma segura incorporant els EPIs necessaris i tenint-ho en compte en cas d'emergència.**
- **Resteu en tot moment amb la persona autoritzada de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA o amb el responsable de la visita. No accediu a llocs per als quals no tingueu autorització. Respecteu l'itinerari de la visita**

Restem a la vostra disposició per a qualsevol aclariment.

Responsable de Seguretat i Salut Laboral
Barcelona Cicle de l'Aigua, SA

NORMES DE SEGURETAT I RISCOS EXISTENTS A LA XARXA DE CLAVEGUERAM

Pel que fa a la seguretat dels visitants, cal esmentar que l'interior de la xarxa de clavegueram és un espai confinat relativament reduït on hi ha aigües fecals, on és probable la presència d'insectes i múnids, i on cal prendre les mesures preventives adients.

Informació sobre els riscos existents al clavegueram

El clavegueram, per les seves característiques, té una sèrie de riscos inherents que han estat detectats en l'avaluació de riscos de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona i BCASA i dels quals us informem

1. Caiguda, cop o atrapament: per arrossegament de corrents d'aigua i/o ofegament per inundació de l'espai de treball. S'ha de respectar rigorosament la prohibició d'entrar al clavegueram quan està activat l'avís de pluja. Davant qualsevol senyal d'emergència i alerta del centre de control es sortirà fora del clavegueram ordenadament, complint el pla d'emergència i evacuació.
2. Atrapaments, cops o impactes: s'ha de seguir l'itinerari establert per a la visita i inspeccionar en tot moment l'entorn per evitar ensopagades. No es pot tocar cap aparell, cable, màquina o eina que hi hagi a la instal·lació.
3. Caigudes a nivell diferent i al mateix nivell: cal caminar sempre a poc a poc per la banqueteta, passarel·la o lloc elevat, sense córrer ni empènyer els altres. No us apropau als llocs on hi hagi risc de caiguda i no hi hagi proteccions. Seguiu en tot moment l'itinerari marcat pel responsable de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona i BCASA. No us aboqueu per la barana de la passarel·la ni de les escales.
4. Trepitades en objectes punxants o superfícies irregulars: cal caminar sempre a poc a poc per la banqueteta, passarel·la o lloc elevat, sense córrer ni empènyer els altres, sobretot si hi ha zones amb terreny irregular.
5. Postures forçades, sobreesforços: cal tenir cura dels moviments en àrees d'espais reduïts.
6. Risc de contacte elèctric: s'ha d'evitar tocar cap cable present al clavegueram i recordar que és un lloc humit i això augmenta aquest risc.
7. Intoxicació per contaminants químics i asfíxia per falta d'oxigen: les aigües residuals, quan fermenten i es descomponen, poden originar l'aparició d'àcid sulfhídric, un gas molt tòxic, i de metà (gas explosiu) i deficiència d'oxigen. Habitualment hi ha perill en llocs amb poca ventilació, però, encara que el lloc sigui un espai molt obert i normalment no contingui aigües residuals (com en el cas dels dipòsits), no podem descartar aquest risc. Per prevenir-lo s'ha disposat un detector de gasos que dona senyal d'alarma quan l'atmosfera no és respirable.
8. Risc biològic: les aigües residuals contenen diversos efluents, alguns dels quals tenen restes de material biològic; per tant, hi ha el risc d'entrar en contacte amb agents biològics, per via dèrmica, inhalatòria o digestiva. Cal seguir les bones practiques següents: evitar tocar-se els ulls, nas o mucoses i, després de la visita, rentar-se les mans.
9. Incendi o explosió dins la xarxa de clavegueram: presència de gasos inflamables poden generar atmosfera explosiva.

L'Ajuntament de Barcelona i BCASA informen d'aquests riscos els assistents a la visita. Per tal de prevenir-los hem establert unes normes de seguretat que cal seguir durant la visita a aquesta infraestructura i que són de compliment obligat per a tots els visitants.

Per a qualsevol dubte sobre els riscos i com prevenir-los, consulteu el personal de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA, o el tècnic de seguretat de BCASA (932 896 800).

Normes de seguretat

1. Respecteu i compliu totes les normes de seguretat indicades en aquest document quan entreu al clavegueram.
2. Resteu en tot moment al costat de la persona autoritzada de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA o del responsable de la visita. No accediu a llocs per als quals no tingueu autorització. Respecteu l'itinerari de la visita.
3. Respecteu estrictament la prohibició de fumar i d'encendre cap tipus de foc. La fermentació de les aigües residuals pot generar metà, i el fet de fumar donaria lloc a un risc d'explosió que hem d'evitar.
4. Així mateix, recomanem no beure, menjar o fumar dins les instal·lacions per raons higièniques. Abans de fer-ho, un cop sortiu fora, cal que us renteu bé les mans.
5. Eviteu tot contacte amb les aigües residuals. Els talls i les ferides que us pugueu fer poden ser via d'entrada d'infeccions.
6. No es permet fer fotografies o gravacions de vídeo sense consentiment previ i per escrit de l'Ajuntament.
7. Circuleu amb precaució i inspeccionant l'entorn per evitar relliscades i cops.
8. No us apropieu a llocs que no tinguin proteccions i on hi hagi risc de caiguda a les aigües residuals o caiguda d'altura.
9. La vestimenta exigida a l'interior del clavegueram consta de pantalons llargs, samarreta de màniga llarga i coll tancat, i calçat tancat amb sola de goma (antilliscant). Hi és totalment prohibit l'accés amb sandàlies o sabates de taló, bermudes i camises de tirants, fins i tot a l'estiu. És prohibit tocar els elements i les instal·lacions de la claveguera.
10. Per accedir a l'interior, l'Ajuntament o BCASA podrà proporcionar el material de seguretat adient en cada cas. Aquest material s'ha de retornar en acabar el servei. El personal propi del clavegueram porta un detector de gasos.
11. L'espai no és recomanat per a embarassades (degut al risc per presència de microorganismes) ni per a persones amb claustrofòbia o amb mobilitat reduïda (espais de mobilitat reduïda).
12. Comuniqueu qualsevol símptoma de malestar, indisposició, etc. al responsable de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA o de la visita, per poder sortir fora.
13. Si teniu cap dubte en relació amb la vostra seguretat, si us plau, no dubteu a consultar-ho amb les persones de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA.
14. La visita pot quedar anul·lada per raons meteorològiques. No es pot accedir al clavegueram en cas de pluja. Es confirmarà la visita un dia abans.

Els visitants han de complir totes les normes i les recomanacions establertes aquí. A més, s'han de fer responsables de tots els danys que puguin produir a les instal·lacions durant la visita a causa d'actuacions incorrectes, imprudències i negligències.

L'Ajuntament de Barcelona i BCASA volen aconseguir un entorn segur i saludable, tant per als seus empleats com per als seus visitants. Si us plau, ajudeu-nos a veïllar per la seguretat de tothom complint els consells següents i donant-los a conèixer als vostres col·laboradors.

ACTUACIONS EN CAS D'EMERGÈNCIA: VISITES A LA XARXA DE CLAVEGUERAM

Aquestes instruccions seran d'utilitat per a tots els visitants a l'hora de fer una evacuació del clavegueram en cas d'emergència.

- En cas que calgui evacuar urgentment el clavegueram, seguïu estrictament les instruccions del personal autoritzat de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA o del responsable de la visita, que us indicarà la sortida d'emergència (es mirarà primer de sortir per l'accés per on s'ha entrat).
- Circuleu amb precaució. Feu tots els moviments de pressa, però sense córrer i sense atropellar ni empènyer els altres. Feu l'evacuació en silenci, amb sentit de l'ordre i d'ajuda mútua, per evitar atropellaments i lesions, i assistiu les persones que tinguin dificultats o que calguin.
- En el cas que en les vies d'evacuació hi hagi algun obstacle que dificulti la sortida, aparteu-lo, si és possible, de manera que no provoqui caigudes a altres persones i que l'objecte no es deteriori.
- En cap cas torneu enrere per buscar companys o objectes personals.
- Mantingueu-vos unit al vostre grup, encara que ja us trobeu a l'exterior, en els llocs convinguts de concentració, per facilitar el control del responsable de la visita.
- El punt de trobada és al davant de la porta d'accés al clavegueram, tothom ha de romandre allà fins que el personal autoritzat de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona o BCASA o el responsable de la visita ho indiquin.

En cas d'emergència per canvi de les condicions atmosfèriques o climatològiques, el personal d'acompanyament donarà avis d'aquest fet. El responsable de la visita acompanyarà els visitants cap a la sortida, i el personal d'acompanyament tancarà el grup.

En cas d'emergència per indisposició d'un visitant, el responsable de la visita ha d'acompanyar la persona indisposada fora del clavegueram, mentre la resta del grup es queda a dins amb els altres responsables o personal d'acompanyament.

En cas que no es pugui evacuar el visitant indisposat, es procedirà a aturar la visita. Cal donar prioritat a l'aplicació dels procediments de primers auxilis i als avisos a emergència. Quan sigui viable, s'evacuarà la resta de visitants.

La responsabilitat de la gestió del grup correspon al responsable de la visita, tot i que disposarà de l'ajut del personal d'acompanyament per resoldre l'incident o emergència.

